

Exploring Virtual Worlds with Disabled Communities:

An explorative study on immersive media benefits within a disabled community in Paisley

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Contents

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	3
ABSTRACT	7
CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION	9
1.1 Framework of the project:.....	9
1.2 The studentship & personal motivation:.....	10
1.3 Positionality:	13
1.4 Assistive technologies:.....	16
1.5 Contextualising VR:.....	17
1.6 Aims:	21
1.7 Research questions:.....	22
1.8 Overview of methods and methodologies:	22
1.9 Originality and Contribution to Knowledge:	25
1.10 Structure of the thesis:.....	26
CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW	29
2.1 The path towards independent living	29
2.2 Crip Theory a tool for disability empowerment:	36
2.3 Disability, Health, and Wellbeing:.....	38
2.4 The power of contemplation: Nature’s healing properties	40
2.4.1 The healing properties of meditation:.....	48
2.5 The Human who plays	51
2.5.1 Game Theory	51
2.5.2 Theories of Play	56
2.5.3 Serious Games and Gamification:.....	61
2.5.4 Disability Gaming:.....	64
2.6 The human who rites.....	66

2.6.1	Routines and Habits, shades of consciousness.....	69
2.7	The medium is the reality	72
2.7.1	The road towards the metaverse	74
2.7.2	The fundamentals of Immersion in VR:	77
2.7.3	VR benefits for wellbeing	82
2.8	Trust, invaluable currency within interpersonal relationships for research purposes.	84
2.9	Gaps and research opportunities of interest:.....	85
CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY		88
3.1	Introduction and overview:	88
3.1.1	Rationale for Qualitative Research approach:.....	89
3.1.2	Rationale for exploratory ethnographic approach:	90
3.1.3	Rationale for Participatory action Research approach:.....	92
3.1.4	Rational for practice-based research (PBR) methodology:	95
3.2	Research Sample:	100
3.2.1	Focus groups sampling:	100
3.3	Overview of information needed:.....	101
3.4	Research Design overview:	102
3.4.1	Literature Review:	103
3.4.2	Transfer Status to PhD Candidate:	103
3.5	Data-Collection Methods:.....	103
3.5.1	Phase One: Ethnographies during groups or sessions.....	104
3.5.2	Phase Two: Pilot Study	106
3.5.3	Phase Three: Focus groups, user test and artifacts building	107
3.5.4	A resume of the creation of the artifacts	109
3.5.5	Materials:.....	110
3.5.6	Participatory user test protocol:.....	112
3.6	Data Analysis and Synthesis:	114
3.6.1	Ethics of engaging on this research:	117
3.7	Issues of trustworthiness:.....	122
3.7.1	Rational for credibility:	122
3.7.2	Rational for Transferability:.....	123
3.7.3	Rational for dependability:	124
3.7.4	Rational confirmability:	124
3.8	Methodological limitations of the Study:.....	125
3.9	Chapter Summary:.....	125
CHAPTER 4: MEETING THE DRC		127

4.1	The Community	127
4.2	Leaders, gatekeepers & negotiating access	131
4.3	Pilot study	137
4.3.1	“A place to visit” workshop - Tue 15 th March 2018:.....	139
4.3.2	“VR Docs for empathy” workshop - Tue 20 th March 2018:	140
4.3.3	“Hands-on.” Workshop - Tue 22 nd March 2018:	141
4.3.4	Reflection and results of the pilot study	143
 CHAPTER 5: PRODUCE – TUNE INTO NATURE		149
5.1	Rituals at the DRC	149
5.1.1	The Creative & Production process:	153
5.1.2	Finding healing landscapes:.....	156
5.1.3	Consultations and testing:.....	158
5.1.4	Results and findings:.....	170
 CHAPTER 6: DISCOVERY - MEMORY GAME		174
6.1	“Discovery”: the Creative & Production process:	181
6.1.1	Discovery Game Concept:.....	183
6.1.2	Discovery task-based usability test, DRC.....	189
6.1.3	Results and findings:.....	197
 CHAPTER 7: DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS		200
7.2	Disabling barriers caused by VR Hardware	201
7.3	Discussion of the meaning of the findings:	202
7.4	Conclusion:	205
7.4.1	Key contributions:	211
7.4.2	Limitations of the study:.....	212
7.4.3	Recommendations:.....	215
7.4.4	Further work.....	217
 REFERENCES		220
 LIST OF FIGURES:		236
 LIST OF TABLES:		238
 APPENDICES:		239

Abstract

This thesis explores the implementation of virtual reality (VR) in a disabled community in Paisley, Scotland. It aims to understand what cultural benefits are derived from this intervention and promote health and wellbeing. Employing real-time digital 3D graphics, immersive media can take the viewer's attention away from the currently inhabited space to a Virtual Reality (VR). While VR has been used to assist various groups, its potential to enhance the lives of the elderly and disabled remains understudied.

The study began with an initial stage of ethnographic research, where the researcher gathered first-hand observations into the reality of a disabled community. This exploration set the foundation for the subsequent step, which employs a participatory action research (PAR) approach. Stakeholders were actively engaged in testing and consultation sessions, allowing participants to voice their opinions and take a co-steering role in developing the VR experiences.

Through negotiations with the community, the researcher created two customised simulations using 360-degree filming and computing software. These simulations were designed to cater to the specific needs and perspectives of the disabled community. In the concluding phase of the in-situ studies, participants' moods were self-reported before and after experiencing the VR interventions.

Following the implementation of the immersive media, results indicated an improvement in mood and increased comfort of the participants. This suggests that VR technology has the potential to bring positive benefits to disabled communities. However, this study also makes emphasis on the need for further research and exploration in this area. Additionally, the study advocates for the practical applications of immersive media in a social care setting, using accessible hardware, and highlights the importance of involving end-users in the development process.

Please, insert your mobile phone in a headset to preview whenever you see this logo, after scanning the QR code.

Chapter 1: Introduction

The Disability Resource Centre in Paisley (DRC) functions as a vibrant community that fosters solidarity among people with disabilities and sensory impairments residing in the Renfrewshire local authority in Scotland. It does this by adhering to a model where the DRC empowers its members to have control over the service they receive, thereby dismantling barriers that hinder their participation. This research aims to investigate the potential applications of Virtual Reality (VR) within this space for their benefit and other similar communities. It specifically focuses on addressing the needs of people with physical disabilities within the DRC, including them in the co-creation process of new audio-visual immersive experiences, rather than relying on pre-existing immersive experiences to promote health and wellbeing.

1.1 Framework of the project

As explained later in this thesis (see **Error! Reference source not found.**), Centres for Independent Living are a solution to provide access to people with disabilities to a place where they can find strength in numbers, advocate for their rights, supply and find information that benefits all members. Such centres, like the Disability Resource Centre in Paisley, are run by and for physically and sensory impaired people to reach their personal and community goals, encouraging them to speak and act to remove barriers that can lead to societal marginalisation.

The DRC exemplifies a user-centric organisation, wherein a significant proportion of the committee of directors, employees, and volunteers are people with disabilities or sensory impairments. Consequently, they possess a profound comprehension of the intricate nuances of the independent living movement. Furthermore, many community members actively participate in the DRC's daily decision-making processes and routine functional activities. This dynamic engagement both imparts direction and purpose to their lives and establishes a reciprocal relationship, whereby the institution is partly administered by and for individuals with disabilities.

The community at the DRC is comprised mainly of adults with physical disabilities. However, while it is hard to illuminate every single condition, during my visits, I also encountered people with varying degrees of hearing, visual impairment, and deaf and blind people. These impairments or disabilities could have been congenital, as well as those resulting or acquired later in life. This project understands disability as just one of the tones in the melody of human experience; with this always present, this project aims to identify opportunities to adapt VR to the wishes and needs of the people at the DRC by establishing a dialogue to empower them to engage with VR and participate in the creation of experiences made for them, while understanding that not all people with disabilities have the same experiences or respond to VR in the same manner.

1.2 The studentship & personal motivation:

This doctoral project is an “Applied Research Collaborative Studentship” (ARCS). This innovative collaborative partnership scheme promotes collaboration among two Scottish higher education institutions (HEI) as part of the Scottish Graduate School for the Arts and Humanities (SGSAH). The two HEIs are the University of the West of Scotland and the University of Edinburgh, working with an external partner based in Scotland, in this case, the Disability Resource Centre in Paisley (DRC). The vision is to become a catalyst for fruitful exchange among these three, leading to the exchange and production of knowledge. The motion of these mechanics, in turn, provides doctoral students with soft skills and fieldwork experience beyond the academic setting to extend further their skills related to research and employability within the respective practical fields.

The topic of *“Exploring Virtual Worlds with Disabled Communities”* was set up as an action research project to explore an issue that needed and needs further exploration. The reasoning behind my application for this studentship, while multiple, was initially to do with my interest in immersive interactive media forms and the fact that I could work on exploring the uses of VR

within this context and creating meaningful experiences for the well-being of others. This might be because I want to create and tinker, and I wish also to support others with my work. This might have started with an educational experience back home, in Venezuela, my country of origin. Every high school student in their final year needed to engage in two hundred hours of social work. In fulfilment of this requirement, I actively participated as a teacher's helper in a school catering to the needs of children with physical disabilities. This invaluable opportunity granted me a foundational understanding of the operational dynamics within an inclusive educational institution whilst also witnessing the realities experienced by these children and their educators. Consequently, I developed a more nuanced comprehension of disability as an integral facet of the broader human experience; I also felt a sense of being part of something great. I am grateful for this experience, as it brought new perspectives.

I have always believed that people possess an intrinsic internal dialogue that shapes their sense of self and determines their values. Through my involvement in this social work, I experienced a profound sense of usefulness and felt satisfied from my contributions. This engagement imbued me with a sense of agency, instilling within me the conviction that I could affect meaningful change in society, helping me build a narrative of the self where I seek to contribute to other people's lives positively, and showed me that working to support others can be a valid career path. Furthermore, during my university application process, I sought to pursue studies in creative computing while also considering social work at the same University as a potential study area. Eventually, I opted for creative computing as my chosen path; my passion for video games and digital interactive art drove me throughout my undergraduate studies in creative computing at Goldsmiths, London. I became engrossed in various projects to creatively use computing for the good of people, such as the development of therapeutic prototypes (see Fig. 1), the design of a musical instrument for the recovery of the hand's fine motor movement, and my culminating project centred on the utilisation of immersive virtual reality to construct an artistic installation intended to illuminate the challenges associated within the autism spectrum. After my Creative Computing degree, I undertook a Master's in Serious Games and Virtual Reality; before the end of the academic year, I saw the advert for the PhD, and after

reading it, I instantly felt it was the right path for me as its main components resonated within me: creative technologies and improving the lives of people with disabilities. As a new researcher, I saw this as an occasion to challenge myself in generating new knowledge and shedding light on areas that have not yet been adequately explored. It also provided a chance to immerse myself in fieldwork experiences closely integrated with individuals who possess unique life narratives and perspectives, this way connecting with them and the possibility to adapt a new form of media to their needs and wishes, bringing a new perspective to their lives by allowing them to effectively explore a new technology that would probably be otherwise inaccessible. Satisfying the urge to be helpful to others and merging their lived expertise within the disabled community and my proficiency in the field of Virtual Reality, we had the potential to forge together something to be proud of collaboratively.

Fig. 1 Musical therapy glove, a toy for recovering fine hand motor movement. (Author, 2017)

Expanding on this, what intrigued me about this research project as a user experience designer was the interaction of people with disabilities with immersive computer media to enhance their lives. As seen in Bhugra et al. (2020), according to Bourdieu, cultural capital is one's cultural competencies, including knowledge, to better one's standing in society, and this can be enriched by access to experiences in our surroundings (Bhugra, 2020). Therefore, as a technological artist enthusiastic about creating virtual worlds, I believe that exposure to new ideas, experiences, and concepts through immersive VR could equip individuals with the necessary knowledge to make informed decisions and improve their living conditions. But more intimately, my motivation stemmed from my first-hand experiences as a fellow human being, as neurodiversity constituted a fundamental aspect of my personal experience in my formative

years. I was diagnosed with a condition that caused epilepsy in my early teens and relied upon medication for a long time. However, I would have preferred not to take it due to its effects, which encompassed numbness in my personality and a feeling of drowsiness. I knew it would be dangerous for me not to; thus, I had no alternative but to comply with the medication regime. In addition to that, both my parents possessed medical backgrounds, thereby reinforcing the necessity of adhering to this treatment. I continued with this medication until I eventually moved away from my parents' home. Then, in my adult years, I came to terms with my queerness just before I was diagnosed with a lifelong disability, which felt like coming out for a second time. I believe these situations made me understand other people's lives with more empathy, who, like me, face the challenges of living in a society where your needs and wishes are misunderstood or ignored by the "normal" majority. Maybe this perception I have is due to my Latin American background, a place where disability is a contemporary social construct with roots in colonialism, intricately intertwined with how society functions and continues to perpetuate itself, pursuing the understanding of "normality" through the wide adoption of the medical, charity and religious models (Yarza de los Ríos, et al., 2020). Consequently, I aspire to contribute to establishing a progressive society where people with disabilities are consistently included in decision-making processes that affect their interests. Finally, it is evident that my interest in exploring the intersection between immersive interactive media creation and assistive technology, coupled with my desire to support others, particularly in the context of disability, influenced my inclination to participate in this project.

1.3 Positionality:

People with disabilities have been a part of my life for as long as I can remember. As I mentioned earlier, I live with a disability, and I am a proud, neurodiverse person. Additionally, growing up, I was fortunate to have people whose life stories made disability a little more natural for me. When my siblings and I were children, our father would often share his story of being born with a cleft lip and cleft palate. Despite undergoing surgery, he struggled to speak like others, and he would stammer due to nervousness. This communication difficulty made

him aggressive, as he was subjected to bullying. However, as he grew older, he overcame his fear of speaking and became a great father and a microbiologist. On my mother's side, my great uncle, who was passionate about raising poultry and training fighting roosters, contracted polio at the age of five. As a result, he initially crawled until his parents had enough money so he could start using a wheelchair. Later in life, he was known locally for his poultry farming skills, which allowed him to make a living. Furthermore, two of my cousins are people with autism, each with unique interests and lives that make the stories of our family richer. One loves music and plays in a band, while the other has a passion for math and engineering, a profession he exercises today. I have also witnessed my grandparents and parents developing age-related disabilities and impairments over time. This is just part of the life cycle, and I understand it will happen to me. Therefore, I can confidently say that disability and impairment have always been familiar to me, via the stories of people near me and my own. However, I now realise that these concepts were primarily presented to me through the medical, charity or religious models, which were the prevailing perspectives within my family circle for understanding and discussing these life experiences; these stories are primarily about people who overcame their disabilities to be productive members of society, which is problematic due to the implication that this perspective brings, where disability is seen as undesirable (see section 2.2).

Upon encountering the community for the first time, as I delved into various models for comprehending disability through my reading, I became aware of a potential bias stemming from my upbringing. I took several steps to confront this bias – and my ignorance. Firstly, I acknowledged to myself that it would persist to some extent. Recognising the necessity of approaching the subject matter with an open mind, I re-evaluated my understanding of disability. This involved actively making peers around me help me enact discussions, interviews, and workshops to gain insights and improve myself as a researcher. Today, I have understood that when writing about people with disabilities, using inclusive language is paramount for fair representation. A second step to stop my bias is to implement inclusive language. While I am aware of the debate between “People first” and “Identity first” (NIN, 2023), this is outside of the scope of the thesis; I will be using guidelines from the UK

government, where there is consensus on how one should communicate with or about disabled people, (GOV.UK, 2016). For the scope of this project, this means that I will be using a people-centred language, i.e., “people with disabilities” or “disabled people”, rather than “the disabled”, and a language aiming to empower i.e., “a wheelchair user” rather than “cannot walk”, also I will avoid medical or religious / charity model labelling that reinforces negative stereotypes or depicts them as passive social actors i.e., “patient”, “Victim of a stroke” or “unwell “. Also, I will not use condescending euphemisms, i.e., “Differently abled” or “special”.

I must also emphasise my belief in the transformative power of immersive media and serious games to bring about positive outcomes in people's lives; maybe this is because I am engaged with different VR communities. Also, I have been playing video since the age of six and consider myself a gamer; my training as a software developer has at its core value the belief that future users of hardware and software should be consulted and have a voice in the decision-making process, especially if they come from communities that have been historically marginalised. Despite initially being considered an outsider due to being foreign to the place, not being a person with a visible physical disability and being a student at the start of the project, I was able to establish a significant level of trust with my informants throughout the project, which is often challenging for an outsider to attain. In addition to that, I strived to avoid overinterpreting their feedback. Recognising the significance of preserving the integrity of their perspectives, I remained mindful not to impose my biases or preconceptions onto the qualitative data interpretation as much as possible. The steps I described in the middle of this section are a way of doing that.

Finally, during my work with people with disabilities at the DRC and engaging with the literature such as the models of disability learning about the disability rights movement, I have come to understand how the able body has been idealised, and this idea of ‘normality’ has been forced into each one of us. As a researcher without motor disabilities or sensory impairment, I have confronted misperceptions about these, as explained earlier in this section.

1.4 Assistive technologies:

This thesis is about how the DRC, a forward-looking resource centre for the disabled and physically impaired adults of the Renfrewshire area, encountered immersive VR for the first time. For this reason, I would like to provide some context concerning this from the perspective of this thesis. Under the social model of disability, the societal dimension of the mentioned archetype is a form of disability where an ableist society creates physical and psychological environments that further undermine those living with disabilities, often unwittingly creating a hostile environment and narratives that work against the right of these individuals for flourishing (Barnes, 2020). Their reality forms part of the human experience, providing many benefits to the world (idem).

The conceptual core of technology refers to any tool destined to achieve a practical goal in human life or to transfigure human surroundings (Britannica, 2023). An example could be a player using a controller to interact with pixels on a screen. In this thesis, we can find, as explained by McLuhan (1967, see **Error! Reference source not found.**), that technology is not only a medium to meet a result, but this medium becomes itself the message, shifting the paradigms of the predominant symbolic domain, and including within itself the previous medium. Media technologies are a medium to help us perform actions beyond our capabilities, but in their path, they also change cultural and physical spaces. For example, media allows us to communicate, inform, teach, and learn. Nonetheless, with some caveats, we adapt ourselves and our surroundings to the characteristics of the media forms; an example of this is the transition of electrical appliances in houses to be able to have light at night to read; in this case, the media was electricity and cities required pipes and cabling, likewise houses sockets to accommodate this media, therefore transforming the spaces around it to accommodate it.

Assistive Technology (AT) or adaptive technologies refer to tools or media developed to make things possible for people with impairments; humanity has used prosthetics as assistive technologies for thousands of years (Draycott, 2022). Today, for example, AT bridges the gaps created by disability, allowing access to the internet and other media to those who experience it. Through information and communication technologies, disabled people can access information about their rights, governance, and welfare (Nagendran, et al., 2021). Assistive technologies can also be affordable and effective; in the form of wearables, they can be used in the monitoring of body signals, such as breathing, body motion or speech, among others, to control nearby devices (Khoshmanesh, et al., 2021), and AT are widely considered as central to achieve the goals of the CRPD, in the effort to close the disability gap (Smith, et al., 2022). Furthermore, I consider that immersive media has the power to be the ultimate assistive technology when tailored to the needs of the users and provide virtual spaces where people with physical disabilities can train, work, relax and learn on their terms, using sensors or controllers to interact with the surrounding areas, avatars or characters, this way levelling the playing field. While the metaverse is not a fully developed space just yet, possibilities for people with disabilities to engage with these spaces on their terms are being built, and this project is part of that process by using assistive technologies such as adaptive controllers (see Chapter 5).

1.5 Contextualising VR:

In this section, I illustrate the current discussion around Virtual Reality. to pave the way for further exploration within the literature review. Our minds interpret the world around us by translating our senses' input. Ultimately, people's reality is built by their perception of the authentic world and social consensus. In contrast, Virtual Reality (VR) is a digital representation of environments and milieus. In other words, VR is a virtual world where, in theory, anything that could exist in our world could be credited to computer code that virtually casts them into existence within virtual worlds. It can be accessed using computer media, fooling our senses, hence placing the viewer in a parallel reality, except that it's not at

the same level as our own. Therefore, VR has become the ultimate philosophical frontier of our time (Metzinger, 2018).

The idea of alternate realities has been part of the fictional collective culture for a long time; for example, in the short classic science fiction story *Pygmalion's Spectacles* (Grauman W, 1935) plot tells a series of events where the main character can immerse himself in the occurrences of a movie, interacting and using his senses every time he wears these spectacles imbued with the strange power of creating these holograms; this sci-fi tale is often thought of as the foretelling of modern Head Mounted Displays or HMDs. The history of VR formally started in the year 1838, which saw the birth of stereoscopic photos & viewers by the hand of Charles Wheatstone, which relies upon the insight that the brain processes a single object of three dimensions from two different 2D images (Kao, et al., 2020).

Building upon this idea, photographer Wilhelm Gruber introduced the View-Master at the New York World's Fair in 1939 (Gruber, 1940). The View-Master was commercially launched in 1942, becoming a financial success: this was because of its appeal as a photo viewer for tourism and the US military understanding the possibilities of this product for training and education purposes, making a substantial acquisition for this intent at the end of the Second World War. Within the next decade, however, it became an educational toy for children (Sell, 2006).

At the end of the 1950s, a prototype mechanical kiosk-like device where users could experience stereoscopic view, body tilting, stereo sound, incorporating tracks for wind and aromas to be triggered during viewing was built with five different movies; in this way, creating a device that could stimulate many sensory systems at once, this was the "Sensorama" (Heilig, 1962). In the 1960s, VR was born with a stereo head-mounted display and images generated by computer graphics in the fully immersive form we recognise today. However, it did not feature interactivity; its name was the "Telesphere Mask" (Heilig, 1957). Later, in 1965, Ivan Sutherland published a paper outlining the creation of the "Ultimate

Display”, where he first introduced the community of computer graphics academics seminal ideas to what would be later known as VR (Sutherland, 1965).

The decade of 1990 saw many milestones for Virtual Reality, among those the creation of the CAVE system (Cruz-Neira, Fernández and Portalés, 2018). The 1990s also saw the popularisation of the term Virtual Reality (VR); Jaron Lanier pushed forward this term in the same period the laboratory he was cofounding, LPV labs, were producing items such as the “Data Glove” (Zimmerman & Lanier, 1989) that would be later implemented by NASA for their VR system “The Virtual Interface Environment Workstation” (VIEW) in 1990, many other ventures popularised VR Technologies, including the SEGA VR (Patent Pending), a head-mounted display for the Mega Drive which cancelled before production (Loowod, 2023).

At the beginning of the 2000s, questions about whether virtual reality could be a tool for research and motor rehabilitation therapy were raised; one answer to this was a group of papers that were finally put together in a journal (Keshner, 2004). In these papers, it was demonstrated that VR extends our ability to influence the nervous system. They also address critical questions of how VR could be used for physical rehabilitation research and finally confirm the equivalence between the natural environment and the virtual environment on motor performance.

In 2011, Palmer Luckey started a crowdfunded “kick-starter” campaign to produce the Oculus Rift (Palmer, et al., 2013). This was a success; the project received \$2,437,429 from 9,522 backers. On March 25, 2014, Mark Zuckerberg announced that Facebook (subsequently renamed Meta) would be acquiring Oculus VR for 2 billion dollars. Then, in 2015, Google Cardboard was released, exposing immersive technologies to the masses, and feeding into the mass collective consciousness of Virtual Reality (Monteiro, et al., 2015). These virtual worlds can be interacted with using appliances designed for this purpose.

Furthermore, the experiences are made following images, physics and affordance rules that hold an uncanny resemblance to those in our world.

Currently, within the mainstream culture, Virtual Reality is associated with immersive VR using head-mounted displays (HMD); however, in the past, the term VR has also been implemented to encompass an array of media technologies such as multi-projected environments as the CAVE system, panel screens depicting virtual environments, Global Positioning Systems (GPS), and 3D spatial audio among others (Laurel, 2016). However, since 2014, when the social media company formerly known as Facebook, known today as Meta, acquired Oculus, the term “Cross-Realities” (XR) started to gain traction. The term XR is used to encompass all forms of virtual realities mentioned and more, where the “X” represents the unknown number value of digital realities crossing our own (Rauschnabel et al., 2022). However, it’s also worth mentioning that “Extended Realities” is a parallel definition of XR, meaning that our reality is extended in a continuum starting with Augmented Reality (AR) which overlays computer-generated images (CGI) over the real world, followed by Mixed Reality (MR) which allows CGI to interact with the real world and vice versa and finally VR which immerses the user fully into a simulation (Stanney, et al., 2021). Because of the topic of this project, I prefer the term VR to differentiate immersive Virtual Reality from the term XR (Cross Realities). Additionally, I prefer to use the term “Cross – Realities” over “Extended Realities” as the latter’s continuum concept is very ocular and does not give the same importance to other forms of digital realities, such as Spatial Audio, which could be a form of XR adapted for people who are blind for example.

Creating cases worth of attention and study, these technologies, whose purpose is to authenticate, could assert differences in a medium like cyberspace, whose nature replicates signals to communicate (Lydiate, 2021). These technologies are becoming adopted as building blocks towards constructing the virtual environment known as the metaverse, a digital space where the internet meets XR. This comprises many subspaces that might resemble our world, where headsets, mobile phones, consoles, and PCs are gateways to these digital spaces.

While the classic VR headset and controllers pose a challenge to the ease of access of people with physical disabilities and other impaired and disabled experiences due to their ableist design (Gerling & Spiel, 2021), in essence, these immersive technologies provide opportunities for all. VR is becoming a feasible alternative to on-demand experiences in fields beyond gaming and demonstrating this by pushing the envelope by becoming an alternative to life experiences in education, training, mental and physical health, and the visual arts, even proving positive immersion effects in adults with long term cognitive issues (Kim & Pang Yanghee, 2019 , Appel, et al., 2020). Furthermore, immersive VR has become a tool for researchers to explore and create customisable visualisation instruments. In this manner, investigators can recreate a study augmenting portability, reducing cost, and obtaining results closer to reality if compared to other methods (Hamad & Jia, 2022).

1.6 Aims:

This project has four main aims. The first aim is to expand our understanding of immersion and the relationship of living with a physical disability in the 'real world' compared to the sense of agency in the 'Virtual World'; this is undertaken through an ethnographic exploration of the people's lives within the community.

Second, to further the objective comprehension of working with immersive media and interactive technologies, this aim was pursued under the accessibility framework.

Third, to promote the advancement of co-creation and co-development with disabled communities, promoting digital literacy.

The fourth aim was to co-create and co-develop bespoke VR prototype experiences that could be used as part of the care regime and sessions at the DRC, aiming to move service users from test subjects to participants (see 3.1.3). This journey would serve the overall purpose of understanding the immersion and engagement intrinsic to these artefacts and discerning how

these media could be implemented at the DRC—potentially serving as a model for other similar settings.

1.7 Research questions:

RQ.1: What is the relationship between the virtual agency afforded by immersive technologies and the experience and restricted agency of living with a disability?

RQ.2: What are the cultural benefits of using VR in this community?

RQ.3: How can immersive media be integrated into the services disabled communities provide?

RQ.3a: What creative and production processes are behind creating an immersive experience tailored to a service centre like the DRC?

1.8 Overview of methods and methodologies:

The present study adopts a practice-based and exploratory approach as its overarching methodology. The principal research methodology employed is ethnographic, with a particular focus on engagement within the context of the Disability Resource Centre (DRC). This methodology was executed across three distinct phases:

During Phase One (see 3.5), the research process unfolded in two interconnected segments. Initially, I engaged in the immersive process of visiting the centre, allowing for the establishment of rapport and a sense of community while concurrently documenting ethnographic accounts. This engagement involved active participation within various community groups, occasionally introducing VR experiences for consideration. Subsequently, I designed workshops to provide participants with a curated selection of VR experiences adequate to the DRC setting. This phase proved instrumental in informing subsequent implementations and addressing multifaceted research inquiries. In alignment with RQ.1, this phase yielded insights into prevailing disabilities within the DRC community, elucidating the

interplay between these disabilities and individual agencies. Furthermore, it laid the groundwork for exploring the potential of VR to improve their sense of wellbeing. A specific focus on mobility emerged because of recognising VR's distinctive capacity to create illusory spatial transformations. Given the expected prevalence of diverse physical disabilities within the population, this thematic emphasis was substantiated. Notably, in unity with Rabinow's perspective on ethnographies as interpretive representations of reality (1996), these ethnographic reflections facilitated a profound comprehension of the DRC's culture. This encompassed insights into social actors, their attributes, ideologies, routines, values, norms, and spatial interactions within the institution. These understandings proved pivotal in delineating the benefits stemming from VR interventions over time, thereby addressing RQ.2. Additionally, this phase laid the groundwork for investigating the practical implementation of immersive media within the DRC, along with the attendant creative production processes necessary to address R.Q.3 and 3a.

The transition from Phase One to the next witnessed the integration of creative interaction design production methodologies aimed at addressing RQ.3a, such as Personas, Scenarios, and Storyboards that represented the DRC community: i.e., the Personas description included an array of identities of people with disabilities as part of their characteristics. I made consultation accessible by bringing the simulations to the DRC. I implemented a process of Participatory Action Research (PAR), ensuring alignment with the needs of individuals with disabilities, a consideration often neglected in previous research endeavours (Oswal, 2019).

Rather than being interested solely in the production of artifacts, the Arts and Humanities research in the UK is primarily concerned with the definition of the research and the use of artefacts to produce knowledge and its process (AHRC, 2019). The two consecutive phases revolved around creating immersive media for and with the disabled community in the spirit of the slogan “nothing about us without us” (See 2.1). Framed within this reasoning, I resorted to a mixed method between arts and human-computer interaction design, as it appeared to

complement my abilities naturally. Eventually, I discovered how these methods could bridge the communication gap between theory and practice thinking, taking a position halfway between the logical thinking of traditional social research and the more subjective interpretation of approaches drawn the arts and design, as seen in Skains (2018).

As previously explained, my research process incorporates ethnographies as a foundational element to investigate the experiences of DRC service users. These ethnographic investigations serve as a conduit to document the impacts of VR engagements on participants' wellbeing and interactions with immersive digital stimuli. Within this framework, two distinct VR experiences were co-created during the research process. These creations were guided by user-centred design principles and an iterative integration of participant perspectives and experiences garnered through participant observation during workshops. This iterative approach aligned with a cyclical iteration model reminiscent of the classical System Development Cycle paradigm to ensure flexibility (see Chapter 3.1). The second phase entailed crafting a 360° video application centred on mindfulness, through focused breathing, accompanied by the illusory transformation of the location to rural landscapes within the west of Scotland. An interactive game experience tailored to memory training was conceptualised and realised in the subsequent phase.

These artefacts were integral components of an overarching creative cycle that steered the research trajectory, exploring diverse avenues of engagement with immersive VR environments. Each phase played a pivotal role in generating insights into the potential applications of VR for enhancing well-being, yielding observations of mood enhancement after exposure to specific immersive encounters. Beyond its primary objectives, the research also demonstrated an interest in capturing the cultural benefits of these immersive media experiences. The workshops conducted during the study predominantly addressed R.Q3 by offering valuable insights into successful VR implementations, enriching the overall depiction of VR's potential impact within the community context.

1.9 Originality and Contribution to Knowledge:

This thesis illustrates the importance of the research on exploring VR with and for disabled communities, particularly given the early stage of VR technology. While past research has explored sufficiently VR's potential benefits for humanity (see Literature Review). To my knowledge, a distinct absence of academic investigation exists regarding the use of VR specifically for centres for adults living with disability following the collaborative approaches explained in this thesis. It introduces members of a disabled community to VR, resulting in collaboratively designed virtual environments aligned with participants' preferences. Through iterative consultations, participants shift from passive consumers to active contributors, producing artefacts that authentically reflect their interests, bolstering empowerment and agency. Ultimately, this thesis aims to establish a precedent for immersive media creation that genuinely encompasses the user's perspective. A summary of the contribution to knowledge is as follows. The project

- i. provides empirical evidence for the adoption of Immersive media in Disabled Communities as a form of community-based intervention, aligned with the service user centric model of disability and human rights model of disability (HRM); this thesis establishes VR's safety and effectiveness, setting a precedent for inclusive immersive media adoption, presenting empirical evidence endorsing the implementation of VR as part of services provided in similar institutions.
- ii. illustrates digital avenues where VR can positively influence the perceived health and wellbeing of disabled communities, using VR to surrogate life experiences, such as virtually visiting places inaccessible otherwise.
- iii. examines and adapts the framework of an ableist technology such as VR, providing evidence of the importance of empowering people with disabilities using accessible technologies in the form of adaptable hardware and software, while recognising the

potential of immersive 3D worlds as an inclusive medium in line the human rights model of disability.

- iv. introduces and advocates for adaptive research and development methods, notably the inclusive adaptation of user experience methods with an amalgam of participatory action research and the System development life cycle. These methodologies are essential best practices for crafting interactive media within disabled communities.

1.10 Structure of the thesis:

The introduction chapter serves as a preface to the current research, highlighting the significance of the study and providing an overview of the subsequent chapters.

The second chapter, “Literature Review,” delves into the theoretical foundations that underpin the study. It begins by exploring the concept of disability, tracing its historical development and evolving societal perceptions (Models). The chapter highlights the struggles faced by disabled individuals in an ableist society and their pursuit of independent living conditions. Additionally, it examines the domains of health, wellbeing, and disability, elucidating the intricate interplay between these concepts. Furthermore, the chapter explains the theory behind the benefits natural environments and meditation pose for our wellbeing, to move into the realm of play and ritual as two forms of emotional regulation, to then engaging into the influence of various types of media on human societies and emphasises the role of virtual reality (VR) in shaping perceptions and experiences. It concludes by examining how VR has been employed for health and well-being. Then, there is a short section related to trust within the scope of this project, and finally, the chapter identifies research gaps and potential avenues for future investigation.

The third chapter, “Methodology”, focuses on the methodological considerations of the study. It is divided into three subsections to address distinct aspects of the research approach. The

first subsection explicates the overall research approach and methodology, drawing upon relevant literature and similar projects with comparable processes. The second subsection provides a breakdown of the research methods employed in the study. Lastly, the third subsection discusses elements and considerations related to the research design, including materials and ethical aspects.

Chapter Four, “Meeting the DRC”, represents the first of three fieldwork chapters, recounting the various phases of the project. The chapter begins by outlining the initial contact and relationship established with the stakeholders of the Disability Resource Centre (DRC). It serves as the basis for addressing RQ1. The chapter is structured into three interconnected sections. The first section, "Community," provides an overview of the fieldwork process and the initial phase of studies. The subsequent section, "Leaders, Gatekeepers & Negotiating Access," delves more deeply into the author's work at the DRC, detailing techniques to build rapport and manage relationships. Finally, the "Pilot Study" section explores the experience of creating a series of workshops, including the materials used and the insights gained.

The fifth chapter is called after the first experience created, “Produce – Tune into Nature.” it focuses on the second fieldwork phase, which involves the creation of a meditation app that incorporates immersive VR experiences featuring natural West of Scotland landscapes for breathing mindfulness. This chapter presents the creative and consultation process for developing this experience and the subsequent testing procedures.

The sixth chapter is called “Discovery”; it details the final fieldwork phase, where a serious game was created, incorporating various memory tasks and a digital landscape simulating a theme park with scenes from around the world. The chapter explains the creative and consultation processes in developing this immersive experience and discusses the subsequent testing phase.

The seventh chapter, “Discussion & Conclusions”, comprehensively discusses the research findings, addressing different aspects of the overall research journey. It highlights the

contributions made by the study and critically examines its limitations. Finally, the chapter concludes with final thoughts, presenting potential future research scenarios and avenues for further investigation in immersive media for health and wellbeing.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

The research process has been practice-based and exploratory. It aims to understand the relationship between Immersive Virtual Reality (VR) and "health & wellbeing" in a disabled community within a social care setting such as the DRC, surveying its cultural benefits through an ethnographic approach. I chose a narrative approach to this literature review (Turnbull & Chugh Ritesh, 2023). The goal was to present concepts to establish relationships among studies and ideas across different disciplines correlated to my research to provide enough theoretical discussion on "Exploring Virtual Worlds with Disabled Communities" within three ever dynamic and negotiated concepts: Disability, Health & Wellbeing, and Virtual Reality.

2.1 The path towards independent living

Disability is a term in constant negotiation and part of the human experience. The World Health Organisation (WHO) estimates that there are as many as 1 billion people worldwide living with a form of disability (WHO, 2021). At some point in our lives, each of us might have experienced some form of impairment, or those bodies who arrive at old age will gradually struggle to function, resulting in some form of disability (idem). In the following section, I wish to explain the most relevant models of disability, as identified within disability studies, and how they paved the way for the independent living movement.

In the United Kingdom, under the "Equality Act 2010", you would be disabled "if you have a physical or mental impairment that has a 'substantial' and 'long-term' negative effect on your ability to do normal daily activities" (gov.uk, 2011). Over millennia, Western societies have proposed various conceptual models to explain and reason for disability, many of them identifying people with disabilities as a burden, treating them with prejudiced opinions and attitudes coming from the able-bodied gaze. In this section, I analyse the periods of history in which the most essential constructed models of conceptualising disability were created, as in different scales, they influence how we see disability today.

In the ancient Greco-Roman world, some academic perspectives popularised the idea that it was expected to leave those born with corporeal differences exposed to the elements, or as Plato put it, "mysterious unknown places" (Goldberg & Lippman, 1974). As per their criteria, those born disabled did not have a purpose in society, as rather than producing resources, they were seen to drain them (Husquin, 2023). Newer perspectives tell us that the treatment of those with atypical bodies was not homogeneous through the Greco-Roman world and its different eras and that parents, caregivers and health practitioners would go to great lengths to accommodate and assist new-borns with congenital physical impairment (Sneed, 2021).

Saving resources was not the only reason those born differently were stigmatised. As Charles Taylor puts it, before the Renaissance, the world lived an "enchanted" world (Taylor, 2007): a world of spirits, both good and evil that could affect and possess us. Disabled people were carriers of bad omens, as if being affected by these spirits, drawing attention not only to them but also to their families and disposing of them was not only a way to protect food and resources but also a way to protect communities from evil forces. These beliefs paved the way for the moral or religious model of disability (Wheatley, 2020 ; Ronen, 2020). In medieval Christianised Europe, disabled individuals were stigmatised, isolated, and feared partly because of ignorance and partly because of interpretations of the religious texts that informed Christian beliefs regarding who could be close to God (Duborg, 2023).

During the Middle Ages and preindustrial era, disabled people would get jobs they could perform (Wheatley, 2020). However, if they could not perform any job or be aided by their families; they would beg in town centres or be given support in the form of housing, feeding, and clothing by monasteries or the clergy as part of their religious duty (idem). Around this period, hospitals began to appear, adjacent or as part of monasteries (Ronen, 2020).

From the High Renaissance (1500) onwards, there was the beginning of a process of "disenchantment" of the world. From this point on, "thoughts and meanings are only in minds"

(Taylor, 2014, p. 291), and there was a separation between man and the world which is outside of us (idem). By the 1800s, Europe was going through a period described as 'enlightenment', and views on disability were becoming more pragmatic, revolving around the "afflicted" individual and public health and social and policy (Anderson & Haydon, 2022). The human body could be manipulated and fixed; the sins and evil spirits possessing us became internalised, along with illnesses or sicknesses (Withers, 2021). During this period, the medical model of disability, sometimes called the 'personal tragedy', arose under the premise that body imperfections are abnormal and a consequence of health conditions, disease, or trauma, using a diagnostic-therapeutic paradigm (idem). Using the same basic idea, Charity is the tragic side of the medical model (idem). This archetype sees the impaired as victims that need charity or pity from the body-able, in contrast to the moral model where people with disabilities or their families would be somehow morally responsible for their impairments. Both models became a predominant model for understanding and explaining disability, persisting till today under the umbrella of the individual model of disability where the problem resides with the impairment conditions of the person that needs to be rehabilitated to "normality"— in this way medicalising and institutionalising people with disabilities or the impaired.

Compared to today, sixty years ago, impaired people's lives were different. In the United Kingdom and many Western countries, numerous disabled people were institutionalised. Most of them did not work, many attended special schools that segregated them from the early years of their lives, and they did not enjoy any facilitated access to public transportation or buildings, making it harder to leave their homes. Since the 1960s, the societal view of disabilities under the optic of "chronic illness and disability", which focuses on the person's functional limitations and perceived anomalies, has notably been argued against (Morris, 2020). Initially, not academics but a newly formed disabled community and activist groups aimed to shift this perception by stressing the significance of diversity, empathy, and inclusion of the mentally and physically impaired (Lawson & E., 2020). They promoted the dissolution of socio-cultural barriers for said individuals (ibid). During this period, the Social Model and the Social Construct model of disability appeared in the disability discourse in opposition to the medical model.

These theories claim that the person does not have a disability but that because of their impairments, they are disabled and oppressed by a collection of factors and expectations derived from a body-able and "Normal" society or institutions (ibid). A staple of the social model of disability was immortalised in this quote from the (Union of the Physically Impaired Against Segregation) UPIAS, discussing disability in 1975 (UPIAS, 1997).

"Our position on disability is quite clear and is entirely in line with the agreed principles. In our view, it is the society which disables physically impaired people. Disability is something imposed on top of our impairments, by the way we are unnecessarily isolated and excluded from full participation in society. Disabled".

(UPIAS, 1997, p. 4)

The UPIAS principles of disability ideology rejected the personal tragedy model in favour of recognising that it was the body-able society to oppress and disable. In the dawn of disability studies, in 1983, the British sociologist and disability rights activist Mike Oliver minted the phrase "social model of understanding disability", spawning the identification of different dimensions of understanding disability through models. Models are ways of understanding ideas and putting them into practice; for example, we have individually disabled people who were seen under the tragic model. Meanwhile, the concept of personally imposed restriction underpinned the social model (Oliver, 2004).

Around that period, the 'living normalisation principle' appeared with the relational model, which was developed in Scandinavian countries in the 1960s (Perrin, 1999). This idea started gaining traction in the U.S., where many believed impaired individuals should live in the most "normal" spaces and milieus (Wolfensberger, 1972). Consequently, in 1972, in Berkeley - California, a movement driven by disabled activists and students led to the foundation of "The Centre for Independent Living". Initially located on a university campus, it championed the idea to make the university's entire academic and social life accessible to all. This new concept of "human services" created a ripple effect, and other communities with similar objectives materialised across the

Western world, allowing individuals with impairment to learn to take more initiative and control over their lives, creating in this way a realisation of their autonomy (Pearson, 2020). From the early 80s, self-organised local and national organisations of disabled people started forming, using the international slogan "nothing about us without us," as seen in Shakespeare (Goodley, et al., 2019). This aimed to bring the voices of the bodies to the conversation and policy-making happening around their lives. Shakespeare (2017) argues that the British-born social model of disability had two critical repercussions. First, it dismantled the societal and physical barriers promoting inclusion within its political strategy, breaking through the paradigms of charity, cure and rehabilitation, transforming the way society thinks about issues of discrimination against the impaired. Second, disabled people changed their perspective on their position: it was not them and their bodies that were at fault; rather, it was the current body-able society that needed to change to accommodate their needs, creating enabling environments (idem). With the gradual integration of disabled individuals during the '80s and '90s, other important models of disability started to evolve. For example, a user-centric model became prevalent within disability services (Whelpley, et al., 2023). Under this model, the impaired and their families were "empowered" to engage in the conversation of treatment and services, with the power to choose which one suits them better, which is opposite to the expert model, which is an offshoot of the medical model. It was used to create policies and decide over the body of the impaired (idem). It should be noted these models are still relevant in regions in development, such as South America today (Yarza de los Ríos, et al., 2020).

In the year 2001, after nine years of consideration between disabled representatives, policymakers, academics, medical and carers, the "International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health" (ICF, see Fig. 2) was established (WHO, 2018). It was approved by all WHO country members, deprecating the CIDH (International Classification of Impairments, Disabilities and Handicaps) from 1980, which contained information related to diagnosis and health conditions; however, it did not take into consideration functional status, thus not considering the person in their world. This framework covers health and health-related domains (WHO, 2023). It feels the person's characteristics, such as body functions and structure, activities, participation,

and the interplay with environmental factors and participatory restrictions (idem). These environmental factors may constitute disabling conditions in their human experience, making the impaired less able to enjoy and perform live at their fullest. This classification allows for assessing the degree of disability (idem). It is often used to determine policy and to address issues pertinent to the impaired, thus way integrating in some way or another the medical model with the physical and mental (Abdi, et al., 2020). Social aspects draw a more precise and more complex picture of someone's health and wellbeing, acknowledging that the medical model is not static but dynamically interacts with the social model, remaining relevant to different cultures, age groups or genders, giving way to one that has been called the "bio-psycho-model" (Whelpley, et al., 2023).

To finalise this review of constructed models, we can introduce the human rights model of

Fig. 2 I.C.F. Disability Scheme (WHO, 2018)

disability (HRM). It was drafted from an organism part of the United Nations; the Committee on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) is the assigned organism to observe the protection of the rights and dignity of people with disabilities (Stein & Lord, 2006). The HRM started at the end of the 80s as an offshoot of the social model, which, while achieving political success in terms

of social justice, has been mainly criticised for being too simple. Explaining disability with impairments (individual traits) and disabilities (socially created disadvantages and marginalisation) separated them. It did not provide solutions for the identified problems; for example, the social model does not try to give moral standards or qualities to establish a disability policy (Watson & Vehmas, 2020). As a complement, the human rights model provides solutions, challenging said inadequacies of the social model but also flagging the basic ideas of the medical model where first, people with disabilities have the right to be sheltered and provided with welfare, and secondly because of their impairment there is a correlation to their legal rights and limits (Lawson & E., 2020).

In response to the medical model, the HRM proposes community-based rehabilitation guidelines (CBR) as a form of scaled intervention, where disabled individuals could participate in the community, as a form to prevent the disabilitation of people with impairment (Khasnabis, et al., 2010). In 2008, the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) took effect, aiming to promote, protect and ensure the non-discrimination, equal opportunities, and promotion of autonomy of individuals with impairments. As seen in the CBR (idem), The CRPD accepts that disability is an evolving concept and legitimises the human rights model. Conforming to the independent living vision of the United Nations CRPD, in Scotland, since 2015, the "Disabled People's Summit" has taken place every year, beginning with the slogan "Getting our Rights Right". This iterative summit aims to recognise relevant topics for the Ministerial Advisory Group on Disability to reflect upon. (Scottish Government, 2021). As seen in Series (2020), while the CRPD does not explicitly define the concept of empowerment in terms of disability rights, Article 3 establishes general principles for the convention, implying empowerment in this context by creating ideal environments for people with disabilities to thrive. These are respect for autonomy and decision-making, recognising their capacity to make life decisions, including their health and wellbeing. Second, Independence and self-determination, meaning that disabled people should have the opportunity to live independently and make choices that are encompassed by their values and preferences. Third, Protection from exploitation and abuse means balancing safeguarding their rights while defending their autonomy; fourth, eliminating

barriers and discrimination means deconstructing the barriers that promote their full participation in society. This involves the promotion of equality, accessibility, and inclusion. Fifth, challenging traditional views of vulnerability entails more inclusive rights-based strategies acknowledging their capabilities and potential. The sixth and final principle, resisting restrictive practices, addresses issues which might include compulsory treatment without consent and legal restrictions that might limit rights and capacities (Series, 2020).

2.2 Crip Theory: a tool for disability empowerment

In the context of disability studies, “disablism” refers to the marginalisation of people based on their disabilities (Scully, 2020). Conversely, “ableism” is the unfairness in favour of non-disabled people (Gappmayer, 2020). Creating an idealised idea of normalcy and desirability of the able-bodied, mentally able and neurotypical, this way fomenting biases, policies, practices, and institutions (Campbell, 2020). The ideas of “disablism” and “ableism” are present and internalised in our societies, leading to the unfair exclusion that occurs through various, often unnoticed, codes and processes embedded in power structures that divide people into the normal and those who are deemed deviant, going as far as exercising survival of the fittest in moments of crisis (Tanure, et al., 2022; Read, et al., 2023).

Crip theory emerged at the dawn of the 21st Century, flourishing within disability studies and aligning itself with Queer theory. It responds to the need for a more inclusive and multifaceted analysis of disability and its intersectionality with other aspects of identity (Karlsson, 2023). In their shared experiences of abjection, Crip theory embodies values of defiance, objecting to and questioning social ableism, much as Queer theory does to heteronormativity. The two also overlap in their exploration of marginalised realities and their promotion of activism (Mc Ruer, 2006).

As a result, Crip theory offers an analytical approach to understanding how disabled people's lives, akin to those of Queer individuals, have been constructed and represented in various contexts through a normative lens (McRuer, 2005). These experiences are often characterised

by pathologising, stereotyping, and marginalisation, regardless of the period or location in which they occur. Furthermore, their situated knowledge has frequently been ignored (McRuer, 2005).

Crip theory resists normativity and empowers people living with disabilities by taking several steps. Firstly, as language is a powerful tool, it reclaims the term “crip”, reinventing this from the derogatory term “cripple”, which has been historically used to abject or cast-off disabled people. In this way defying and challenging negative connotation associated to this term, this way creating a sense of pride for the crip community and those who identify with it (Andrews, et al., 2022).

Secondly, valuing and validating their situated knowledge highlights their unique experiences and viewpoints. As seen in Johnson & McRuer (2014), the term “Cripistemologies” embraces the lived individual experience of people with disabilities by sharing their ways of knowing and navigating the world, rejecting able normativism of time and space (Chandler, et al., 2021). Hence, crip-terms such as “Crip-Time” appeared in Wälivaara (2021). This is a flexible approach to bend able-conformist time frames to the needs of disabled bodies and minds (Kafer, 2013). Another example central to this thesis is “Crippling Technoscience”, a term that comes from the intersection with feminist theory. This term is not only about creating an accessible world for disabled people but also breaking with the historical approach of disabled communities passively consuming design and technology made for them by experts who were detached from their realities and experiences. Instead, these terms stressed the importance of working in relationships and practices that facilitate the exchange of disabled people’s knowledge, skills, resources and situated wisdom to create technology and design accessible spaces or artefacts, centring the work of disabled people through the lens of knowers and makers, further nurturing disabled culture and politics (Hamraie & Fritsch, 2019). They are lastly resisting ableist aspirations of overcoming one’s disability, i.e., the “super-crip” stereotype to identify an unhelpful narrative where a person with a disability conquers their disability through sheer willpower (McGillivray, et al., 2019).

Thirdly, it acknowledges the intersection of a broad range of disabilities, including mental and neurodivergence, with other markers of identity, such as race, sexuality, gender, and age, among others. Recognising that forms of oppression or marginalisation can exist simultaneously. In this manner, it is finding a coalition among different identities to fight against attitudes such as ageism, disablism, ableism, homophobia, sexism, racism and other forms of oppression and exclusion (Hall, 2021).

In short, while crip theory is still an evolving field, it is a critical framework to uplift disabled individuals by challenging structures of power, especially ableism and disablism, recognising the diversity of disability experiences, exploring where it crosses with other identities for the need to explore more inclusive and nuanced conversations of disability with activist and academics alike. In this way, it becomes a part of the disability rights movement that sets out to create a ripple effect of empowerment, throughout our societal biases, policies, practices, and institutions.

2.3 Disability, Health, and Wellbeing:

Definitions of health have evolved. According to the World Health Organisation (WHO) in 1948, health can be defined as a "state of complete physical, mental, and social wellbeing, and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity" (WHO, 2023). While this definition grounds health in society, it sees health as a goal. This definition was later revisited by the Ottawa Charter in 1986 to see health and its promotion as a resource that society and the individual should use; nonetheless, it has been criticised for its aspirational focus on the absolute that health is the absence of infirmity, given that mental or physical chronic conditions can be managed to experience wellbeing (Fancourt & Finn, 2019). According to McCartney (2019), other definitions provide an alternative, focusing on their understanding that health is culturally constructed and that encompasses the ability of people to adapt to their current reality and regulate themselves within their setting, offering one definition that doesn't see disability as a cause of loss of

health. As “a structural, functional and emotional state that is compatible with effective life as an individual and as a member of family and community groups” (idem), this definition of health can be more subjective and individualistic, but always correlated with society one lives in. This takes into consideration other parameters of health such as difference from inequalities and inequities in gender, ethnicity, hereditary factors, working and living conditions (ibid). The terms “health” and “wellbeing” are often conflated, and while there is an intrinsic connection between the two, as they influence one another, not always having a high level of life satisfaction, and having a positive state of mind and body (Wellbeing) equates to having good health in the medical sense, and vice versa (Department of Health , 2013). Wellbeing can be divided into two categories. First, “Subjective well-being”, which is the person's perspective about their life satisfaction, positive affect and if they find meaning in their lives, and second “, Objective Wellbeing” has to do with human rights, access to water and food, education, safety etc. (idem).

Assistive Technologies (AT, see 1.4) is an umbrella term that encompasses systems, devices or software that can enable a disabled person to adapt to environments, e.g., stairs, doors, or objects such as books and computers, in a manner that is tailored to their needs. These technologies permit people with impairments to engage in different daily activities by removing barriers that prevent their participation in society and maximise independent living. According to the United Nations, AT directly impacts their health and well-being, and they are a human right in line with the *"Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities"* (UNRCP) "because they are recognised as the first crucial—and mediating—step towards equal opportunities" (United Nations, 2016).

Culture is an experience that can be collective, encompassing other rules, codes, narratives, models, etc, and personal, containing our worldviews, skills, and values (Cerulo & Leschziner, 2021). Culture is the thread that conjoins society; it has been shown that participation in culture (in the case of this project, involvement with a new type of media) can contribute to improving health and wellbeing in communities, making them more cohesive, it can also

increase meaning and happiness, be a medium for intercultural understanding, relieve isolation in senior citizens, and improve quality of life in general (Fancourt & Finn, 2019; Tymoszuk, et al., 2021)

Our feelings play an essential role in the subjective self-interpreting quality of life. In established psychological discourse, the relationship between mood and emotions is that "emotions" are shorter-lived but more intense and can come and go in minutes, while "moods", being less heightened feelings, can last from hours to a couple of days (Ekman, 2007). According to Ekman (2007), moods activate emotions based on how we feel, meaning that if we are in a sad or cheerful mood, we will be more attuned to perceiving the world under one of these manners. It has been claimed that with emotions, we can point out with ease a reflective reason why we are feeling a certain way, but with moods, we rarely know why we are feeling that way. Richard Coyne (1999) subscribes to the idea that there is a difference between moods and emotions. He believes that, when it comes to the effect of digital media on our emotional spectrum, researchers tend to overlook the role our moods play when engaging with media and each other. He also suggests that moods are not tied to a specific incident but are a collection of emotional inputs that incite us to action; they are an active state that we can propagate and communicate with the use of digital media: "We are not just passive receivers of moods foisted upon us; we are complicit in the making of moods." (Coyne, 1999, p. 3). In this way, Coyne warns us that as media consumers, we should be conscious of their emotional effects on us in our everyday lives, as we are not only moving bodies but also have moving minds with emotional states that need attention. This is also the case for disabled people, who increasingly rely on different types of digital media to enhance their lives.

2.4 The power of contemplation: Nature's healing properties

Healing environments are spaces with the right conditions to provide a therapeutic effect for individuals. Florence Nightingale championed this term in her book "Notes on Nursing" (1859), bearing in mind the optimisation of care spaces such as hospital rooms and doctors' offices and

stressing the importance of the introduction of natural elements to these spaces for the healing of patients, championing this message for the creation of health-promoting environments. Nevertheless, the concept of 'nature' has remained an elusive and continuously negotiated notion depending on the setting. McLuhan asserted that the word 'nature' is an abstraction that has changed over time, from the ancient Greeks to modern humanity. He writes that the Greeks individuated two words for the world around them. The first word was 'physis' (nature), and the second was 'chaos', which was everything else, subtly different to today's human who has constructed a Euclidean or mechanical world and calls everything that humankind has not created nature inverting its value to 'chaos' (McLuhan & Powers, 1989). The Scottish public health sector acknowledges studies that suggest that natural environments have a restorative effect on an individual's wellbeing, reducing anxiety and encouraging recovery (Health and Social Care Alliance Scotland, 2022). Nowadays, the benefits of nature in our psychological and physiological wellbeing are well established (Bratman, 2019; PY, et al., 2020). In addition, although humans and our social activities are part of nature, we are often perceived in contemporary thought as belonging to another classification, outside of the natural phenomena in the broadest sense (Ducarme, 2020).

Macnaghten and Urry, in their book *"Contested Natures"* (1998), argue that in contemporary thinking, nature is thought of through three conventional doctrines. (1) Environmental Realism, a 'nature' that lives independent of our awareness, conceptualises nature as an entity independent of society. (2) Environmental Idealism, which establishes underlying values that define natural spaces. This concept is almost romantic and spiritual. (3) Environmental Instrumentalism, which sees nature as resources and benefits for our health; nature is the heritage we received and must be taken care of for future generations. Macnaghten and Urry contest that there are only three conventional ways to think about nature. They undermine nature's "social" dimensions as if there is only one and a corresponding set of human responses. They propose another approach for deconstructing and interpreting nature, adding more layers by stressing that our perception of nature can derive from "embedded social practices". This includes cultural, pragmatic, and the self versus the bodily experience nature exercises over them

(McCartney, et al., 2019). This is summarised in the following way: "There is no singular as such, only a diversity of contested natures; and that each such nature is constituted through a variety of socio-cultural processes from which such natures cannot be plausibly separated " (Ibid, p.1), similar to the arguments about environmental instrumentalism set out above. In the next section, we can see how four traditions of theory conceptualise nature as environments for restoration and mood improvement, each one influenced from their point of view, creating an ever-growing conversation crossing different fields (see Fig 3)

Fig. 3 Academic perspectives about Nature as a healer. (Author, 2020)

Firstly, in anthropology, the theory tradition of medical geography proposes the ever-growing terminology of "therapeutic landscapes" (See Fig.4), proposing that "health" and "place" are intrinsically connected, explaining that these environments are changing settings, situations, locales and milieus, holistically associated with healing (Williams, 1998). These milieus are linked to the concept of "sense of place", which is the *"transference of moral and aesthetic judgements to particular sites"* (Gesler, 1991, p. 164). Initially developed by Gesler, the therapeutic

landscapes terminology is one of perceived well-being, where the encounter with environmental, societal, and individual factors exerts a healing influence in specific sites (Gesler, 1992). Therefore, these therapeutic landscapes are addressed by Gesler (1992) as 'Natural environment', 'Built environment', 'Symbolic environment' and 'Social environment', providing a breadth of interpretation for academics in other traditions of theory (Kearns & Milligan, 2020).

Similarly, in the field of psychology, the approaches of environmental psychology use the system of terms "Healing Gardens" in combination with "Therapeutic Landscapes" (see Fig.5). Within these terminologies, we can find embedded the co-existing frameworks of "Aesthetic-Affective Theory" (AAT), and Stress Reduction Theory (SRT) (Ulrich, 1983). Focusing both on emotions and physiological responses (Top-Down Processing), In the field of human perception, Top-Down Processing is

the cognitive process through which the brain uses the information gathered by the sensory system (Hear, Smell, Touch, and using the pre-existing knowledge creates an understanding, This includes Cognitive and practical evaluations, but also meaning, association and expectation (Koivisto, 2022). AAT contends that within the human evolutionary heritage, there is a constant preference for stimuli derived from natural milieus, and how the initial response to these environments are feelings, not thoughts, signalling danger or safety to humans or, in other words, when to relax (Ulrich, 1983; Ulrich, 1993). In addition, SRT argues that humans prefer to be adjacent to natural spaces that present themselves with depth, complexity, and structure (Ulrich et al., 1991). SRT focuses on how natural areas diminish physiological stress and negative thoughts, suggesting that the inclusion of natural spaces within care spaces could bring relief from physical symptoms, stress reduction, recovery from traumatising physical and mental experiences, and a sense of self-reported wellbeing in individuals; With the potential to improve the wellbeing patients and care staff members alike (Ulrich, et al., 1991; Cooper-Marcus & Barnes, 1999).

Fig. 4 Discussion domain within medical geography, "Therapeutic Landscape", (Author, 2020)

The theoretical tradition of environmental psychology also proposes the terminology "Restorative Environments" and, within it, Attention Restoration Theory (ART) (Kaplan, 1995). This focuses on the bottom-up cognitive process, which says that attention is divided into two sub-sections: a) voluntary or directed attention, which requires effort while performing a task and b) involuntary attention, where significant or amusing stimuli absorb attention. Environments can provide natural stimuli that encourage relief from 'directed attention fatigue' (DAF) and stress; these natural processes initiate effortless attention while keeping us from boredom (idem). ART suggests that our directed attention is a limited resource. ART argues that exposure to natural environments and their "patterns" may restore our ability to concentrate, positively impacting our attention capacity and overall wellbeing. Directed attention is vital for self-care and independent functioning. When there is no associated illness, people with signs of "directed attention fatigue" display deteriorating symptoms on the self-regulation of mood (Nisbet, et al., 2019).

Fig. 5.Areas of discussion within Environmental Psychology, (Author, 2020)

According to Kaplan (1989), for natural environments to change negative mental states to positive ones, they should exhibit specific properties, and the first one is the subjective or objective sense of "being away", allowing our attention to escape from a depleting environment. Then, the second property a domain needs to elicit is "soft fascination". This means being in an environment where your attention is held but not drained; for example, a long walk in the forest allows the individual to meditate on ideas while enjoying the surroundings, leaving mental power for reflection, making connections or realising opportunities. This is how Kaplan defines it: "Soft

fascination may be a mixture of fascination and pleasure such that any lack of clarity an individual may be experiencing is not necessarily blotted out by distraction but rendered substantially less painful" (Kaplan, 1989, p. 192). This before mentioned type of fascination is in juxtaposition from what the Kaplans call "hard fascination", which is the type of distraction that requires effort, and to focus our attention, an example of this could be binge-watching a compelling TV show; Both "fascinations" contribute to the sense of restoration. However, they differ in their effects; while "soft fascination" helps us to introspect and "make sense", "hard fascination" entertains and reduces boredom (idem). In addition to "being away" and "soft fascination, for an environment to be restorative, it requires the property of "extension" or "extent". Extent is the feeling of involvement in a space open for exploration, which differs from the space you are away from. It also needs to balance feeling safe and not having too many structures or rules. Extent also applies to imaginary internal spaces when it comes to thoughtful meditation. At the highest level of the pyramid, when you have the feeling of being away, also the meditative state of soft-fascination and the understanding that the environment is safe and compelling to explore, there sits "Compatibility", or the understanding of what space is for, and it's a familiarity to you. For this, the individual and space must demonstrate an affinity for one another (ibid).

ART is a popular and widely cited concept in the academic literature, with studies reporting results in line with ART (Yap, 2022). For example, before and after studies using "before and after" tests with visual media and real environments, using different exposure types, i.e., real-world vs artificial environments/stimuli in controlled test settings, generating results in agreement with Kaplan's ART (Stenfors, et al., 2019). However, some critics point out that certain aspects of ART are underdeveloped (i.e., soft fascination) or that there is not enough evidence for the "bottom-up" mechanism from which the restoration is meant to occur, and finally, that nature is not necessarily restorative in every case (Johnson, et al., 2022; Hansen & Guodong, 2023).

In the theoretical tradition of ecological psychology (see Fig. 6), we can find the terminologies "Salutogenic Environment" and "Therapeutic Landscapes", and this is used to underline the theory of environmental affordances by focusing on the inclusion of nature in visually aesthetic design elements in urban planning, influencing landscape architecture in the creation of "salubrious landscapes" (Szczygiel & Hewitt, 2000). These support public health and create green spaces that afford a healthy lifestyle, social contact, and community among urban dwellers (Gordon J. Walker, 2019). The studies designed to understand the importance of green spaces in cities are many (von Lindern E, 2022).

Fig. 6 Areas of discussion within Ecological Psychology, (Author, 2020)

“Horticultural therapy” is a therapeutic approach that promotes horticultural activity and walking outdoors, facilitated by a trained therapist to achieve a treatment goal (Nicholas, et al., 2019). Sustaining that gardening or the explorations of such spaces is particularly meaningful for adults, this way supports the theories of “flow” experience and sensory stimulation theories, such as ART & SRT, when it comes to the enjoyment of the natural patterns and design of the garden there is a sense of restoration or regeneration(idem). This approach uses the terminologies “healing garden” and “therapeutic garden”; these may trace their roots to the medieval monastic tradition of “Hortus conclusus”, where these spaces were used for therapeutic and spiritual purposes (Beck, 2000).

Within Horticultural Therapy (see Fig. 7), Healing gardens are urban environments dominated by greenery, including other natural elements such as water and flowers; these places are perceived as medically preventive medical tools (Dushkova & Ignatieva, 2020). These city landscapes are associated with care institutions and are open to visitors; however, a therapeutic garden is a sub-category of the healing garden, as this one is related to horticultural or occupational therapy for

a specific group of individuals (Hastuti & Lorica, 2020), the DRC counts both with a Healing Garden and a Therapeutic Garden (see section 4.1).

In line with Kaplan's (ART) and Ulrich's (SRT) groundwork, the literature shows that all indoor or outdoor gardens have healing properties. Nonetheless, according to Cooper-Marcus and Barnes, the beneficial experience is attributed to elements such as access to nature, positive distraction in the form of fresh

Fig. 7 Areas of discussion within Horticultural Therapy, (Author, 2020)

air and greenery, and sunlight avoiding negative distractions such as insects, smoke, urban noise also mentioning strangers to the place may constitute a stressor especially for the psychologically ill, a "sense of control", which is the ability to access the garden quickly and the ability to make choices on where to walk, contemplate or perform a therapeutic activity. And finally, "physical movement and exercise" (Cooper-Marcus & Barnes, 1999).

These domains demonstrate how this concept of nature is no longer an evolving dialogue in academia; nature is not defined but explored and negotiated, where one tradition of thinking borrows from another. In the same order of ideas, "therapeutic landscapes" started as a theory in real geographic locations, famed for their restorative effects—for example, Epidaurus in Greece, Bath in England, or Lourdes in France (Gesler, 1993). Nowadays, the terminology also goes beyond physical geographies, including places of imagination, media, the arts, and literature, and is used to help marginalised communities in society. The elderly and disabled (Liu, et al., 2023). this terminology has a holistic approach and aims to answer the question of where are places of health and well-being. It is also important to note that healing depends on deeply personal circumstances, adding other layers of complexity, such as the socio-cultural and psychological (Gesler, 2003). In short, Restorative environment theories (ART, SRT) seek to understand how these natural environments elicit processes that can restore our attention and help us recover from stress (see Fig. 8). Subsequently, there is the approach of healing gardens

and the sub-category "therapeutic garden", and they have to do with the design of natural spaces within care spaces to execute meaningful action on the path of healing. Finally, Salutogenic environments, borrowing from therapeutic gardens, have to do with creating areas that contain nature to create resilience for urban dwellers, patients and care workers alike, creating an ecosystem where nature is defined as a healer.

Fig. 8 Clouds provide us with self-similarity patterns; this is a non-engrossing distraction that helps to restore attention through contemplation (author, 2020)

2.4.1 The healing properties of meditation:

Having explored the theories behind how natural elements have been studied and discussed for their therapeutic effect on the mind and body, we now turn to the second component of the VR experience: mindfulness. Every person at some point in their life experiences anxiety; these feelings are expected when it comes to specific trigger moments, such as an exam or a difficult

conversation; while it is a normal human response, in itself, anxiety can constitute a cause of impairment for daily life (Penninx, 2021). However, across all age groups, a connection between people who identify as disabled or stroke survivors and the persistence of psychological distress is well documented in studies (Chun, et al., 2021; Cree, 2020). They are showing evidence that there is a significantly higher response to psychological distress among groups of physically disabled individuals compared to non-disabled groups (Cree, 2020) . It is worth acknowledging that individuals with physical disabilities may exhibit varying responses, influenced by factors such as neurodiversity, gender, sexuality, and social status. The combination of these factors can make it challenging for many disabled individuals to regulate their emotions, leading to emotional fatigue and profound consequences. While there is no specifically designed meditation based treatment for the physically disabled, currently in the UK, under the NHS, the routes of treatment for this generalised condition are medication and psychological therapies that could also be accompanied by mindfulness-based cognitive therapy (MBCT), which is commonly used to treat depression, and Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) which is usually used to ameliorate anxiety (Simmonds-Buckley, et al., 2020; Zhang D, 2021).

Mindfulness-based stress reduction (MBSR) is a structured programme of 8 weeks focused on cultivating resilience by simple awareness of one's current state in a non-judgmental manner, even accepting uncomfortable feelings; it was created by Kabatt-Zinn (1995). In it, the individual pays attention to thoughts as they pass through their mind. It is a technique to ameliorate physical and psychological distress (Querstret, 2020). While it finds its origins within Buddhist teaching, it has been practised for the last 40 years in a non-secular manner in the West, with studies that suggest this type of technique can improve vitality and coping (Feldman & Kuyken, 2019), it has been found that even "brief, daily meditation enhances attention, memory, mood, and emotional regulation in non-experienced meditators" (Basso et al., 2019) and can be a feasible technique on pain and discomfort management (Brintz, et al., 2020). Whereas mindfulness is a passive and accepting activity, it requires discipline, mental training, and considerable attention effort in a path of struggle before achieving a mindful state (Feldman & Kuyken, 2019). Guided mindfulness MBSR can take many forms; a "body scan", for example,

could be done through Muscle Relaxation (PMR) and “Focused attention”, and a model could be Mindfulness-based breath training (MBBT). While the first focuses on tensing and relaxing groups of muscles to help people take control of their bodies, the second (MBBT) focuses on controlled breathing exercises used mindfully. These techniques are commonly used to aid individuals suffering from anxious episodes (Gao & J., 2018). In comparison, MBBT trains the individual to mindfully breathe (Kabat-Zinn, 1994). This means restoring natural respiration, producing no stressed inhalation-exhalation, and avoiding shallow breathing. In the same fashion, PMR trains the individual to articulate a muscular response to moments of stress, resulting in a calming effect on the body (ibid). The use of mindfulness-based techniques used in mainstream health and wellbeing channels to achieve focus, anxiety and depression reduction include promising results that benefit disabled individuals (Simpson, 2020), not only for stress reduction in social settings but also for pain reduction in chronic physical conditions (idem) Allowing people to be aware and have effective reactions against stressors (Simmons, 2023). Finally, Kaplan has also recognised the benefits of mindfulness for stress and "Directed attention deficit" recovery after engaging in mindfulness meditation, establishing a connection between the positive effects of natural processes and mindfulness (Kaplan, 2001). In conclusion, by looking at the beneficial effects of spending time contemplating natural environments and practising mindfulness meditation, it is evident that there is one underlying calming similarity. In both activities, there is a focus on specific patterns that allow people to have moments of contemplation and still leave mental bandwidth to process thoughts and emotions. But while the fascination experienced with muscle relaxation and breathing meditation is introspective, the fascination experienced on ART & SRT is outward-looking.

2.5 The human who plays.

Play is a primal society activity, research with primates suggests that play for leisure creates community and prevents conflict (Palagi, et al., 2006). A game could be defined as an activity where decision-makers aim to reach a goal within a limiting context, this goal-seeking can lead to amusement or other forms of reward (Stenros, 2017). Games can communicate ideas, behaviours, and information; also, they can be spread in the same manner as any other cultural abstracts (idem). To design the games of the future, is necessary to understand that games have always been part of human societies (see appendix A). This shows how the experience of being human holds an innate compulsion to play, while attitudes towards games are not always positive (Iacovides, 2019). Games have shown to be able to help people to deal with their feelings, facilitated social connections, provide a coping mechanism in times of existential doubt and supported personal evolution (idem). As Csikzentmihalyi (1997) sets out, games were “developed over the centuries for the express purpose of enriching life with enjoyable experiences.” (Csikszentmihalyi, 1997). In this section I will explain what a game is, and how game theory can help us understand players motivations, then to explain why people play, I will explain play theories, following this I will then explain the topics of serious games and gamification to understand which possible applications of gaming are to enhance human living experience, to then explain how gaming forms part of disabled people’s lives.

2.5.1 Game Theory

“Rational Choice Theory” is an umbrella framework that studies how individuals take decisions according to their preferences and guided by their rationality (Krstić, 2022). From this umbrella “Game Theory” emerged to become a Mathematical framework that analyses how conscious rational decision makers in the form of players, interact with one another within the rules of a game (conflict or negotiation) (Brown & Shoham, 2022). Game theory is an enormous area of studies spanning into different fields of knowledge such as biology, sociology, political science, economics, and Physics (idem). Therefore, I will explain the aspects of game theory that intersect within the interests of this thesis, which are those parallel to game design, in this case the basic concepts of a game and players stakes. Formulated by John von Neumann and Oskar

Morgenstern; Game theory was pioneered in their book *"Theory of Games and Economic Behaviour"* (1944), born from the field of mathematics, game theory is used to construct models of rational behaviour when the agents are confronted in situations where their interests, and objectives meet, in this way leading to a solution, within this framework. The basic concepts of a game are, first, Strategies are the feasible courses of action an agent can take to maximize a payoff, for example in "Rock, Paper, Scissors" each turn we have three strategies which are Rock, Paper, Scissors. Payoff is a reward associated to the different courses of action within a game. Games are the scenarios and rules where players interact, where the payoff is affected by the interdependency of their decisions. In these games, players also called agents, choose their strategies simultaneously or can take a turn in a predetermined sequential order, games can go from one turn each to hypothetically infinite (Ross, 2023). Conversely Games Theory also contemplates "Games against Nature", these are games where Player 1 is a rational decision maker with his own preferences and objectives, and Player 2 is not, i.e. a race against time, where a two people team needs to prepare as many cookies as possible. In this case "Nature" has not strategies but "states", in the case of the most recent example is "Time" (idem).

Games types normally fall into three main categories. First is non-cooperative games, where a player gain comes at the cost of another player loss, also called a Zero-sum game, then we have Cooperative and finally Mixed (Brown & Shoham, 2022). In non-cooperative games the "Nash Equilibrium" is the optimal solution for any player; this means that players have chosen an initial strategy of play, knowing each other's strategy options, and have no incentive for changing course of action. In this scenario, every player has achieved the best payoff for their situation, notwithstanding what other players had decided to do (idem). This is because decision makers acting in their own self-interests can arrive paradoxically to sub-optimal outcomes when they do not trust each other or compete with one another. This is explained through a thought experiment called the "Prisoners' Dilemma" (de Melo & Terada, 2020). This thought experiment assumes that both players are rational and self-interested. In this scenario, two criminals (Poppy and Ptolemy, see example Fig. 9) have been arrested for a minor crime by the

police and interrogated in separate rooms. The scenario assumes that one of them was also involved in a major crime, but the police doesn't know who, and they wish to find out. The strategies available to each prisoner are 2, either cooperate by remaining silent or defect by confessing and betray their partner. The solutions to this dilemma are 3, if one defects and the other doesn't, the one who had defected will be set free and the other will have a harsh sentence and spend 10 years on jail (see Fig. 9, letters C, B). If neither defect they both will be held in jail for a year (see Fig.9 Letter D), If both defect each will get to spend 5 years on jail (see Fig.9, Letter A), according to game theory while this is not the solution with the best outcome. With both criminals defecting the game would have achieved the "Nash equilibrium" (optimal solution) as both players would have acted in their benefit and their choice would have had the best result possible for them regardless what the other players action is.

Poppy's Strategy

Fig. 9 Game matrix of Strategies to Prisoner's dilemma (Author, 2023)

Cooperative games are games where players help one another to achieve a winning condition or a payoff, meaning that all players benefits from the same payoff (Molinero, 2021). Finally Mixed (strategy) Games are those where both players can decide among strategies of cooperation and competition depending of the framework of the game (idem).

Cooperative and Mixed games arrive to the soultion by using the value of every individual players contribution as the measure to divided the costs or gains distributed to players at the end of the game, this is called Shapplely value (Merrick & Taly, 2020). For example, if in a cooperative baking game, where the scope is to bake as many cookies as possible per day, a team is comprissed of two players (1,2). As their strategy they may choose to work towards the payoff togheter or separately. During the first day, they decide to go work separately. Player 1 produces 10 cookies, and player 2 produces 15 cookies, the total result would be be 25 cookies in day one. if we assume that the value per every cookie sold is equal to 1 coin, then at the end of the day from the 25 coins total, Player 1 would receive 10 coins and Player 2 would receive 15 coins (See Fig.10).

Fig. 10 Shapley's value day one input (Author, 2023)

For day two, the two players decide to work together, at the end of day two they produce 45 cookies therefore there are 45 coins to split after these cookies have been sold. In this case, according to the Shapley Value, they would split the gains into the following manner, the result from day one (25 coins) would be reduced from the total of day two (45 coins), then the remaining (20 coins) would be divided by the quantity of players (2), then this amount (10 coins) would be added to the total gain of each player. Therefore as a result of the second day, player 1 would earn 20 coins, while player two 25 coins (See Fig.11).

Fig. 11 Shapley’s value explanation for second day (Author,2023)

From a game design perspective, this section illustrates, what a game is, the basis of a game i.e. rules, strategy, and payoff. Players are motivated by a payoff that can be maximised by following a strategy, finding in a conflict situation the best solution possible in interdependence with the other players’ choices. Additionally, Shapley’s value rationalises mathematically, how to fairly distribute the payoff in cooperative games.

2.5.2 Theories of Play

The field of human evolution refers to the appearance of the *Homo sapiens* (Latin: “wise man”). The *Homo Sapiens* is the “(hu)man as a knower”, as a unique category of mammal hominids, the species to which all modern human beings belong. Within the analogies of the humanistic renaissance of the 14th Century in Italy, we find the term *Homo Faber* or (hu)man the maker - a transformative term, conferring upon humans the ability to forge their destiny. In modernity, we can also find the term used in other accounts as a creator of artwork (Kubler, 2008) or, related to the intellect; "In short, intelligence, considered in what seems to be its original feature, is the faculty of manufacturing artificial objects, especially tools to make tools, and of indefinitely varying the manufacture." (Bergson, 1911, p. 139) *Homo Faber* can also be interpreted as the term "Workingman" which lends juxtaposition to another fundamental statement of what it means to be human: *Homo Ludens* (“The Playing Man”) or “The (Hu)man as a Player”: the one who wants to be entertained and have fun.

It is widely accepted that play has been part of human culture and societies since pre-recorded history. The act of playing can be found in other animals who played before humans, or as the Dutch cultural historian Johan Huizinga puts it in his classic book *Homo Ludens*, “play is older than culture, for culture, however inadequately defined, always presupposes human society, and animals have not waited for the man to teach them their playing” (Huizinga, 1949, p. 1). He also points to that for play to occur, there must be fun. Therefore, he identifies characteristics of it that can be summarised as follows. Play can never be imposed; it needs to be a voluntary activity and feel free. Play is not an ordinary or serious life. When play occurs, it takes place in a magic circle, an alternative reality with activities and constitution that exist out of “real life” and has been agreed upon. It has its limits of time and place (a yard, a board), and it demand order (idem). Play is an immersive illusion, not connected to material interests, and no material gain can be obtained from it. Huizinga view games as a fundamental aspect of life and says that play is older than culture: before the *homo sapiens*, animals knew how to play, and by playing humans learned about one another and their surroundings, creating civilizations and societies, and that culture and play are on the same level. He explains and systematically analyses how play is constituent

of generations of cultural forms that can be creative & lighthearted, such as languages, art and poett, to also include social systems such as Law and War, the latter having a more sinister and serious undertone, Later Caillois building in the terms developed by Huizinga would coin the term “Magic Circle”, as the imaginary liminal space where plays happen (Caillois, 1961)..

Building on Huizinga’s “Play Theory”, French philosopher Roger Callois in his influential book “*Man, Play, games*” (*Les Jeux et Les Hommes*, originally published in 1958) criticizes these theories for being simultaneously too broad and too narrow in terms of conception and definition (Ehrmann, Lewis and Lewis, 1968). Caillois argues that Huizinga was too broad because he failed to delineate the conceptual space of culture, where play ends and the “sacred” and “institutional” starts. He also deemed it as too narrow that play has more than one characteristic, considering several possibilities, he created a division of four main rubrics, depending on the role of competition, chance, simulation, or vertigo is dominant. he called these agon, alea, mimicry, and ilinx, respectively (Caillois, 1961).

Caillois believed all games subscribed to one of these categories, and that they could complement one another. In the text, we can see that in addition to Huzinga’s competition (Agon) which refers to fair competition and honour, including those situations where conflict is present; then he adds three more play forms; Alea: which refers to chance, including games of gambling diverging from Huizinga’s initial idea that there is no material gain or loss in play; Mimicry: this refers to simulation or roles, for example when somebody plays to believe he is somebody else. We can see this mimicry play an important role in the aspects of societal constructs such as rituals in Religion and Law, or the creation of communities, for example, sports fans wearing the same soccer team uniform at the grades, and finally; Ilinx: this refers to Vertigo, in the sense of altering perception, i.e., spinning around till you feel dizzy, rolling down the hills. I would argue that first moment of awe when one uses VR belongs to this category. It is also worth noting that these categories can and often do go hand in hand with one another, and the firsts two categories mentioned (Agon & Alea) can complement one another in terms of “Virtue” and rules-based in the equal chance of success, while the second two (Mimicry & Ilinx) complement each other in

terms of suspension of the self (pretension) and simulation; and as a final example, Agon & Mimicry have the power of creating communities (See Fig. 13).

He concluded that these categories are subject to a superimposed polarity on the first, a continuum running from “Paidia” (spontaneous play) to “Ludus” (controlled play). “In general, the first manifestations of paidia have no name and could not have any, precisely because they are not of any order, distinctive symbolism, or differentiated life that would permit a vocabulary to consecrate their autonomy with a specific term. But as soon as conventions, techniques, and utensils emerge, the first games as such arise with them: e.g., leapfrog, hide and seek, kite-flying, teetotum, sliding, blindman’s buff, and doll-play. At this point, the contradictory roads of agon, alea, mimicry, and ilinx begin to bifurcate. At the same time, the pleasure experienced in solving a problem arbitrarily designed for this purpose also intervenes so that reaching a solution has no other goal than personal satisfaction for its own sake. This condition, which is Ludus proper, is also reflected in different kinds of games, except for those which wholly depend upon the cast of a die. It is complementary to and a refinement of paidia, which is disciplines and enriches” (Caillois, 1961, p.19, see Fig.12).

Fig. 12 Caillois’s psychological attitudes and principles of games (ebrary.net, 2014)

Play theorist Brian Sutton-Smith (1997), who, like his predecessors Huizinga and Caillois, dedicated his work to discover the cultural importance of play in people's lives, asserted that any

proper definition of play should apply to all life stages, not only children. He says that play is ambivalent. It can be at once frivolous and enjoyable but also deadly serious. He specified that play in culture constitutes seven rhetoric's or narratives (Sutton-Smith, 1997). He described them as possessing ideological merit, where those who subscribe to them seek to convince fellow humans to accept and adopt those ideologies as a way of living. He categorized them as those who come from the ancient and modern world (idem).

The rhetoric's of the ancient world is the following: play as "Fate" revolves around the idea that destiny controls our lives, and it's applied to gambling; play as "Power" deals with the concept of metaphorically re-enacting actual conflict, where it represents becoming heroes. It applies to many sports where there are competition, strategy, and negotiation of space, for example, games where two or more teams go against one another; football, chess, water polo.

Play as "Identity" deals with the idea of establishing or affirming cohesion and identity of the group of players through acts of rituals or celebrations, laying on values such as tradition. Festivals like Oktoberfest exemplify this narrative; Play as "Frivolity", in the pure Kantian disinterested nature of play, as it revolves around the idea that play resolves nothing and it's only for leisure in opposition and sometimes protests order.

The rhetorics of the modern world have to do with how societies in the 20th Century try to interpret "Play," and they can be organized as follows; "Progress" as play is an essential exploration of learning and developing cognitive or social skills, a good example of this is how we think today of how animals and children need play to adapt and understand how to negotiate the world and affect it. "Imaginary" as play, is the flexible place for creativity, improvisation, and innovation, totally separated from work; "Self" as play, usually has to do with escapism from the everyday life focusing on enjoyable experiences, relaxation, and solitary activities Sutton-Smith says we can see this last one "in individualism, capitalism, secularisation, phenomenological philosophy, 'amateur' sports metaphors, psychology, leisure theory, performance theory, narrative theory." (Sutton-Smith 1997, p.175)

Sutton-Smith says that these narratives can also oppose one another. For example, he suggests that the rhetoric of power or progress is incompatible with the rhetoric of frivolity, because they cancel one another. In closing remarks, he argues that because the definition of play is ambiguous and difficult to define, there is a tendency by the subscribers of each narrative to advocate and take and defend the definition they endorse.

Many thinkers have tried to define the characteristics of play, passing from a set of characteristics to add a myriad of them. Among those with a focus on childhood development, we can find the Russian psychologist Lev Vygotsky; in his essay, *The Role of Play in Development*, he identifies the play activities in children as one that is desired by the child. Involving an imaginary situation and a set of rules that might not be laying down in advance or are created as the game progress (Vygotsky 1978). Another example is the one of Kenneth Rubin in *Handbook of Child Psychology* (1983), who defines the custom of playing as one of intrinsic motivation, that focuses on meanings rather than ends, which separates itself from an exploratory behaviour, implying acting, being free from external constraints; and engaged by the participants (Sage, 2018). As we can see by these definitions, humans learn the meanings of play from childhood. Besides that, these definitions of early play behaviour in humans are aligned to Huizinga's and Caillois's definitions but also demonstrate that while play is innate to the human condition, the codes of play are learned and open to negotiation. In the same order of ideas, while play has been defined in many narratives as an act that is more appropriate to children than to adults, in the book *“Play for Life: Play Theory and Play as Emotional Survival”* Sutton-Smith (2017) argues that play is a response to our emotional system, that allows us to feel in control and still represent or our feelings of sadness, fear, disgust, anger, happiness, and surprise, And this approach continues in all life stages, to refine awareness of the human capability (Sutton-Smith 2017). Finally, play is understood better when the limits with their opposite are drawn. In this case, “Play” is not “Work” and so we find within the experience of being human that the *Homo Ludens*, finds itself in constant negotiation with its counterpart, the *Homo Faber*, as children and adults alike continuously seek to play as a form of emotional survival.

2.5.3 Serious Games and Gamification:

Serious Games (SGs) as a concept has evolved over time. Its roots can be traced to 1970s when they were first introduced by Clark Abt, with the intention to provide educational experiences through games, this way addressing the shortcoming of the American school system, by providing serious or casual opportunities and affordances for participation in various organizational or socio-political structures through their metaphors. He insisted that these games were not solely for amusement but a way to incentive students to learn (Abt, 1970). During that period serious games were made out of cardboard, however that period coincided with the dawn of computer games (see appendix F), so later in this period games like “Oregon Trail” a history game and “Lemonade Stand” (1973) a business simulation game appeared (Rawitsch, et al., 1971; Jamison, 1979), however, these games had technological limitations (Adamovic, 2021). Today SG is a field of study, and a concept that encompasses games that can be played with a purpose that goes beyond the simple pleasure of leisure, for example, informing, promoting health, training, educating, and instructing (Damaševičius, 2023). As seen in Silva (2019), immersive situations are at the core of serious games as they increase players motivation and provide context for the phenomena of Escapism, which in this context has to do with engaging with media that engross your senses and help you cope as a form of emotional survival (Stenseng, et al., 2021). she explains that Botte (2009) proposes a taxonomy of SGs that may be divided into three parts, the first is role-play, where situations may not borrow from situated realities, then we have Business games, where the situation take from realities aligned to the topic of any enterprise, and finally reality games, where all aspects of the game are based and dependent on reality (Silva, 2019). Core elements of serious games include a balance between the core components of a game and the seriousness the metaphor is trying to convey (Caserman, 2020), we can assume that the basic elements of a serious game are (see fig.13) i) a goal to act upon, ii) fun, compelling players to participate with the game and enter the magic circle, iii) to have play mechanics and clear scoring rules, iv) to provide the player with a takeaway, something they can incorporate into their lives (Cowan, 2017; Maugard, 2019).

Elements of Serious Games

Fig 13 Basic elements of serious games, based on Cowan (2017) and Maugard (2019). (Author, 2023)

In the section Game Theory (2.6.1) and section Theories of Play (2.62) we have explained what games are, how goal strategies can shape game experiences, principles of playing and what compels players to engage into the ludic experience underpinning the theory behind “i, ii, iv”.

For this we can understand that the takeaway is the scope that makes a game serious.

However, not everyone agrees that all games are made to allow the players’ outcome to be the one of learning and gaining skills for the real world. As the game philosopher Ian Bogost says, while games can be used for outcomes for the player related to learning and skill gaining, they are persuasive in a way different than the spoken word, and this attribute could be used for political, social or corporate scope through gamification (Ernst, 2023; Sharma, 2023).

The term gamification was first coined by Pelling in 2002, between the boundaries of computing interfaces, making experiences enjoyable due to the affordances of interactive media (Pelling, 2011). None the less while gamification is often attached to the interactive medium, as well its present in the analogue form, in classrooms, therapy rooms, corporate training rooms etc. as such gamification can be understood as the harnessing of human predisposition to play using game mechanisms (Larson, 2020). These game design elements could constitute points that are quite common to see on gamified experiences (idem). These might be awarded after the player completes a mission, for example, ranking leader boards that

measure and displays player success against one another, creating competition, or performance graphs, which are different from ranking leader boards because they do not normally compare players performance against others, but which measure performance against a set of goals over a limited time. Team-mates, even if they are synthetic agents can induce the player to cooperate or compete. Meaningful stories provide context and appeal to the emotions of the gamer (Costa, 2019; Larson, 2020). Avatars can give a sense of identity to the player and, in some cases, can be chosen or modified by the user, leading to self-identification (Jahn, 2021).

The main ideas of gamification are not new. A famous magical nanny phrases it as "In every job that must be done, there is an element of fun. You find the fun and SNAP! the job's a game." (*Mary Poppins*, 1964). Furthermore, two key gamification elements, badges and ranking, date at least back to the early 1900s where Boy Scouts could earn them by performing a task, creating community and identity, in a tradition that persists still today (Kim & Castelli, 2021). Many game philosophers have voiced their ethical concerns behind modern gamification techniques as a part of contexts directed to profits such as marketing and management tool to exploit the human compulsion to play (Thibault, 2019). These techniques are being successfully used for marketing and management (Thorpe, 2019; Larson, 2020). The application of game elements has also been used in domains that do not have monetary gains as main goal, for example gamification has been used to facilitate research, and to promote positive health outcomes (Damaševičius, 2023); in education, for attention improvement; in disabled students (García-Redondo P, 2019) or intervention that aim for the empowering vulnerable groups through skill training, behaviour support i.e. exergames for exercising, step counting etc. Games are also used for knowledge transferring, such as a website with gamification techniques to inform about rheumatoid arthritis, or others such as games for people with PTSD to have resilience over intrusive thoughts (Lubbe, 2021). In conclusion, if SGs are games with the purpose of finding a benefit for our lives by harnessing the power of play, then gamification is a technique that has the potential to help add engagement to necessary tasks, by intervening them and making them easier and more enjoyable.

2.5.4 Disability Gaming:

As we have seen in the past section to play is a human need as a tool for emotional survival. In this context to game as a pastime is everyone's right, as videogames have the potential to benefit to one's perceived wellbeing (Halbrook, et al., 2019; Johannes, 2021). 20% of gamers around the world identify as disabled (Ellis, 2019).

Published research related to the experience of disabled gamers is scarce. However, in 2020 a UK disability equality charity consulted a total of 812 disabled gamers (see table 1). 66% said they face barriers on issues related to gaming, the main issue being the price-tag of assistive technology. According to Scope (2020), people with disabilities find themselves in average with almost 600 pounds in additional expenses in the cost of living over other people. This unfair for the livelihood of gamers that happen to be disabled people.

Another common complaint was related to time or knowledge required to implement assistive technologies. 40% of those surveyed could not find assistive tech suitable to their needs, and finally many found that many games and consoles in the market presented incompatible software or hardware incompatible with their abilities for example, in applying colour contrast, subtitling options, adjusting sensitivity of the controllers, mouth operation, and eye tracking, among many others.

50% percent of those surveyed stated that not having enough information about the accessibility of a game has prevented them from buying it, as the information is not specific enough or is unavailable at time of purchase. If the game is incompatible with their needs, on many occasions they cannot reimburse their purchase, due to unclear communication.

Finally, 40% of those surveyed said that have found negative attitudes from another gamers, online and offline (Scope UK, 2020). These results highlight the issues disabled players face, by locating disabled gamers in society as consumers and as part of the gaming community. In built environments (real and digital) as physical and digital bodies, they want to flow through these

digital environments and interact in their own terms with assistive technology created for disabled gamers. As some note, one of the big issues is that many videogames glorify the ability to play and that on itself that is a problem (D4D, Disability and Community, 2021).

Table 1 Survey Results reflecting challenges disabled gamers face. (Scope, 2020)

However, in the last years we have seen an effort from many sectors to address barriers around gaming for disabled people. First by stablishing guidelines for game accessibility, directed to developers, covering a wide range of disabilities and strategies to make games accessible (GAAG, 2012) ,and the creation of internal policies and hardware such as accessible controllers to cater for the needs of disabled gamers (Microsoft, 2019). And charities advocating for disabled gamers and online communities diffusing specific information to players about what they could play i.e., (Can I play that?, 2022). However, while online gaming and e-sport communities have become more accessible in recent years cyber bullying persists (Christina & Reny, 2019; Dinansyah, et al., 2022). This is a problem, given that for many disabled people gaming is one of the few opportunities to socialize in leisure (Cairns, 2021).

2.6 The human who rites

As Noted by Helland and Kienzl (2022), in academia “Rituals” are studied under two pretences, one where rituals are defined universally, or those using specific case studies. The universally defined rituals discourse proposes a broad definition that, however, fails to recognise its own Christian-Western origins, being mostly discussed among white male dominated circles. The other side of the discourse provides narrow definitions, that are time and space fixed, and these perspective risks being too simplistic (Helland & Kienzl, 2022). Defining what a “Ritual” is a complex task: therefore I will introduce what this complex idea is using different perspectives. In his essay "Symbols in African Ritual", Victor Turner proposes that rituals are the performance of pre-set activities which occur in a secluded place, and these involves “words, objects and actions” (Turner, 1973 p.110) that mark life cycles and transition points to influence extraordinary beings or powers.

Similarly, as seen in Singh (2022), Turner sustains those rituals can be defined as "prescribed formal behaviour for occasions not given over to technological routine, having reference to beliefs in mystical beings and powers." (Geertz, 1973). His interpretation somehow understands in an objective manner the concept of rituals as a liminal space or transition, although he alludes to component such as formality, repetition, and symbolism. Yet Turner stirs the conversation alluding to elements belonging to the religious, the cosmic or the enchanted world; with this interpretation, he neglects a set of more everyday or functional ritual actions such as court hearings, or weddings. The before mentioned acts have effects that are axiomatic in nature and not based solely on religious or cosmic beliefs. Leach (1968) defines rituals as a form of social communication rooted in culturally defined behaviours (Singh, 2022).

In contrast, another vital definition comes from the American religious historian Jonathan Smith's book *"To Take Place: Toward Theory in Ritual"*. In this book, he maintains that "Ritual is, above all, an assertion of difference" (Smith, 1987, p. 109), where the social actors pay attention to their conduct, to what otherwise would be "empty" actions, void of meaning. In other words, these actions would be mechanical repetition, as a habit or a routine. He also establishes that space,

which is decided casually according to the preference of the social actors, enhances the attention towards the action (Idem). Although he recognizes the importance of the space, he also asserts that rituals are signifiers that mark spaces as sacred, but these are highly portable and do not mean anything in themselves. In synthesis, according to J. Z. Smith, rituals are a physical strategy used by the social actors to "signify" that some actions have more meaning, importance, or power than others. These actions create physical spaces of importance, a sense of place that enhances the rite, extrapolating rites beyond religion or the enchanted (idem).

Building upon the idea of "assertion of difference", as seen in Helland and Kienzl (2022), the American religious scholar Catherine Bell tries to define a ritual in a more universal and secular manner by means of the dynamics of "ritualization" (Bell, 1997), in an effort to distinguish some forms of rituals as more personal strategies detached from their relation to forms of control. About this, she says: "At a basic level, ritualization is the production of this differentiation. At a more complex level, ritualization is a way of acting that specifically establishes a privileged contrast, differentiating itself as more important or powerful. Such privileged distinctions may be drawn in a variety of culturally specific ways that render the ritualized acts dominant in status" (Bell, 2009, p. 90). From this excerpt, we can understand that rituals cross universal boundaries taking different shapes depending on the cultural context, and that these ritualized acts employ culturally specific strategies to differentiate themselves from other actions. To exemplify this, Bell draws a comparison between the Catholic eucharistic meal mimicking a regular family meal (ibid). According to Bell (2009), the eucharistic meal is a ritualistic action because while it draws from the idea of a big family gathering around the table for dinner, it differs in the acts being performed, such as the time intervals between which the action is performed, and the sufficiency of the food to provide any satisfaction.

In his book "*Homo Ritualis*", the German Indologist Axel Michaels provides a highly amalgamated definition of ritual, that serves in a way to separate rituals from other similar event that are conflated such as habits, routines etc. He does this by pointing at specific ritualistic dynamics. "The framed and structured performance of formalised, that is, repetitive, in principle public and

variable, action(s) or enactments in variable, intense modes with individually or socially elevating implications or qualities that transform or confirm the identity, role, status, or authority of participants and social groups" (Michaels, 2015, p. 32). With this definition he suggests that rituals are a form of stylized multimodal social or individual performance, as "enacting". Furthermore, he says that these acts are voluntary rather than routines, meaning these acts are performed with intensity or attention. These acts are also can be symbolic by defining transformation or reaffirmation of "identity, role, status or authority" but overall, there is a formal frame behind them, therefore these acts are not free, in the sense "play" is (see section 2.5.3).

When we think about rituals, an array of performative actions come to mind, from a small gesture such as bowing to more elaborated events such as seasonal offerings and sacrifices of the enchanted world. According to Richard Schechner, among others (Campbell, 2021), rituals in modern societies are ubiquitous and while many people equate rituals to the sacred, these are not only observed in human behaviour but also in modern media such as the internet or videogames (idem), and beyond the human spheres even animals living in the wild exhibit rites (Schechner & Brady, 2002) . This begs the question, what are the benefits for the individual of engaging in rituals? Or as a society, why we do rite? The wellness provided by rituals is multifaceted. Schechner in accordance with Turner and Michaels, asserts that rituals "arise around disruptive, turbulent and strongly ambivalent interactions." (Schnener, 1987, p. 5) . From this they serve as a liminal space, marking moments of transition. Other such as Briller and Sankar (2011) agree that rituals are powerful agents to help people confront the passing of time into "old age" and beyond. They conjoin society and add meaning to key moments, offering "order, continuity, predictability" (Briller & Sankar, 2011, pp. 6-10), or as Schechner (1987) puts it, getting people through difficult transactions around psychological or physiological needs, with minimum effort or damage. He suggests that these processes sublimate non socially accepted impulses into more socially conventional actions, for example "purifying violent acts" into actions that do not arouse retaliation and where society is the public of these performances (Schnener, 1987), recent studies both from secular and religious perspectives, provide evidence for the incorporation of

rituals in daily life, as a form of anxiety management and societal cohesion, even providing increased joy and meaning (Becker & Sangster, 2019; Baxter, et al., 2020; Lang, et al., 2020; Grønseth, 2021). In resume, communities and individuals alike use rituals in religious and secular life, as an assertion of difference between moments of transition, to face change and providing order, continuity and predictability as means to address psychological and physiological needs, many times ritualizing habits to reap the benefits of a ritual, depending on the context.

2.6.1 Routines and Habits, shades of consciousness

The importance of adopting a lifestyle around good habits are widely acknowledged in academic studies related to the generation of wellbeing (Arlinghaus & Johnston, 2019; Wood, 2019). Also, the importance of maintaining the service user's daily activity patterns as part of their care or support is documented (Schrader, et al., 2020; Arlinghaus & Johnston, 2018), and some maintain that mundane habits such as personal care, could be made into rituals, bringing positive wellbeing benefits later in life (Aulino, 2019). This is relevant to this thesis, because historically practice the habit of self-care has commonly relied on rituals given that through them, there is a reminding of the self and their personhood, providing purpose, and predictability when navigating the world, this in turn, creates a sense of wellbeing through self-reliance (Martínez, et al., 2021).

“Practice makes perfect” is an old expression used to encourage those who want to hone a skill. Routines are actions that are so well engrained in our psyche that can be performed with the investment of little energy and consciousness, helping individuals with the performance of daily activities (Du, et al., 2022). In contrast, while sometimes conflated (Kwon, 2022), habits differ from routines due to their structure (Arlinghaus & Johnston, 2018). At a basic level it is understood that habits are triggered by the need felt by an individual to act on a contextual cue (idem). Within the behavioural fields of knowledge, habits have been studied under the umbrella of the old concept known as “stimulus-response” model, where in this case a person gains certain mastery over their environment by repetition and learning, acting on trigger stimuli coming from the environment but also to satisfying specific inner motivations, “reinforcing” an action (Giesen,

et al., 2019). From this repetition we can understand that habits give way to routine behaviours to satisfy a need and act on an environmental stimulus, a model called the “habit loop” has been created to illustrate these phenomenon (Duhigg, 2014). However, habits are not an instrumental behaviour (see Fig.14).

Fig. 14 “Habit loop” as proposed by Duhigg (Author,2023)

An example of an instrumental behaviour is one where the goal is what drives the action (Perez, 2021), in other words by entering in your living room, if its dark and the lights are off, you might want to turn the lights on. You have entered these spaces many times and without giving it a thought, you coordinate the right arm and hand movements to turn the light switch on. However, if you find yourself in an unfamiliar space, and in a similar need of clarity, you wouldn’t know on what side of the door the switch is. This need triggers a “goal-directed” action where we would use more energy and attention to perform a task. By this, we can understand that habits are a series of compounded routines, that have been triggered by a need to receive a reward, where the recipient spend little energy and attention. Finally, as set out in the last section, being studied by many disciplines only makes rituals difficult to define, but maybe rituals cannot be understood as “one size fits all”, and as noted by Bell (1997), the best approach to understand rituals might be the one of symbolic interactionism, where they take energy and consciousness to perform,

the fluidity of their boundaries, their modularity and adaptability, are part of what rituals are at their core. Adapting their building blocks to vernacular language, time periods and endemic cultural symbolism, situations, and milieus, makes them able to find a privileged space of differentiation where the actors consciously and intentionally perform a given pattern of actions, taking in consideration the explanation we have made between, Ritual, Habit and Routine, The relationship between the three could also be understood in an spectrum where to perform Rituals more energy and focus are required than to perform a Routine, and at the bottom of the spectrum we can find Habits that take little energy and focus to perform (See Fig. 15).

Fig. 15 Visual representation of the relationship between Habits, Routines, Rituals (Author, 2023)

As a final note and as explained by Schechner (1976), in modern polite society, many of these ritualised small and subtle communication transactions take place, seamlessly inserted among our quotidian habits: with a handshake a person could be welcomed into a group, or with a head bow and a smile a person could be acknowledged, signifying their presence has been validated and their status shifted from unknown to known (Schechner, 1976). In previous sections I have illustrated how, in an ableist society, the life experience of a disabled person cannot be equally compared to those experiences of the body able. This inequality opens lines of enquiry, where the experiential commonalities of those with physical impairment in relation to rituals can be examined.

2.7 The medium is the reality

According to Marshall McLuhan in his book "Understanding Media: The Extensions of Man", the medium or technology of choice in some way amplify one's capabilities. According to him, "all technologies are extensions of our physical and nervous systems to increase power and speed" (McLuhan, 2013, p. 119), Introducing a new form of media creates new environments, having ramifications within our societies, changing our symbolic domains in unexpected ways, he explains that whenever society adopts a form of new media, it changes the way we interact with one another and the environment around us, the main idea is that the correlation between the changes produced in societies by any adopted medium or technology is greater than any content produced by that medium (ibid, p.19). He continues, "The medium is the message" because it is the medium that shapes and controls the scale and form of human association and action" - "Indeed, it is only too typical that the "content" of any medium blinds us to the character of the medium." (Ibid, p.22) also emphasising that the message of a medium is always another medium, and that media embeds itself in the very fabric of society, altering our societal processes and the way we look at ourselves and one another, and our interpersonal dynamics. Therefore, rather than altering just our lives in a tangible form, the medium is both the message by reforming intangible processes and the very nature of the content delivered by them.

In his book *The Medium is the Massage – An inventory of effects* (McLuhan, 1967), McLuhan describes how with the appearance of different types of mediums, the way we live is reshaped, advancing our societies. According to him, the rise of some forms of media can be linked to periods of growth and advancement in human history. In the text *The Gutenberg Galaxy* (McLuhan, 1962) he explains that before the invention of the written word, we lived an acoustic age, where orality was predominant, as individuals in our societies at the time were not familiar or had no technology or mediums of literacy. In those times, our societies relied on co-presence to communicate, and used mainly speech and sound to convey ideas making the ear the predominant organ, in another account, he also asserts "Until writing was invented, man lived in

acoustic space: boundless, directionless, horizonless, in the dark of the mind, in the world of emotion, by primordial intuition, by terror. Speech is a social chart of this bog." (McLuhan, 1967, p. 29), And he continues to explain that with the arrival of the written word, "It abolished mystery; it gave architecture and towns; it brought roads and armies, bureaucracy. It was the basic metaphor with which the cycle of civilisation began, the step from the dark into the light of the mind. The hand that filled the parchment page built a city." (ibid, p. 29) This meant that the era where co-presence was needed to communicate ideas was over, and we moved to the age of literacy, and by turning sound into visible items, the written word became more credible as we did not need the unreliable memory to keep track of history or events, the act of reading and interpreting text made us more individual as those who could read and came to be those who controlled the flow of information and knowledge acquiring power over those who couldn't. The print information age arose with its ability to mass-produce the commodity of the printed page with the invention of the printing press. It allowed for people to read on their own and allowed for communities to exchange common symbols with one another, solidifying societies by the quicker transfer of language and nationalistic ideas and made the eyes the predominant organ and books an extension of such eyes. The printed device "confirmed and extended the new visual stress. It provided the first uniformly repeatable "commodity," the first assembly line—mass production." (McLuhan, 1967, p.50). With the invention and adoption of the telegraph, we moved to the electric information age, this age saw the invention of the Radio and the Television. moving to the new electronic age, in an interview, he says, "If the wheel is an extension of feet and tools of hands and arms, then electromagnetism seems to be in its technological manifestations an extension of our nerves and becomes mainly an information system." (McLuhan, 1966) He thought this new age of electronic media was more powerful because it dematerialised and dispersed communication; it encouraged participation and unified people. It could stimulate many senses at once and had a "retribalizing" effect on societies, redefining the boundaries of "here" and "there", bending time and space, this way globalising the world.

Marshall McLuhan was not present to appreciate the proliferation of the internet, bringing upon us the digital age. It would have been difficult or nearly impossible for him to forecast the effect

this would have in society, and even for us as we are going through this process, we cannot see the final form of this epoch, but today we can see the internet and smart devices are the dominant media, encompassing every type of media that came before. On relation to this he forecasted "the next medium, whatever it is — it may be the extension of consciousness — will include television as its content, not as its environment, and will transform television into an art form." (McLuhan, 1997, p. 210). At the time consumer computers were scarce, and few could afford them. Therefore, it was not possible to predict a future in which the global village would share information with the immediacy of today's internet, but he left us a tetrad, (tool created by McLuhan to analyse media effect). In a section called "*Angels to Robots: From Euclidean Space to Einsteinian Space*" of his book "*Global Village*", saying that... "A computer as a research and communication instrument could enhance retrieval, obsolesce mass library organisation, retrieve the individual's encyclopaedic function and flip into a private line to speedily tailored data of a saleable kind" (McLuhan & Powers, 1989, p. 143). The idea of retrieving information "into a speedy private line with saleable content" sounds very similar to the internet and the social media we know today.

Every new type of media brings exciting new possibilities and affordances, but McLuhan warned that "Control over change would seem to consist in moving not with it but ahead of it. Anticipation gives the power to deflect and control force." (McLuhan, 2013, p. 257). With this quote we can understand that before the arrival of a new form of media, it could also change our environment in a damaging manner, and he asserts that we should move ahead of it and channel it for the benefit of society.

2.7.1 The road towards the metaverse

As explained in the last section, the media technology has the power of augment human capabilities enhancing our power and speed, and with every new medium type also come changes to our societies, shaping them after its form and characteristics, where every new technology is more important than the message it carries, as the message can distract from the medias true impact in our way of living. The Metaverse can be defined as a post-reality medium

where other forms of media converge, seamlessly merging physical reality with the digital world, with interconnected virtual spaces, with its own economies and governance (Mystakidis, 2022). This way creating a network of interconnected cross-realities (XR), where people can learn, work and play (idem). In this medium, internet technologies merge with XR, and through immersive media people can interact with one another following rules like those found within the tridimensionality of the physical world (Murray, 2020). In this set of digital realities, instead of their own bodies, users inhabit digital avatars and interact with one another in a meaningful and life-like manner, simulating face to face encounters, even if the users are not within the same physical spaces, in this world users can create and have an input in the evolution of the metaverse (idem), this space represent an emerging brave new world of opportunities for people with disabilities inclusion in the fields of content creation, exploration, wellbeing etc. (Radanliev, 2023).

Following this, given that Immersive VR is a medium that has the potential to contain computer media in its simulation form and the internet as a tool for information retrieval and distribution, we can explore the "Form" of the virtual reality medium by exploring the relationship of "virtuality" (Simulation of the real) that exists between human and images and how this relationship can create phenomena such as Immersion through the illusory transformation of what is perceived as real (Rauschnabel, et al., 2022). I will first trace back how VR came to be and how this relationship has evolved, to then be conceptualised as spatial Immersion, which can be defined as the perception of the reality around the viewer being affected (Augmented Reality: AR) or transformed (immersive Virtual Reality: VR).

VR is a term for computer-generated audio-visual media which can be interacted with by the user in real-time, typically using a head-mounted display (HMD), creating the illusion for the viewer of placement in a different space to the one he or she is currently inhabiting, always anchored in "the real" (Rauschnabel, et al., 2022). This sense of immersion and emotions associated with digital technologies is an illusory phenomenon that predates the dawn of what we understand as computer graphics. The idea of perceiving alternative realities has been around since the

ancient Greeks (Harris, 2022). Plato sparked the discussion around human concepts of reality and perception with "The Allegory of the Cave", where he narrates the story of a group of prisoners that have been forced since birth to face one wall of the said cave, unable to turn their heads, the prisoners could only perceive a vision of animals and humans representing the world, through the flickering shadows projected by a light source further back to them. While imprecise representations of reality, they interpreted these shadows as real. As a result, the prisoners have no wish to leave the cave, as they do not know there is more to the world. Because the passing shadows they individuate in the wall is all they know (idem).

As discussed in chapter in the section 1.5, the history of immersive media within the field of computer graphics started with the "Ultimate display" (Sutherland, 1965). The sense of spatial immersion, however, is not new. Throughout the history of art, people have sought to create an essential relationship to images, which can also be described as Virtuality (Grau, 2007). Nowadays, we, as mainstream media consumers, tend to associate "virtuality" with the new dawn of computer graphics. However, Grau (2007) argues that within the timeline of Western art, there is a portion of artistic practice that has used painting to create a transformation of the location to place the viewer at the centre of a virtual scene. see the comparison of the old technology (Fig.16) with the new technology (Fig.17).

Fig.16 *Villa dei Misteri - Pompei* (Pagani, 2019)

Fig.17 *The Cave Automatic Virtual Environment* (Davepape, 2001)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

From Roman wall paintings to the nineteenth-century panoramas, Grau (2007) traces the origin of our relation to the immersive virtual media and its effect on us as viewers to these diorama-like pieces:

"...the idea of installing an observer in hermetically closed-off image space of illusion did not make its first appearance with the technical invention of computer-aided virtual realities. On the contrary, virtual reality forms part of the core of the relationship of humans to images." (*Grau, 2007, p. 163*)

In line with this idea within the baroque period, the "Trompe-l'œil" (See Fig.18) a perspective illusory painting technique, used realistic imagery to give the impression that the painting is in three dimensions, similar illusory phenomena can be observed in other disciplines such as cinematography & architecture where "Forced Perspective" is used to trick the viewer (Margarete, 2018) . When dealing with immersive art, we should appreciate this comparison between a fresco and the "CAVE" system (Cruz-Neira, et al., 1993), which was inspired in Plato's "Allegory of the Cave"; while technologically different, and a hundred years apart, these two types of media create Immersion. However, they do so through different technologies – different media.

Fig. 18: *Trompe-l'oeil mural metro*, Morelos, Mex., Mexico (CC, John Pugh 2016)

2.7.2 The fundamentals of Immersion in VR:

Immersion is a multifaceted term with debated meanings (Agrewal, et al., 2020) . I am not seeking to add to this debate, but to discuss how immersion is created, departing from two concepts: Presence and Flow. For this, I borrow and clarify terms from psychology, media, Human-computer interaction (HCI), and videogame design. For the experience of immersion to occur in VR, the technology relies on different types of tracking (head, body, room etc.), mediating interaction with the virtual world and in turn generating different subjective responses to the viewer/user and these media artificially input data to our sensorimotor channels (Gibbs, et al., 2022). The subjective experiences of vision, sound, are expected and judged by our senses, eliciting the illusion that we are somewhere else (ibid). These phenomena are very personal

experiences that lead to realistic behaviour "in" the virtual setting (Pan & Hamilton, 2018). In this section, I will now name the concepts and describe the phenomena found in Virtual Reality that compose the illusion of immersion, giving examples from the non-digital and the digital.

Gardner (1983) explains that in written media, the reader experiences the phenomena of "Psychic distance", which he defines as the "distance that the reader feels between himself and the events of the story" (Gardner, 1983, p. 111) . In other words, the written media has the downside that it places the reader far away from the characters point of view; providing little explanation about a scene or characters could advance the plot. i.e., "*in the dark, they walked toward the intruders*" (Author, 2021). Nevertheless, to provide a comprehensive description of the surrounding of a given scene, and the thoughts and feelings of the characters subjective point of view, the reader can be brought closer to the perspective of the character and further engage the reader into the story. i.e., "Cloaked by the shadows, they stealthily closed on the intruders; with their hearts pounding, their minds were consumed with anticipation" (Author, 2021), as per this example, more detailed passages help us conceptualise the gap of perspective between the reader and the perspective of the character, where higher levels of details can help readers feel closer to the story (Gardner, 1983). Nonetheless, this gap cannot be closed employing traditional media, as we are constantly reminded that these thoughts and views are not unique to us but belong to the narrator. A similar term, "psychological distance" is a construct used in other fields such as computing games and psychology, to identify the psycho-social-spatial distance of objects and events surrounding people i.e., attitudes towards climate change (Maiella, 2020; Fox, et al., 2020). The Qualia epiphenomena are the conjunction of subjective first-person experiences, unique to each of us, as lived through our senses while performing an activity (Jackson, 1982). These collections of subjective thoughts, emotions, sensations, and perceptions that belong to somebody when living an experience will not be the same to somebody else, this way creating an "Explanatory Gap" (Levine, 1983), as it's the case with "psychic distance" and "psychological distance".

This philosophical gap between knowledge and experience cannot be closed with traditional media, but it can be bridged with VR through the conscious experience of “presence” (Xie, et al., 2021; Yung, et al., 2020). The qualia of presence are the most basic phenomenological and psychological sense of Immersion (Barfield, et al., 1995). It is the subjective sensation of being aware of our physical or digital environment while feeling a part of it, in other words it's the feeling of just existing. This state of consciousness creates the figurative place transformation to create the illusion of being somewhere else. Based on his observations, Slater argues that for the sense of presence to occur, two spatial illusions must take place, "Place Illusion" (Pi) and "Plausibility Illusion" (Psi) (Slater, et al., 2022).

"Pi" has to do with how the world is perceived. For this to happen, we as viewers need two essential factors. The first factor is a 3D stereoscopic display, the second one is a whole field of view (180 degrees, 360 degrees), and the third one is head & position tracking. This includes the experience quality of self-location within the frame of reference the virtual world provides (idem). "Psi" is about what is perceived in this world as probable. i.e., social interactions, or physics (idem). We can find other fascinating examples about the Immersion's effects of presence through the relationship of images and humans in Grau's arguments, where he discusses the idea of "Obedience through presence", analysing the panorama of "The Battle of the Sedan" by Anton von Werner (Grau, 2007):

After winning the battle, the Prussian rulers chose to capture the event in a 7000 square feet painting, creating it with the purpose of being exhibited on Alexander Platz in Berlin (1883). Grounded on the optical and physiological concepts of Hermann von Helmholtz, it was designed entirely as propaganda for public viewing. This was a genius achievement for both inception and execution artfully, creating a sense of patriotism and respect for the new German Kaiserdom that echoed throughout the country (Ibid, See Fig.19).

Fig. 19 Battle of Sedan immersive mural (Werner, 1883)

If the illusions within presence have to do with our surroundings, the Body Ownership illusion has to do with our perception of our virtual body and the illusion of ownership of that virtual body; This sensation makes bodily sensations seem unique to oneself (Slater, et al., 2022). A classic example of this is the Rubber hand illusion (Botvinick & Cohen, 1998). It has been claimed that immersive VR can recreate this sensation. VR makes it so that the user accepts the virtual representation of herself to the point of recognising as accurate the visuotactile stimulus to their avatar or changing the perception they have of people from different races by embodying an avatar with different skin colour, creating empathy towards them and reducing the implicit racial bias (Pan & Hamilton, 2018). The same occurred when people with no colour deficiency were induced in VR simulation where participants who experienced colour-blindness were more likely to help real colour-blind people (T. I. Chowdhury, 2021). This experiment has a playful side, where inhabiting bodies and experiencing this immersion is a form of mimicry play within Caillois's psychological attitudes and principles of games. Furthermore, such an embodiment illusion can be so convincing that it elicits "Homuncular Flexibility". Jaron Lanier (2017) how humans could map their movements to lobster avatars in a non-1-1 limb ratio with relative ease. This means that users can learn to control bodies different than their own by changing the correspondence between tracked and rendered motion. (Lin, et al., 2019; Osborne & Jones, 2022).

For many empirical psychologists researching human-computer interaction (HCI) as seen in Ikwunne and Hederman (2022), engagement is "a category of user experience characterised by attributes of challenge, positive affect, endurance, aesthetic and sensory appeal, attention, feedback, variety/novelty, interactivity, and perceived user control" (O'Brien, 2016). In the field

of video game development, this involvement of consciousness is referred to as “Immersion”, when immersed and individual attention is engrossed in the task at hand, suppressing any other external stimuli (Leroy, 2021). According to the Game Experience Model (GEM), Immersion in the field of videogames is typically divided into four categories: “sensory-motoric immersion”, “cognitive immersion”, “emotional immersion”, and “spatial immersion” (Suovuo, et al., 2020), this way providing what is known as “escapism into media (Kamm, 2020).

Sensory-motoric immersion: This involves tactile operations and has to do with performing actions, i.e., pressing a set of buttons in an unbeaten, timely sequence to achieve a goal, challenging the player to achieve mastery of the sequence. Cognitive immersion: this is the mental challenge component, Learning or developing solutions, i.e., Strategy or Tactic. Emotional Immersion is the construction of narratives, presentation of conflict / Solutions and characters. Spatial immersion: it is the real-time exploration of the virtual 3D space, even when experiencing a non-immersive VR game.

As just shown, spatial immersion belongs to the qualia of presence, but to exist in the virtual world is not good enough to make us want to stay. Then what makes us stay in the virtual world? - “Flow” or task immersion is a state of consciousness where one feels “in the zone” as if finding meaning and enjoying said task, bending people’s perception of time and making them go to any length to pursue it (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990). Social psychologist Mihalyi Csikszentmihalyi proposes that for flow to occur several different conditions must be met. The objectives must be clear and match the abilities of the person, but also provide immediate the feedback in terms of rewards or failure: this is because the course of action can be changed if needed, providing a sense of agency and equilibrium between the challenge at hand and the set of skills of the user (ibid). Another characteristic is that within the activity there is opportunity for focus and concentration meaning that distractions or worries disappear within this state and the activity is an end on itself and is intrinsically gratifying (idem). According to Csikszentmihalyi (2008) the most enjoyable moments in people’s lives are not times of relaxation or restful repetition, but the moments where we lose ourselves in a task. Flow state can be observed in both work

activities and playing activities (Csikszentmihalyi, 2008). When the “flow” state is achieved through gaming, it has been linked with effects of flourishing and wellbeing (Tse, 2022). In the case of immersive VR, we can conclude that Cognitive and Emotional immersion belong to the qualia of Flow, where the player or viewer can find engaging visual stories and challenges to keep him interested. Finally, sensory-motoric immersion connects presence and flow, creating the experience through the perception of the user.

2.7.3 VR benefits for wellbeing

Historically, many researchers have explored the immersive frontiers for the possibility to improve people’s health and wellbeing, integrating immersive VR within different fields (Wilson, et al., 1997; Jack, et al., 2001; Laver, et al., 2017; Lee, 2019). As seen in previous sections, immersive VR has become a tool for researchers due to the affordance of this media for constructing life-like scenarios and situations, creating test conditions eliminating external interferences. This illusion of “presence” can induce different valences of emotional responses from users, and responses to the sensory stimuli in Virtual Worlds can be compared to those experienced in the real world, furthermore, the human body can be mapped into the virtual world, producing the “embodiment” illusion, heightening the illusory transformation of location. Moreover, it is claimed that emotions reproduced through the personal experiences in VR can elicit a sense of engagement that goes beyond the real world (Pan & Hamilton, 2018).

In this section, I will review recent studies that have been used to improve health and wellbeing using VR, including studies in which VR has successfully helped researchers make advancement in the manner this media can positively influence human health and wellbeing. I will introduce some sociological concepts pertinent to my research and give examples of research done in each subfield, starting with social cognition. Social cognition theory revolves around how humans can perceive, interpret, store, and apply information about social occurrences and others (Schunkl & DiBenedetto, 2020), using avatar embodiment to understand other people’s realities, has been applied in multiple studies to explore elicited empathy, leading to positive results, suggesting the reduction of negative biases towards the “other” (Tassinari, 2022). In ecological psychology

studies have explored the wellbeing effects of VR in people's moods and focus, e.g. in Mattila (2020), one hundred participants were exposed to as little as 5 min of immersive forest exposure, and the results suggest that the intervention had a positive effect in mental restoration and affect, contributing to their sense of wellbeing (Mattila, et al., 2020). Another similar study where participants were exposed for 8 minutes, shows the safety of VR interventions and positive result in positive mood changes, feeling excited and enthusiastic with adult participants with Cognitive and/or Physical disabilities, participants did not exhibit negative side effects, dizziness, orientation confusion or hearing aids issues (Rutkowski, et al., 2020).

Jeremy Bailenson (2018), says that VR can be used for training and exercising, allowing the user to practice and gain "mental representations" (mental maps) knowing what to expect by "chunking" the necessary skills giving the ability to automatise processes to deliver actions more effectively (Bailenson, 2018). VR capabilities for training and exercising have branched into studies dedicated to understand how to combine VR with cognitive-motor interventions for rehabilitation, having as a target demographic the elderly and people who had an stroke resulting in a disability (Park J-S, 2020). In a systematic review of randomised control trials, were VR-based (Interventions (Games) /Training (Exercise)) tasks combined with traditional rehabilitation on cognition, motor function, mood, and activities of daily living (ADL) after chronic stroke where implemented and compared against regular rehabilitation. Results compared against those in control groups, showed that VR-based interventions had better outcomes in attention and execution of task, overall cognition, and mood. However the results for VR-Based Training against a control group did not show any significant betterment in motor function, global cognition and ADL (Gao, et al., 2021), However, bigger and better designed trials are needed (Idem).

VR can also be used for memory rehabilitation, as it has shown potential for people who had strokes, people with dementia and Alzheimers. This has been done with the introduction of reminescence therapy, which involves a generally a conversation with the participants to affect their memory, integrated with the use of immersive media, showing imagenery and sound to enhance thair capacity to remember trough emotional conections, affecting their perceived

wellbeing positively even when compared with other traditional 2D media (D’Cunha, 2019; Mancuso, et al., 2023; Tominari, 2021).

Serious Games has been used for therapeutic and game-exercise purposes in VR, in both cases games can make physical and cognitive rehabilitation, or pain during exercises more manageable and engaging, showing that serious games interventions for therapy are as positive as non passive intervention to help recover executive functions (Abd-Alrazaq, 2022; Park J-S, 2020), however, some note that there can be also negative effects related to motion sickness with off the shelf games used for this purpose (Park & Lee, 2020), in contrast others note the lack of enough therapy games made for therapy purposes, addressing different needs (Ahmad, 2020). In this section I have shown the potential of VR for inexpensive, non pharmacological intervention for the promotion of health and wellbeing, in the next section I wish to explore gaps I have found in the literature.

2.8 Trust: invaluable currency within interpersonal relationships for research purposes.

In this section I survey trust theories and studies related to the scope of this thesis, as trust is the angular stone for user-centred design, building trust with informers and participants is paramount for frank and open conversations and relationships (Solarino, 2020). Trust is a dynamic of social relationships. It glues modern society and it is at the core of the establishment and flourishing of human relationships (Schilke, 2021). While trust poses the possibility to build connections having access to other people’s knowledge, help and guidance, it can also lead to vulnerability. Trust is maintained by the idea of each part maintaining their end of the bargain; its opposite is trust erosion by betrayal, posing a vulnerability to this relationship (Idem).

According to Schickele al (2021) trust studies can be summarized into two silos. First there is “General trust”. This has to do with trusting other people independently of their situation,

taking into consideration attitudes such as faith in the goodwill of others and the fact that humankind is benevolent in nature (Goldberg, 2020), or the moralistic principle that others can be worth of our trust (ibid), as seen in McLeod (2020) that can be studied as a personality trait maybe due the motivation of the trustee to be trustworthy and maintain relationships (Hardin, 2002), or culturally occurring in diverse societies as the base of morality (Baier, 2004). Second, we have, “particularized trust” also called in other literature “social trust” (Siegrist, 2019). Studied under the premise of situations of high social uncertainty, it does not focus on assessing individuals’ disposition to determine trustworthiness. However, it does rely on the assessment of the broader context and relationships between trustor and trustee, such as, history of past interaction, reputation, and expectations of future interactions (Schilke, 2021).

The “TORI” framework created by Gibbs (1972), created to illustrate the benefits of creating an environment based on trust. It stands for Trust, Openness, Realization, and Interdependence. Where the growth of the community starts with every individual dealing with his fears and choosing to trust, finding a place and an activity in the group that resonates within him, taking ownership of his experiences and realising the impact of his actions with empathy, and promoting connection, this way forgetting roles and positions. This trust would flow towards the community and cascade into openness. This is about self-awareness: understanding one’s feelings, what we want, and what we know, allowing this information to flow. The next step in the cascade is realization. In this step people find meaning in the interaction with one another, engaging in production that matters to them. This leads to the last step, interdependence, means that people find synergy and functioning is high within the community. Communities find their functioning deeply intertwined with trust. The more trust, the better communities’ function, finding themselves diminished by the absence of trust (Gibb, 1972).

2.9 Gaps and research opportunities of interest:

To satisfy the aims and objectives of this thesis, I have identified the broader themes of Disability, Health & Wellbeing, and Virtual Reality. Virtual Reality is a new form of media, and its broad horizons are ready for exploration. In the following subsection I would like to identify the

weaknesses and gaps in the knowledge I have encountered. While this might not be explored for reasons related to time and funding, these open new lines of enquiry and meet the scope of this exploratory research.

While the survey of the literature related to natural landscapes and meditative experiences overall result suggest that participants to the respective studies benefited from restoration of their attention, at the beginning of this study there was no description in the literature of the creation of this combined experience in the immersive media and its deployment in a disabled community as a form health and wellbeing activity. The current investigation seeks to experiment with forms of co-creation, and co-development in a consultation cycle with a disabled community to create experiences that might benefit them.

Serious games in disability are an ever-evolving field of research. However, most of the literature on play focuses on children, in comparison a relatively limited amount of work has been done with communities of disabled adults and in the non-medical care of the elderly. Furthermore, immersive serious games could be used for the exploration around benefits and attitudes around physical and cognitive therapy in a disabled community or used in creative ways to combat isolation a very regular issue during the current pandemic. While all these topics are very interesting, in this research I have experimented with co-creation and co-development methods and through this iterative consultation I have created an immersive experience where participants can have the adventure to visit distant lands and use their vision to hunt for requested items.

There is a breadth of research related to the avatar embodiment illusion, however the systematic reviews I have found revolve around the abled body (Mottelson, 2023). The VR embodiment illusion has been implemented to explore social aspects of the human experience through the lens of social cognition. In subjects as mental health, race, and disability. In contrast the current discourse fails to explore avatar virtual embodiment and social cognition attached to it from the disabled-body perspective. Within this section I have identified the

themes revolving around the present research project, providing enough information to explore worlds with disabled communities. In the following section I will survey the methods and methodologies implemented during this research process.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Introduction and overview:

This study is an exploration of a disabled community in Paisley using a qualitative ethnographic design approach and an inductive strategy to access their situated knowledge. In this chapter, I will restate the research questions, describe the methodological approach, and justify my choices. As previously discussed, Virtual Reality (VR) has advanced rapidly since its resurgence in 2015 and can be used as a tool to enhance the health and wellbeing of people with disabilities. The primary purpose of this investigation is to explore this potential, while the secondary purpose is to gain a deeper understanding of the relationship between the virtual and real worlds and the broader cultural implications of these technologies on the lives of people with disabilities. Our goal is to make immersive technology more accessible and inclusive for people with disabilities, with a commitment to co-creation and involving them in the design process. This approach results in both research tools and artifacts that are a product of this collaboration. Ultimately, our aim is to promote the proper implementation of VR in disabled communities, integrating it into existing support and leisure interventions and providing more choice to those who can benefit from it. These purposes are addressed by the following research questions.

RQ.1: What is the relationship between the virtual agency afforded by immersive technologies and the experience and restricted agency of living with a disability?

RQ.2: What are the cultural benefits derived from the insertion of VR in this community?

RQ.3: How can immersive media be integrated as part of the services disabled communities provide?

RQ.3a: What creative and production processes are behind creating an immersive experience tailored for a service centre such as the DRC.?

Having restated the research questions, I summarise the various points of discussion encapsulated within this chapter. In (3.1), the introductory section not only reframes the topic within the methodology chapter, but also provides rationale for the different approaches within this inquisitive endeavour. (3.2) describes the research sample, while (3.3) offers an overview of the required information. (3.4) addresses the research design, (3.5) explains the methods of data collection, and (3.6) provides an account of data analysis and synthesis. (3.7) discusses ethical considerations, (3.8) explores issues of trustworthiness, and (3.9) delves into limitations of the study in terms of methodology. Finally, (3.10) offers a summary of the chapter.

3.1.1 Rationale for Qualitative Research approach:

Qualitative research design is a versatile investigatory modality that adopts a constructive philosophical perspective, to elucidate how intricate social phenomena are construed, understood, and experienced, typically occurring within a specific context or timeframe (Dale & Volpe, 2018). The qualitative researcher collects information of meaningful moments in people's lives, through various data types such as interviews, photographs, observations, and field notes among others, gaining insights into attitudes, behaviours, value systems, culture among other markers that make the human experience. The researcher emphasis is on deciphering phenomena in their natural milieu, making sense of these snapshots with the meaning people see rather than the researchers (Mays & Pope, 2000). Seeking to achieve a rich and holistic understanding of the topic rather than a reductionist one (Denzin & Lincoln, 1984; Denzin & Lincoln, 2003). While qualitative research design can have its limitations (see section 3.8), it also possesses notable strengths. Subjects and Issues can be explored comprehensively. It also presents the ability to guide and redirect interviews in real time, making them flexible and adaptative depending on the scenario. The research framework can be adapted to new emerging information. It can also construct compelling narratives drawn from harnessing human experiences. It does this by considering subtleties and complexities that might unveil further lines of enquiry that might be missed by positivistic approaches (Anderson, 2010). As a researcher I believe that relying solely on quantitative methods to undertake this endeavour would not probably yield the nuanced comprehension needed to fulfil the objectives of this

project, therefore I have opted to base this research mainly in qualitative methods. The study's key characteristics are firstly, the exploration of factors that control interactions in this context, secondly, the ability to foster contextual understanding, thirdly the promotion of naturally occurring interactions between researcher and the institution members, fourthly a perspective of interpretation and uncovering of meaning, and finally using research framework flexibility and grounded forms of enquiry.

3.1.2 Rationale for exploratory ethnographic approach:

From this project beginning, it was clear that within the framework of qualitative approaches the study required an ethnographic research design. Ethnography is a flexible method of enquiry to gain deep knowledge about a group within its cultural context, but also a product that describes them, focusing on behaviours, typical day-to-day patterns, and human thought (Fetterman, 1998). As a methodology modality this allows for the exploration of socio-cultural phenomena occurring in communities (Denzin & Lincoln, 1984; Merriam, 1998), allowing for the recollection of culturally specific and contextual rich data over a period of time, and its recorded on the site where this meaningful interactions occur in a naturalistic manner, ethnography is dialogic as the community under study can potentially have access to the ethnographic material and provide feedback (Angrosino, 2007). Conducting this research methods comes with many advantages. Firstly, ethnographies are longitudinal forms of historical recording, meaning that changes in the community can be traced. Secondly ethnographies can produce detailed rich data, in the tradition of thick description, where social actions are recorded with physical behaviours adding a layer of subjective explanations that could help outsiders grasp the meaning brought in by the people (Geertz, 1973). Thirdly the data is collected in the natural setting and with an insider perspective allowing for a deeper conceptual understanding. Last, it has the power to give a voice to underrepresented or marginalised groups (Wolcott, 1999). Data collection takes three forms in this form of seeing, a) observation: in this modality the researcher while enjoying an insider perspective also takes professional distance to engage in the perception of social interactions, activities and

interactions with the field setting (Angrosino, 2007; Fetterman, 1998), b) interviewing: as the form of conversational enquiry (Angrosino, 2007), c) archival research: the analysis of official or unofficial material (idem).

Because of the novelty of immersive media, this research is exploratory in nature. Stebbins defines this type of research as exploration. "Social exploration is a broad-ranging, purposive, systematic prearranged undertaking designed to maximize the discovery of generalizations leading to description and understanding" (Stebbins, 2001, p. 3). The purpose of any exploratory investigation is to become acquainted with an unresearched or new phenomenon that is not well understood. It covers an extensive range of methodologies, such as formal and informal qualitative approaches, recognizing the explorer's subjectivity—using inductive reasoning (Heit, 2010), creating generalizations, rather than confirmation or problem-solving. To clarify the dimensions of said phenomena and explore new lines of inquiry at a later stage, the created knowledge, in turn, can lead to the creation of theory or hypotheses to study the issue further (Stebbins, 2011). According to Walliman (2017), exploratory research needs to state its intentions by describing the 'subject' and 'scope' of the issue that can be obtained from the studied phenomenon, and then suggest the 'method of approach' while highlighting the product of this process (Walliman, 2011). For this reason, I will restate the intent of this research.

This project intends to understand the relationship between immersive media and the subjective wellbeing experienced after these encounters by members of a disability resource centre located in Paisley and to understand the possible practical applications of immersive media in a community such as the DRC. For this reason, I am looking at the effects of immersive VR on their "health and wellbeing" by analysing the community's engagement with immersive media. For this purpose, I am using immersive VR to understand how it could be used as an alternative to the services regularly provided by the DRC—intending to interpret if they experience a mood improvement leading to good health and wellbeing or if there will be no significant difference in these individuals' self-reported health and well-being. While the goal

here is to understand the correlation between immersive media and quality of life, rather than adopting a problem-solving approach, a secondary scope of this project is to record and translate the cultural benefits recorded through the ethnographies, in the hope that these findings become helpful information for the implementation of immersive VR media into other similar institutions. To gain the insights of others and identify existing knowledge, I also engaged with literature related to my research as my secondary research.

These explorations engage in two other approaches to produce primary data. The main one is ethnographies, where I will be engaged in compiling information about the daily life at the DRC, where I have taken field notes and pictures, and then summarized it into a diary of ethnographic findings; I had chosen this modality as it fits the context (Creswell & Poth, 2013). There is also a practice-based element, where the researcher creates a piece of artwork, i.e., photography, painting, music, video game, and uses it to drive the research in an experimental manner (Candy, 2006).

3.1.3 Rationale for Participatory Action Research approach:

The core of this study is an exploration of people using immersive media to improve the health and wellbeing focused on physically disabled service users at the DRC; with the secondary aim to find routes of sustainable implementation within the services or sessions provided by the centre. For this reason, hearing the views and opinions of the DRC community at the core of my research design. Therefore, the guiding principle of this intervention is Participatory Action Research (PAR), this approach is focused on the community, therefore we could also call it community-based action research, (CBPAR) as design wise all stakeholders participate and become co-researchers as they voices are heard. Nonetheless, issues such as the meaning of the topic and Collaboratory equity are heated points of debate (Suarez-Balcazar, 2020). These types of approaches are seen as the gold standard to address health, and wellbeing and participatory differences experienced by marginalised groups (idem). As discussed by Barbara Schneider (Schneider, 2012) , Participatory Action Research originates with its northern and southern

traditions. PAR was championed by Kurt Lewin, who conceived it as “Action Research”, the northern tradition of PAR, providing it with the democratic dynamics and cyclical aspects of its methodology (see Fig.20 for a PAR example used for this research).

Fig. 20 Participatory Action Research Cycle, interpreted by Author (2020)

On the other side, influenced by Marxist theory, the southern tradition provided an aspect of knowledge-creation through the gaze of the oppressed. This process, in turn, creates a dynamic where academic knowledge is created through the perspective and participation of those who had been socially subjugated, also provided by the tensions of these interventions with ‘food for thought, granting them with the mental capital to make considerations on their own position, provoking societal change as a result of the newly found agency, these traditions finding among its champions Paulo Freire, Orlando Fals Borda & Mohammad Rahman (Schneider, 2012; Wakeford & Sanchez Rodriguez, 2018). While PAR provides benefits of collaboration and action, other issues arise from the power interplay, or authenticity when representing their lives of others. When creating media and text “with communities”, especially working with challenged communities and the production of cultural media artefacts, the report on the artefact's positive impact can sometimes be inflated (Jeffery & Kelly, 2016).

In the tradition of the disability rights movement *slogan* “*Nothing About Us Without Us!*” and as Schneider points out, it’s my duty as a researcher to strive for the inclusion in my work of the views of the impaired, to empower them to voice their thoughts and make their own choices. For this reason, I have designed a system where the consultation of this community takes centre stage in a ‘people-based inquiry’ for the creation of knowledge with the incorporation of three different blueprints for research, that allowed me to navigate this matter with a system of methods that borrows from three approaches: descriptive, ethnological & simulation (Walliman, 2011).

I would like to explain this by surveying these methods taking from Walliman (2011). Ethnological methods are a collection of qualitative approaches which rely on the observation of people. It takes place in the natural environment or setting of the studied community, emphasizing the need to contextualize the actions of social actors. The challenge of this approach is that for an external observer trying to understand the meaning of social, the cultural dependencies of a community are not readily explicit. The interpretation belongs to the perception of the researcher as a snapshot in time. Within this research, I will be experiencing the environment first-hand, most of the time as a participant-observer.

Descriptive methods depend on closely monitoring and recording occurrences, as observed. This can take on numerous shapes and incorporate different methods of data collection. The experiences of the researcher and the participants can be recorded in the form of field notes, surveys, photos, moving images, sound recordings to be later analysed. This type of design is influenced by two factors, complexity, and the extent of the study.

Simulation is a research model where the creation of artificial environments leads to the acquisition of knowledge. This inductive method can be two (i.e., paper prototyping) or three-dimensional (i.e., Scale model or computer generated), testing information on the relationship between the user and the artifice. These approaches converge and intersect with one another at different points of the serendipitous creative process I am employing.

3.1.4 Rational for practice-based research (PBR) methodology:

Making sense of our own creative processes within Practice-based Research (PBR) is challenging. Fortunately, Skains (2018), borrowed from different models, namely the cognitive process model” (Flower & Hayes, 1981), “Geneplore Model” (Finke, et al., 1982), “The Serendipity Model” (Makri & Blandford, 2012) and the “Systems Model of Creativity” by Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi (Csikszentmihalyi, 1996). Skains offers the “The Practitioner Model of Creative Cognition”. She created this as a guide for creative practitioners to explain their methodology and seek answers to their research questions (Skains, 2018). I adapt her model to my creative practice and display it, and I will explain each one of the models Skains is integrating, linking them to my work, to be able to understand and communicate the variables of this project. This is important because it allows the practitioner in me to critically analyse the generation of ideas, coping strategy and the by-product of the tensions between the external forces and creativity.

Flowers and Hayes’ (1981) “Cognitive Process Model” with three main cognitive blocs possess enough granularity to be used as a foundation to assess the “composition activity”, while all these processes are occurring at the same time this model is helpful to differentiate the different blocs in which the creative process of writing occurs. “The Long-term memory” holds the pre-acquired knowledge and writing skills of the researcher. Then there is a “Working Memory” bloc, this block stores the actual writing production process that counts with its inner processes such as “Planning”, “Translating” (converting mental, sounds, images, and feelings into writing), “Reviewing”, “Monitor” which is the steps of evaluation contrasting it with the elements present in the “Task Environment” (see fig.21).

Fig. 21 Cognitive process model (Flower and Hayes, 1981)

Skains (2018) explains that while this model explains the “mental fluidity” of the thought process, it is very self-contained, not accounting for external influences. To overcome these challenges, she proposes the integration of Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi’s “Systems Model of Creativity” as seen in Skains (2018), Csikszentmihalyi’s explains that the tensions between the field (Society), the Domain (Culture) and Persons (Genetic & Environment) produces novelty, or in other words. “a person, using the symbols of a given domain. has a new idea or sees a new pattern, and when the appropriate field selects this novelty for inclusion into the relevant domain” (Csikszentmihalyi, 1996, p. 26) (See Fig22).

Fig. 22 The Systems model of creativity (Csikszentmihalyi, 1999)

The “Geneplore model” is a hypothetical model for inventiveness. As a maker of creative constructs discussing how the practitioner concoct thoughts to produce artifacts can be challenging. To respond to that question, Finkle et al. propose a cyclical model where the generation of “Preinventive structures” (glimpses of ideas) and “Preinventive exploration and interpretations” are shaped by the imperatives of the products (Rhetorical problems, then we expand or focus on the concept, and the process iterates on itself (See Fig.23).

Fig. 23 The Geneplore Model (Finkle Ward & Smith,1982)

Within the plan to maximize the scope of the research there are artifact they are both created within a co-creation process within the Participatory Action Research approach (see 3.1.3). The process behind the creation of artifacts to satisfy the practice-base element of this research can be defined as one of serendipity, and perfectly connects with this project exploratory approach. “Empirically-Grounded process model of Serendipity” can be defined “a process of making a mental connection that has the potential to lead to a valuable outcome, projecting the value of the outcome and taking actions to exploit the connection, leading to a valuable outcome” (Makri & Blandford, 2012, pp. 691-692). This can be explained as a cognitive process afforded by the “knowledge” and “experience” of the practitioner to associate significant elements, make meaning out of them and create a beneficial result using the necessary skills (See Fig.24).

Fig. 24 Empirically Grounded process model of Serendipity (Makri and Blandford, 2012)

The presented model is appropriate for the discussion of my work. Built into it there are different models that acknowledge the existence and influence of the field, in this case those academics and cultural representatives who I discussed my work with, i.e., my supervisory team and the domain which refers to the cohesive thread of culture and me. Within “Me” I acknowledge the long-term memory which encompasses the most important factors in my case recorded through ethnographies. This long-term memory feeds into the “writing process” which also includes media production elements feeding back and forth with the task environment (see Fig.25).

Fig 25 Adapted from Practitioner Model of Cognition 2016 (Author, 2020)

3.2 Research Sample:

To access groups or sessions, I applied a snowball sampling strategy (Moser & Korstjens, 2017), where I would contact the DRC either by email or would personally visit a week before the sessions that interested me to register my interest to visit. Either one of the session organizers or my supervisor would put me in touch with the primary contact for the desired session. This sampling method was perfect as it allowed me to build trust, and be known by word of mouth, to meet additional staff and service users.

Simulation focus groups, semi-structured interviews: As seen in (Levinson, 2017) in modern times the gap between ethnographic paths of knowledge acquisition and PAR has become narrower, moving towards the creation of knowledge and artifact for and with the people of the visited culture, rather than distant participant observation as if looking over their shoulders (idem). Therefore, guided by the principles of PAR, I employed a cyclical protocol of focus groups, where participants would enter in contact with virtual reality simulations, and this, in turn, would facilitate discussions around immersive media, allowing them to express their opinions and share how they feel. In the beginning, I had groups of two people. However, it just felt natural to have four participants at the time, as this was closer to the numbers in groups or sessions at the DRC, and the semi-structured interviews were a natural fit since they lead to conversations needed to answer the research questions as seen similarly in Longhurst (2006).

3.2.1 Focus groups sampling:

To gather participants for the focus groups I used purposeful sampling (Patton, 2002; Patton, 1990). This meant that I would seek to find information rich participants. For this reason, I would use a snowball sampling method, either contacting the DRC or key staff members directly to pass the word on their groups, this is also known as network sampling (idem). The criteria for the selection of participants were a) all participants were part of the DRC service user, or with physical disabilities, sometimes Staff member. b) participants who manifested that their vision conditions allowed for an adequate use of the VR headset, this includes interocular

distance (Bogren, et al., 1986), as all headsets available to me at the time had fixed eye distance , (see Fig 26).

Fig. 26 Fixed IPD in Lenovo Daydream and Samsung Gear VR (Author, 2020)

The recruitment was done on the day with their help, I would also ask them to allow me to use a room available, and I would always be accompanied by a staff member who assisted me as a cultural ambassador and would help me many times to read information to the participants or translate the purpose of the activities. Focus groups would normally gauge around 10 -12 participants, in sub-groups of 3-4 at the time (see chapters 4, 5, 6 for further information).

3.3 Overview of information needed:

This exploratory ethnographic study is focused on a disabled community in Paisley - Scotland, with a population of around 120 service users local to the Renfrewshire council. To understand what the benefits of Virtual Reality are, how to build immersive experiences with the cooperation disabled people, and how to correctly administer VR within the services provided by the four research questions were explored to gather the needed information, it was

determined that the information needed fell into these categories. a) Structural, b) Cultural, c) Demographic. d) Theoretical.

- Structural: in other words, how the centre works, this includes staff hierarchy and duties, what types of services it provides and what are the modalities of service administration and space.
- Cultural: Identity of social players, Patterns of social behaviour, values, beliefs.
- Demographic: Information related to the population demographic such as age range, disability, gender, and VR literacy.
- Theoretical: Literature regarding the theories underpinning the themes revealed through exploratory ethnographies as the study progressed.

3.4 Research Design overview:

Below there is an outline of steps to undertake the project. Subsequently there is a timeline explaining the phases of enquiry development.

1. Due to the nature of the project, before starting I had Disclosure and Barring Service (DBS) check.
2. Following the proposal, I the researcher acquired the university research ethics committee permission.
3. I Proceeded to visit two sessions a week at the DRC to commence the writing of ethnographies.
4. I Proceeded to collect literature relevant to themes related to VR and disability studies.
5. I proceeded to study different off-the-shelf Virtual Reality experiences, bearing in mind their compatibility with the DRC.
6. I created and delivered a pilot study workshop with off-the-shelf experiences. In this study, semi structured interviews were conducted with 12 participants.
7. Interview responses, and field notes were analysed and integrated into ethnographies.

8. Using the data gathered from participants to the pilot study workshops, I created user experience research tools such as a) User journey, b) Personas and c) Scenarios.
9. Successful transfer event to Ph.D. candidate status.
10. Artifact prototypes were created, and user tested with customers at the DRC. Twice per prototype during user test workshops feedback from participants was gathered and taken into consideration for the subsequent iteration of the prototype
11. Final prototype was tested in a pilot study workshop. Semi structured interviews and self-reported wellbeing sheet administered were conducted with 12 participants.
12. Interview responses, and field notes were analysed and integrated into ethnographies.

3.4.1 Literature Review:

Given the multifaceted nature of this study, a continuous and selective literature review was undertaken to guide this project. The topics orbit around the following themes. A) Disability and wellbeing: These seek to study models of understanding disability, and what behaviours humans use to find meaning a elicit a sense of wellbeing. B) Trust as a form of connecting with the DRC, C) What is Virtual Reality and how it encompasses other forms of media to create new realities, a survey of literature relevant to the VR and themes health and wellbeing. The focus of the review was sought theory behind themes and sub-themes to finally integrate them.

3.4.2 Transfer Status to PhD Candidate:

After completing a first phase of ethnographies and literature review, the student advanced to PhD candidate status by defending a research project proposal that included a sample of the Ethnographic work up until that date an explanation of the problem statement, background of the enquiry in question, a literature review, and the proposed methods and methodology.

3.5 Data-Collection Methods:

Qualitative methods provide us with many descriptions of people, groups, events, and phenomena to help us gain a deeper understanding of them. On certain occasions, to draw a clearer picture, quantitative methods could also be integrated within qualitative methods

(Hammarberg, et al., 2016). The latter allows us to calculate the numerical correlation of variables, moving between 'before' and 'after,' and they are ideally suited to answer questions like 'How many?' and 'How often?' In user experience (UX), these are necessary to estimate the probability of a successful implementation of a digital experience. Nonetheless, contrasting what people say against what people do is a form of participant observation. Therefore, I mainly use qualitative research methods, but at times I have resorted to quantitative methods to triangulate the effect of the created cultural artifacts.

A discussion of the validity of combining different methods can be found in Jick (1979), where he argues that embedding methods within other methods can help address the limitations of these primary methods. Following the same line of thought, I will now introduce phase one. While primarily employing an ethnographic approach, I aim to (RQ.1) understand the relationship between the agency experienced by a person with a disability and the agency afforded by immersive technologies and (RQ.2) identify cultural benefits derived from the integration of immersive technologies in this community as they become evident. Throughout the course of the research, data collection methods included conducting literature research to monitor and comprehend topics related to my study. I accomplished this by creating and continually updating a literature review document as a secondary research method, which offered a foundation of academic literature to inform all research questions. In this section, I will outline the phases of data collection implemented during the fieldwork for a logical progression of events.

3.5.1 Phase One: Ethnographies during groups or sessions

During the first six months, to better understand the reality at the DRC community, I conducted direct participant observations of the life at the DRC, this helped me create an understanding of what means to be a physically disabled person, and have an idea of how could implement VR at the DRC, this way answering RQ1 and seeing the initial cultural benefits of integrating VR into this community answering RQ2, this is also true for the phase two of the study. Under this protocol, I visited groups or sessions, 'actively' participating, and collaborating by helping group leaders with tasks such organizing tables, distributing material, or bringing tea or coffee to service users.

Ethnographies during group sessions were chosen as the primary method for data collection. (For a more detailed explanation of this phase, please refer to Chapter 4) As outlined in Singleton and Straits (2005), it is essential to present oneself and state one's intentions when conducting non-covert research. In my case, I aimed to establish trust and enable the participants to become acquainted with me while generating enthusiasm for my research topic. To achieve this, I attended numerous sessions. Before the commencement of each session, the group leader would briefly introduce me by name. Subsequently, I would straightforwardly explain that I was a student conducting research at the center with a focus on understanding VR technology and its potential applications in disabled communities. I expressed my desire for them to participate in my research and extended my gratitude for allowing me to spend time with them.

During the sessions, I would take discrete notes and pictures; then, I would write ethnographic accounts of these encounters within the next day or two. This interpretative form of data collection helps the researcher to let disabled individuals speak for themselves, yielding what Clifford Geertz (1973) called "thick description", which encompasses the idea to create a comprehensive description where the ethnographer outlines a clear shape of cultural and social relationships and contextualizes it (Holloway, 1997). To put it plainly, this approach allows the researcher to experience and take detailed notes of the daily lives and routines of the people being observed, and expose fundamental cultural patterns and ponder on the research site's values, ethics, and forms of livelihood. When taking notes of my observations and interpretations, to be as descriptive as possible, I adapted a simple guideline of questions as seen in Vanderbilt (2012). I asked myself, a) what is the layout of the space or room?, with this question I considered visible physical conditions such as the layout of the space, or specific objects that might have an impact in the development of the events, b) who were the people involved?, what were the statuses or roles of these social players at the centre?, c) how people interacted with one another?, What is their body language?, and specific behaviours, for example, What is the relationship of social actors with mediating technologies? This helped me draw with words a clear picture of what occurred in the everyday setting. This form of participant observation was

essential for the development of the study, as it allowed me to stay for extended amounts of time in their environment, allowing me to connect with them through their rituals in a non-intrusive manner. This way I learned about the codes embedded into the meanings of their everyday life (Silverman, 2016). To write the ethnographies, I also considered items such as pictures hanging at the walls and the DRC's daily schedule. I must also confess that I followed the digital incarnations of the DRC, particularly on Facebook and Twitter. These channels allowed me to engage in polite and playful interactions, strengthening my bond with the centre and keeping me informed about community events. Through their webpage and social media presence, this trend of researchers strengthening connections using social media has been well-documented. (Lupton, 2014).

3.5.2 Phase Two: Pilot Study

Focus groups, in the form of workshops, were used to explore simulations in depth from the participants' perspective. This pilot study aimed to test whether this kind of experiences and format would be effective answering RQ3 and RQ3a. During these sessions (see section 4.3), I employed Participatory Action Research (PAR) to empower service users to consider the types of experiences they wished to create. The inquiry took the form of semi-structured interviews. I considered this conversational format more conducive to participation, as it is a more intuitive way for participants to communicate their realities. (Brinkmann, 2020). Moreover, this is the same format used in the DRC service groups, for this purpose I used open-ended questions, surveying the effects of the experiences on their mood and taking field notes during these. Throughout the experience, I take field notes about interesting occurrences from my participants. These include registrations of sporadic short conversations with different staff members or service users to find out pieces of information regarding the field (DRC), the disabilities of participants in general, or thoughts related to groups or sessions. The main purpose of this sessions was to expose participants to different forms of VR and democratize the decision-making process to produce the artifacts that would answer the question about how immersive media could be integrated into the DRC (RQ.3) and what processes are behind creating immersive experiences for centres such as the DRC (RQ.3a)

3.5.3 Phase Three: Focus groups, user test and artifacts building

I created this focus groups to study if the artifacts were implementable at the DRC, to build knowledge whilst creating the cultural artefacts, this way answering RQ3, and RQ3a. Each of the immersive VR experiences set out to follow a creation process modelled after the “Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC)” this is a software creation methodology that can be modelled around users with human computer interaction (HCI) methods (Nathanael, et al., 2022). this can create good user experience (UX) and have an impact in the wellbeing of users (Szabó, 2023). SDLC is the gold standard in software development, combined with an agile project management approach by implementing the iterative acquisition of user requirements, adapting the project promptly to the stakeholder's needs and having a deep knowledge of the stakeholders and their business (Kashyap, 2018).

The SDLC (see fig.27), shares the quality of “Participant Action Research” (PAR) where researcher and participants work alongside to understand a problem and draw from each other strengths to find a solution in a democratic manner, but focuses on the creation and implementation of artifacts, this has four phases of software creation are “Requirements analysis”, “Design”, “Implementation”, and “Evolve” (testing). The optic of this method is within the user-centred design field. While the model illustrates an excellent overall pattern of the progression methods and how they inform one another, it does not account for the myriad connections and minor tasks that do not fit into a simplified model. Still, it is a valuable tool to guide the process and make sure one considers the next step when finishing the current.

Fig. 27 User-Centred SLDC (Author, 2019)

3.5.3.1 Requirements:

This sub-phase is at the very beginning of the ladder of immersive experiences creation. In this step, I estimated the project's feasibility, the user needs, and how I envision the experience to develop. In this phase, the aiming to identify preconditions, i.e., assets, computer software needed, the functional requirements about the users and their relationship with the technology, operational requirements about the centre, and design limitations for the scope. This was done via focus groups, the later integrate elements of participant observation, and interviewing around a theme, to gain deeper understanding about a topic (Krueger, 2015).

3.5.3.2 Design:

This phase is the second; after gathering all the information, I created a user journey and storyboard to be used alongside the user personas that I created. To create these, I used traits of real stakeholders to reflect on the needs and wishes of the users and social actors' roles. I also worked on

3.5.3.3 Implementation:

During this third phase, we developed the existing software through two primary methods. We either recorded videos using a GoPro 6 camera rig and produced videos using ADOBE Creative Suite (2018), or we utilized UNITY 2018, a cross-platform game creation engine, along with other digital tools. This stage involved resolving coding issues, creating stages, managing assets,

troubleshooting, and building. These tasks were closely related to the second phase, and we alternated between design and implementation based on changing needs, results, and inspirations before moving forward.

3.5.3.4 Evolve:

Also referred to as the 'testing phase,' this stage, while not the final step in an iterative agile project, involves a back-and-forth process between implementation and verification just before delivery. During this stage, I tested the effectiveness of the software, focus group semi-structured interviews, and materials with academic colleagues. I then visited the centre to gather feedback from staff members and service users. I listened to their input and returned to refine and improve the experience in an iterative process.

3.5.4 A resume of the creation of the artifacts

The creation of the two artifacts follows processes adapted to their needs, the first artifact "Produce: Tune into Nature" required the monoscopic 360 recording of Scottish landscapes. I did this by visiting and recording landscapes suggested by participants during focus groups and choosing with them which environments they preferred. In addition to this I hired an actress with a soothing voice and a neutral Scottish accent to read over a script created by me, taking from other different guided breathing meditation procedures, the audio-visual material was produced combining the ADOBE creative suite (2018) and UNITY (2018) to create the OCULUS application and 360 videos used within the study. The Second artifact "Discovery" was created entirely using Unity and elements from the unity asset store and programmed in C#. While the participants at the DRC did not directly intervene in the production and creation process, I believe because of the iterative consultation cycle I chose to produce these artifacts, this was a process of co-creation.

3.5.5 Materials:

Head Mounted Displays (HMD): Two different kinds of HMDs were used. The first type was powered by a Samsung Galaxy (S7) mobile phone with the Samsung – Oculus “Gear VR” operating system, featuring 3DOF (Three degrees of freedom) allowing for the users to look up down and rotate their head, and a removable Samsung Gear VR headset (model: SM-R325NZVCXAR). This HMD was complicated for me to deploy at the centre, and uncomfortable for many users as it was fiddly to use since the headbands often would not keep the headset stable. Another issue for participants with glasses was that the glasses were not always fitting comfortably within the headset. Many times, by trying help them fix their sight within the headset, this would trigger the mobile phone to stop displaying images, and it didn't have different settings for Interpupillary Distance (IPD). I had only one pair, which was hard to use with bigger groups. The second type of HMDs was a standalone Lenovo Mirage (model: ZA3C) headset powered by Google's Daydream operating system and experimental 6DOF (Not full), which allows for freer movement within the virtual environment, allowing the user to pivot their head in any direction as well as moving in all directions. This HMD was easier for me to place on the heads of the users as it rested ergonomically in people’s heads and the strap band was easily adjustable by a back wheel. However, this one also did not have a system to adjust in interpupillary distance of the lenses. I would also like to say that I would have the simulation loaded by the time of the study. For more information on 3DOF and 6DOF see Rossi (2023); other instruments created for the workshops are the following.

Participant information sheet: This document contains information about the study, an explanation about the way the participants have been invited, what is their entitlement as participants, overall event description, the description of the content, and contact information about the researcher and supervisory team, they would be given enough time and assistance to read if needed.

Research consent form: This form asks for the participant's consent, making sure that they have read and understood the participant information sheet, that their participation is voluntary, that

they know they can withdraw at any point, and that their data will be treated confidentially. They also agree to have their voice and likeness recorded and confirm that they freely agree to participate in the study.

Conversational interview guide sheet (simple semi-structured interview): This has three different sections (1) Questions about the participants that do not identify them (age, gender) and questions about their disability, their expertise in the use of VR and how they were feeling. (2) A headset section – in principle, I merely ask them to wear the headset to play the experience, and I take notes. (3) A debrief section with simple questions about whether they enjoyed the experience, about immersion, and about engagement. This also features qualitative and quantitative questions to collect data on the user test aspect of the experience, this way gathering their feedback and thoughts in a Before and After manner.

Mood-chart forms: this form was distributed to the participants to fill themselves or with the aid of the staff member present during this session. The chart was created as I observed in many focus groups the more able participants would dominate the conversation and those who couldn't shy away from expressing their ideas, feelings, and thoughts. Therefore, to help them gain certain granularity in self-report I decided to use visual representations to aid them to self-express (see fig.28)

Fig 28 Pain/comfort scale, (Mixed sources interpreted Author, 2019)

This approach aimed to understand the participants' feelings and their overall mood before and after the study. The chart was divided into two parts. The first part integrated two types of pain or discomfort scales, ranging from 0-10, and using facial expressions from 'Great' (equal to '0') to 'Horrid' at the very end of the scale. These scales were adapted from the 'FPS-R' and the 'Wong-

Baker' scale. Additionally, a numerical scale was integrated. These scales are typically used to overcome speech barriers and enhance the granularity of self-reporting in patients. The combination of emoji-like and numerical scale complemented images, words, and numbers to facilitate understanding and validate the effectiveness of this method. (Pathak, et al., 2018; Klimek, et al., 2017).

Taking on the emotional granularity idea from Lisa Feldman, the second part of the form features a “valence/arousal circumplex” chart created originally by James Russell. This was very helpful as visually maps effects with word, and it is easy to understand if it is explained as if it was a clock. It features two axis, one vertical axis explaining the arousal (High-Low), and one horizontal explaining the valence unpleasant to pleasant, for further reading on this please refer to (Russell, 1980). This implementation reduced the chance for faux participation (Levinson, 2017).

3.5.6 Participatory user test protocol:

I would always clean the headsets, charge their batteries, and upload the simulations 24 hours before the focus groups. During the sessions, I would record the occurrences with videos or audio unless any participant would object.

a) Participant's briefing (onboarding):

Before the interview, time was allocated to meet and greet the participants so they could be put at ease and the workshop could be explained to them. At this point, I clarified to the participants that they might be recorded and observed if they agreed to participate by signing the participant consent sheet. (5 min approx.) In this first phase, the scope was to introduce the participants to the space where they were greeted and have them brought to the room to start the workshop. The researcher will read to them the participant information sheet, explaining who is involved and how the experiment will be conducted and reported. (15 min approx.)

b) Semi-structured conversation:

The initial conversation and questioning moved from general questions to more specific questions, depending on the conversation development. (15 min approx.) If scheduled, I would also provide a mood chart so they could evaluate their mood.

c) Experience (Simulation):

The second phase is the facilitation of the VR experiences. With the participant's permission and once it has been ascertained that there are no obstacles to the workshop proceeding, I as the researcher arranged the setup and fit of the VR headset over the attendees, taking care to attend to and record any specific challenges presented by the participant's disability. During the participant's experience, the researcher observed in silence, ready to assist if needed be, and took notes on the participant's behaviour and body language. (15 min approx.)

d) Debriefing (Offboarding):

Following a similar format as phase one (semi-structured conversation), the primary intention was to find out how the participant felt after experiencing VR media in the context of their wellbeing. (10-15 min approx.) During this contact time with the participants, I would take photographs, record videos to help me remember moments, and sometimes audio, unless participants had yet to decide not to take a picture or video. After the initial iteration of focus groups, I realized that some participants were not allowed to speak or have the low emotional granularity to communicate how they felt. This is also very common in body-able studies (Barret, 2017). Therefore, I added visual representations to help my participants communicate how they were feeling by adding a “Valence arousal circumplex chart” and a mood chart as a simple manner to triangulate their perceived mood improvement (see Fig. 29)

Fig. 29 Valence & Arousal chart (Russell, 1980) interpreted by (Author, 2019)

3.6 Data Analysis and Synthesis:

Qualitative studies can produce a plurality of data that could be analysed and interpreted as analysis depending on its themes or contents (Vaismoradi & Turunen, 2013). The data extrapolated from the initial visits at the centre were thick descriptions, ethnographies, and photographs. Alternatively, the data produced from the focus groups are answers to the mood chart and ethnography style reports constructed from Audio-visual recordings.

The purpose of the audio-visual recordings was to create ethnographies to describe what I had seen during the fieldwork. Many of my participants disabilities included the use of spoken language; therefore, I analysed the videos to see their body language, and using memory, compared it with the fieldnotes and the interview extracts and created an account of what occurred during the day, I followed a protocol where I would complete the ethnographies within two days after every visit. To create ethnographic accounts after the sessions helped me manage the data better, and I would classify it in two categories 1) Ethnographies 2) Visual Material, and I would use a thematical analysis as this would allow me to make sense of the material in a systematic manner.

One example of when I integrated the ethnographic diary and visual material was to create personas. An incarnation of ethnographies into tangible elements is the Personas. They drive the

Human-Centred design as they are highly descriptive. This “hypothetical archetypes” are based on real individuals designed to raise awareness of the user motivations, wishes and objectives (many times also called frustrations) throughout a project (Korsgaard, et al., 2020). This prospective user even if it is fictional must represent the receiving end of a digital experience (idem). To create them I wrote profiles of my participants as real stories and coded them to protect their identities.

For a Persona to act as the user, it needs to be compelling and believable, they are not a replacement for the actual users or their alter egos. Adling & Pruitt (2006) argue that when characters are not well constructed, or not based on real data they are not believable (Adlin & Pruitt, 2006). Therefore, the focus on “who is the user” can be lost, just like in the early persona-like efforts. Chapman & Millham (Chapman & Millham, 2006) see personas as an attractive mean of communicating data but advise to not to rely heavily on this method as these archetypes cannot be adequately verified or falsified. However, this is not a problem in my case, with that in mind and the fact that my participants will have to remain anonymous. In this section, I will discuss the construction of personas using a and how these archetypes helped me understand the needs of my users and help me keep the focus on them, by explaining how using DRC user profiles, and other data I have been able to build representative characters of the population I am working with, this in itself is a form of data protection, as I am coding the identities of my participants and only making apparent marker that could identify them.

The term persona has been around since the early nineties, but what this method encompasses is still unclear, meaning that the information description of the profiles varies from one study to another, adapting the patterns to the areas of the life required to understand what kind of person is experiencing the product, or artifact. For this reason, I have adapted the personas data to the aspects of their lives that might be relevant to the study, always seeking empathetic to have an empathetic viewpoint (Bennett & Rosner, 2019).

I have already familiarized myself with the data as I have written the ethnographies, I analysed the three Codes, that I will colour code and explain a continuation, this I am using to construct the personas in this study; First code was the “Personality and demographic background” because this make them relatable, Second (2) the code of “Disability and assistive technologies they use” in their everyday life, because this give a description of their needs and finally the third one (3) was their “Wishes & Frustrations”. I used this to identify what matters to them respect to the study (for the coded material related to participants see appendix B).

“(1) Megan is a Renfrewshire resident and a married mum of two; she is 64 years old, she is calm and introverted, none the less she is open to conversation. She used to work as a public servant managing a department in the Paisley area, when she had a Stroke, (2) this affected her Speech, motor movement and stiffness especially in the left side of her body, and quite often she feels muscular pain. She is a walking stick user; she uses the DRC bus to commute 3-4 times a week to the centre. In her spare time, she visits the beach or the lakes with her family.

Her favourite sessions are the singing group and the self-running; however, she participates in diverse ones depending on what she would like to do on the day. (3) Her frustrations are her mobility issues, anxiety, and sometimes her low mood. She is interested on finding ways to fight her anxiety and low mood.

It is worth mentioning that even if she struggles on constructing long sentences or articulating dialog when speaking, she enjoys visiting the singing group, achieving a great performance in this activity.

She owns a smartphone and uses emails and social media, she also watches television and listens to the radio, in my observation her response to media it’s quite normal for what we could expect in somebody her age.”

I would then find commonalities among the users and create believable personas. In this way I found a way of conveying who they are by adapting the personas to their reality. In total I have created 6 personas (See appendix B), starting by representing the ratio of gender, age, disability and in the end adding lifestyle. Here there is an example in Fig.25

„Let me tell you about that time...“

Emilia used to work for the local council authority, now however, she is retired. She lives with her son, his wife and grandchild. Her cat is called Arthur, she is described by her friends as bubbly and warm.

She had a stroke 5 years ago, which resulted in a light motor and control condition (Ataxia), she also experiences limb debilitation and pain (Paresthesia). While she mobilizes herself around the house with minimal effort. However, she requires assistance to go shopping, or visit friends.

She has attended the DRC for less than 4 years, she relies on the council bus to visit the DRC, and her service days are 4 times a week during the mornings, at lunchtime she goes back home. Her favourite session is the Taichi class; other than that, she goes to sessions where she can socialize and have a pleasant time.

Sometimes she feels anxious, she wishes to go to interesting places.

- Emilia Willson
- 60 years old
- Retired
- Renfrewshire
- Friendly and Chatty

Fig. 30 Persona Archetype (Author, 2018)

3.6.1 Ethics of engaging on this research:

In the last section, I have provided a statement of steps to comply with policies and procedures regarding research ethics review done Independently. In this section I seek to stablish what ethical consideration were observed during the conduction of this project, linking to relevant literature, and building upon case studies realized by other researchers.

The role of research in modern society goes beyond academic institutions, through this process researchers provides lawmakers, practitioners and legislator with legitimate evidence that can be used as the base of decision making to solve or alleviate practical issues in society (Baker, et

al., 2004). In this sense, research seeks to analyse and reveal the social world, but also to produce meaningful change (idem). However, this should be done making sure that during this process the researcher engages with research with participants, rather than conducting research on subjects, and makes sure the participants are properly informed before giving their consent and to balance the benefits versus the hardship. However, it has not always been that way, specially referring to research involving people with disabilities, as it historically has been done under optic of the “medical progress” creating an unequal relationship between the researcher and participants (Bryen, 2016).

Perspectives on research ethics are numerous. However, related to community-based Participatory research (CBPR) done with exploratory and participatory approaches, I had identified mainly three strategies as seen in Brydon-Miller & Wood (2022). Firstly, we have, “Case Studies based” approaches, where different scenarios are used to illuminate challenges and concerns within the context of community-based research during the research process (Banks & Brydon-Miller, 2019). Then we have “Everyday Ethics” which observes the effort of the researcher to identify ethically salient aspects of everyday interaction in moment-to-moment decisions within the field and work out a good course of action as they go along (Banks, 2019). And finally, we have “Feminist, Communitarian, and Covenantal Ethics”, in short, the focus is on human relationships and ethical demands, and less on formal review policies or procedures (Hilsen, 2006).

Within the broader ethical research framework of the United Nations' Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2006), especially in its article 3, the respect for the inherent dignity, individual autonomy, non-discrimination, inclusion, and independence of said group is established (United Nations, 2006). Furthermore, Bryen (2016) and Resnik & Hackett (2022), drawing from other sources (Emanuel, et al., 2000; Resnik, 2018), provide ethical research guidelines to work with humans and adapted to work with people with disabilities. The following set of statements summarises these guidelines and clarifies my ethical approach:

- A. Ensure beneficence and non-harm in the design and implementation of the study, meaning that risks have been minimized and are acceptable in comparison with the benefits the participants might receive from the study. Reflecting upon this point, this research complies with the University of the West of Scotland's Ethics Committee Guidance (2018), project ID 4657, and GDPR guidelines (Information Commissioner's Office, 2019). The study is regarded to pose minimal risk to participants. The likelihood and magnitude of discomfort or irritation anticipated in the research is not higher than events in ordinary life and gives them the chance to experience new media forms such as VR. The necessary Disclosure and Barring Service (DBS) checks were completed prior to starting the research.
- B. Collaboration with people with disabilities in conducting research for their benefit: while design rigour should produce transferable knowledge that can be translated into socially valuable results or applications, it should also see people with disabilities as partners in the production of knowledge. Reflecting upon point B, research processes and results might be transferred to another institution (see section 3.8.2). Under the principles of participatory action research (PAR), research is a partnership. However, variability of participation and control is expected (Gustafson & Brunger, 2014). As seen in Lanette (2022), reciprocity is a mode of social exchange: it is a cornerstone of respectful research relationships, where there is an expectation of mutual exchange of help, knowledge or resources. When done ethically in participatory research, reciprocity strengthens the relationship by promoting beneficence, informed consent and justice, offering reassurance that the benefits are distributed across the community (idem). Furthermore, the scope of reciprocity is not to balance the power relationship or distribute tasks, but to create spaces where participants can exercise agency and both parts can be fairly validated for their contribution (Lanette, 2022). Within this research our exchange meant knowledge exchange from both sides. As seen in Northway et al. (2014) knowledge exchange in participatory research takes three forms i) "representational", which is useful to predict and control consequences, ii) "relational",

which has to do with the reciprocity of the relationship based on respect, trust and authenticity and lastly iii) reflective knowledge which is the knowledge based on critical theory and related to the research topic and the change we seek on the social world (Park, 2001).

- C. Consent should be informed, voluntary, and easily understandable. Information should be transmitted in a manner that can be understood easily and succinctly for participants to make free choices i.e., use simple English, use of images, provide enough time. Explaining that they do not need to take part in the study, and if they decide to do so, they can withdraw from the study at any time without providing an explanation, the information material should also contain the contact details in case they wish to have further information or withdraw. Reflecting upon point C, Ethics are not part of everyday language, however it can be translated into “looking after people”, making sure they felt comfortable, and they knew what to expect, and have support in case they require it (Northway, et al., 2014). For example, during the visits the present staff member would introduce me and allow me to introduce my research topic. I would do this in plain language and in an unhurried but concise manner, making sure that everybody knew the reason I was there. Like a mantra, I would repeat something along the lines of “I am a student, and I am here to understand how VR could be beneficial for a disabled community like the DRC, thank you for having me”, then I would do my best to integrate into the activity facilitating and getting to know my peers. During the workshops I communicated long in advance the workshops so they could have a staff member available to provide me with support during entire duration of these. The benefit was twofold: the staff member was my cultural ambassador, and I would learn from them on how to better communicate my ideas and implement the workshops in this setting. On the other side s/he had the expertise in the dynamics of the centre and provide support for participants. I also looked after people by i) carefully selecting VR experiences that would be engaging and would not pose any distress, ii) redacting documents that in easy English and did not have jargon. iii) Some documents contained

visual aids, iv) leaving them copies of the documents ,as similarly seen in Bryen (2016). Finally, as a difference between individual consent and collective consent (Bussu & Lalani, 2021), during my visits the participants to the activities consented me being there and they are sharing their live stories with me when they did not object my presence, but during the workshops signed consent was taken every time.

- D. Privacy and confidentiality should be respected. This means that the data gathered could not be traced back to participants, in a way that their dignity, confidentiality and privacy is undermined. Maintaining anonymity is hard in a place where everybody knows each other (Bussu & Lalani, 2021). Nonetheless, anonymity and confidentiality are two critical issues. I addressed these by using only participants' initials when using the focus groups documentation and presenting the results to the DRC members as a community rather than individually and coding them into personas. Furthermore, I kept the recorded videos stored in my PC and deleted them maximum after three weeks of taking them, in accordance with the GDPR. See Appendix "E", for all the relevant documentation.

- E. Participant recruitment should be done in an equitable manner to ensure diversity, furthermore reasonable arrangements on regards of the needs of the participants should be done to ensure accessibility during the implementation process. During this study, I consulted the "Involving Disabled People in Social Research" (2011) guidance by the Office for Disability Issues, aiming to abide by their guidance for this study in terms of creating a research design that would be as inclusive as possible given the constraints, this include recruitment, and attaining informed consent, as regards the Mental Capacity Act, accessibility and data gathering (Office for Disability Issues, Department for Work and Pensions, 2019). In considering my praxis, one important form of inclusion is the creation of personas using UX methodologies and taking in consideration the participants' characteristics, representing them in an authentic manner (Oswal, 2019). Diversity was ensured by the fact that staff members would

identify participants who could benefit and had different life experiences (Appel, et al., 2020)

3.7 Issues of trustworthiness:

Trustworthiness in qualitative and quantitative research works under two different paradigms that reflect their worldviews. This therefore makes it sensible to apply different criteria to examine their quality (Goertz & Mahoney, 2012). Quantitative methods entail an intrinsic correlation between numerical data, theory, and a deductive research approach. Their construction of social reality is objectivist, and data gathering comprises experiments and surveys that are then analysed using statistical tests (Black, 1999; Bryman & Bell, 2015). To convince readers to determine the quality of quantitative research, it is examined under four lenses: a) internal validity, b) external validity, c) reliability, and d) objectivity. For a comprehensive explanation, see Lincoln & Guba (1985). Qualitative research accepts multiple subjectivities, seeking a deep understanding of situations; therefore for some validity cannot be found in qualitative research (Smith, 1984), Others propose that the act of presenting qualitative research strategies is a demonstration of accuracy on itself (Creswell, 2014) . Moreover, Lincoln & Guba (1985) propose that methods need to be validated under analogous lenses to quantitative methods: a) Credibility (analogous to External Reality), b) Transferability (analogous to external validity), c) dependability (analogous to reliability), and c) confirmability (analogous objectivity) (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). In the following part of the section, I shall address each one of these points in correlation to my research.

3.7.1 Rationale for credibility:

Credibility is a crucial component of research design. Under this criterion, findings must be valid not only from the perspective of methodology and interpretation but also be clearly credible to participants, readers, and the researchers themselves. This can be achieved through prolonged engagement, persistent observation, and triangulation of data collection methods, among other strategies (Terrell, 2016).

In the introduction section, I have explained positionality. Now, I will elaborate on other credibility strategies that support the validity of this research. First, during the ethnographic fieldwork, I, as the researcher, maintained 'prolonged engagement and persistent observation' with the participants and the contextual space. I visited the centre at the beginning of the project, sometimes twice a week, and participated in various sessions and activities, writing ethnographies after every visit, engaging also with the data and its analysis for extended period. Second, I integrated different forms of data collection methods and data analysis to achieve triangulation, for more about Methodological triangulation see sections 3.5 and about Data triangulation see section 3.6. Additionally, I can claim the implementation of 'member checking' strategy as one of my supervisors worked in the field, and I made my work available to them for examination. I also conducted regular update sessions with my supervisory team and engaged with literature as soon as themes regarding to my research was made apparent: this means that I engaged in theoretical triangulation to strengthen the credibility of this research.

3.7.2 Rational for Transferability:

To validate the transferability of this project's processes to other institutions is relevant to these endeavours specially for research questions RQ3 & RQ3a given that other similar institutions might benefit from the lessons learned (Bloomberg & Volpe, 2008). Transferability entails that these findings can be extrapolated to other similar situations or contexts (Patton, 1990). In this thesis this has been achieved by purposeful sampling during workshops and "thick description" of participants and context, using field notes, and pictures to create more vivid explanations of the situations encountered (Stahl & King, 2020; Patton, 1990; Geertz, 1973). Thus qualitative account claims can achieve relevance when being contextualized against other similar but not identical backgrounds (Patton, 1990). This research can also claim transferability because, during a competition to expand their portfolio of immersive experiences, 'Produce – Tuning into nature' was selected to be included in the library of experiences offered to the service users at LOROS Hospice. This reaffirms the importance of mindfulness and immersive experiences as a part of the services that social service centres may offer.

3.7.3 Rationale for dependability:

Also called reliability, at its core, this means that another investigator could follow the decision-making process and replicate the study within a different context. Because this study is practice-based (PBR) and involves a creativity element (see section 3.1.4), it would be challenging for another researcher to replicate the results in a similar institution. However, this project can claim dependability based on the logic of its design, which can be easily followed by another creative researcher (see 3.4 & 3.5). During this process, I followed a series of steps: (a) I encountered the DRC while writing ethnographies about the centre and its people, (b) I evaluated other immersive experiences available online to gain an idea of what was accessible, (c) I created workshops for them to try new experiences and provide feedback on the experience I was creating for them, and (d) in these workshops, I interviewed them in a conversational manner and provided them with a mood form to self-report their mood improvement in a before-and-after manner. This provides two claims for dependability in the flow of arguments and logic as seen in Lincoln & Guba (1985). It can also claim the validity strategy of method triangulation by using ethnographies, focus groups and surveys. and theory triangulation, as the results align with those described in the literature review in terms of mood improvement after experiencing the simulation.

3.7.4 Rational confirmability:

Lincoln & Guba (1985) propose that a researcher needs to be reflective, achieving this by making the reader aware of perceptual biases he might have. In my research this reflexible auditing takes the form of positionality (see section 1.2 & 1.3) where I explained that while I grew up in a society that deemed the abled body and heteronormativity as “normal”. Through my life experiences I understood that the only normality in life is change and variance in the human experience and as such we should find ways of respectfully portray the lives of others. This consistency can be found in the creation of personas (see 3.6) and the ethnographic accounts (see chapter 4-6). This also provide with enough information to claim reflexivity in the form of journaling.

3.8 Methodological limitations of the Study:

As a qualitative research study, limitations are expected (Anderson, 2010). Firstly, research quality is rooted in the researcher's individual experience, and it is more likely to be influenced by individual biases and perspectives. Maintaining rigour can be challenging and demonstrating it can be elusive. The quantity of data can be enormous, and in this case, the presence of the researcher in the field, while offering benefits, can also influence the responses of workshop participants and the behaviour of session attendees a phenomenon referred as participant's reactivity (Maxwell, 1996). The presence of the researcher during focus groups can also impact issues related to anonymity and confidentiality. Finally, visualizing, and characterizing data can be more time-consuming and complex. This research is also exploratory (Swedberg, 2020): this has its limitations, for example because of its exploratory nature the scope may not always be clear, and this can bring challenges, such as requiring a high number of efforts to determine a research design and implementation. Finally, exploratory research relies in questioning methods that are open ended, leaving space for doubt. Underlying issues may remain unresolved. Finally, the practice based (PBR) approach borrows methods normally used in other fields (Candy, 2006). One of its deifying elements is serendipitous creativity, that make the decision taken in the co-creative process nebulous to explicate and elusive to track (Skains, 2018).

3.9 Chapter Summary:

This chapter provides a summary of the study's research methodology, detailing its key points. The research is qualitative, ethnographic, and exploratory in nature, and it also incorporates elements of participatory action research (PAR) and practice-based methodologies. This multifaceted methodology was employed to address the research questions, which aim to gain a deeper understanding of the potential benefits and challenges of introducing immersive media within a disabilities resource and services centre. The focus is on understanding how this media can enhance the living experience of individuals within this context, and how people with disabilities can actively participate in decision-making processes, particularly in software development, by involving them in the co-creation process.

During the ethnographic research, the researcher actively participated in most of the sessions provided by the centre and had access to the lives of potential participants in the focus groups. Therefore, approximately 11 - 12 participants were intentionally selected for each one of the four focus groups reaching more than 10% of the population. While the primary method used was ethnography, other data collection methods were also employed, including focus groups and mood surveys for participants to self-report their moods. The data underwent manual thematic analysis, and the surveys were also analysed manually before being compared to the existing literature.

This study can assert its validity through various strategies, including vividly descriptive situations, the logical flow of the design model, and the triangulation of methodologies. Themes identified in the literature were compared against the findings from the fieldwork.

The primary objective of this study is to contribute to the evolving understanding of immersive technologies and their positive implementation in social disability service settings. In the following three chapters, I will describe my fieldwork experiences, drawing connections between previous research and my own ethnographic findings.

Chapter 4: Meeting the DRC

In recent years immersive media has been used with distinct groups, including people with disabilities and the elderly, with the purpose of creating wellbeing. We can employ interactive experiences to visit other realities, use serious games for physical rehabilitation, or visualizations to treat phobia, anxiety disorder, or aid pain management. While studies about the use of immersive media with user groups that face physical and cognitive challenges are at an early stage, this type of media has increasingly been recognized by the promising results of pilot studies to represent a qualitative advance on previous digital forms, and that has given rise to the question of virtual reality's applicability in care settings. In this chapter, I first discuss the community at the DRC, then explore the relationships I established with service users, key community leaders, and staff members, describing how some of these social actors became gatekeepers, and my relationship with them.

4.1 The Community

As described in the literature review, the social model of disability is relatively recent, paved the way for many independent living communities, and the field of disability studies is still growing and fluxing in social research. The Paisley Disability Resource Centre (DRC) registered with the Care Commission in April of the year 2002 to provide a day-care service to a maximum of 60 users per day. The DRC has a mission statement that aims to provide adults with physical disabilities or sensory impairment activities and services through various leisure, social, educational, and employment delivery groups to promote independent living; there are currently more than 98 service users who are registered to use the centre.

The centre's primary way of promoting independent living is through classes or sessions, providing a framework of social interaction under the service user model of disability where the

service user and their family play a leading role in the choice of the activities s/he will choose. Amid the events provided by the centre, we can find ones such as Arts, Tai chi, Yoga, Knitting, Computing, and swimming among many others. These services are mainly provided through activities where the community's participation in the community and peer support are considered the major defining elements of this community's health and wellbeing. If “health and wellbeing” were to be simplified more holistically, based on the de facto working definition in the DRC, their activities imply that health and wellbeing is “The experienced quality of life resulting from combined physical, social, intellectual and emotional components which are subjective to the community or the individual within it” which closely resembles that employed in Welsh care-work (Welsh Government Resources, 2019).

This institution is a street-level building and has a range of specialist accessible facilities, including a kitchen, library, and a club room. As many other similar institutions, It is surrounded by a garden that can be used for horticultural therapy or a contemplating space. The centre counts with many specialized care professionals and has among its ranks volunteers that attend the centre as part of their learning or work experience. The centre is located just on the outskirts of Paisley town centre (see Fig. 31).

Figure 31 DRC community building Front View (DRC, used with permission, 2017)

A regular day for the service users could be broken into the following routine, and they would arrive at the centre from 9:30- 10:00 Hrs. They would come either by the bus provided by the DRC or transported by a family member, and then they would participate in the morning activities, have lunch from noon to 1 pm, and then they would go home or participate in the afternoon activities. After four pm, the centre closes until the next day. In the image below, we can see the DRC weekly schedule, which reveals information about the culture and organization at the centre. During the morning or afternoon sessions, I was allowed as a guest to interact with the service users and staff members (See Fig.32).

Monday 10 ⁰⁰ - 12 ⁰⁰	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday
CURRENT AFFAIRS COMPUTING (College) COOKING CRAFT SWIM AT LINWOOD PHOTOGRAPHY <i>LUNCH</i> <i>12 - 13⁰⁰</i>	GYM AT LAGOON PERSONAL PRESENTATION INTRODUCTION TO NEW I.T SOFTWARE. AUDIBLE BOOKS HISTORY OF MUSIC	PHOTOGRAPHY WOODWORK DEBATING COOKING. ART	GYM AT LAGOON MOVIE MAKERS GARDENING SINGING SELF RUNNING CRAFT GAELIC AT BEECHWOOD	CREATIVE WRITING ALTERNATIVE HEALTH MAGAZINE GROUP GYM AT LAGOON UPCYCLING PROJECT
<i>3⁰⁰ - 15⁰⁰</i> TAI CHI MEMORY SKILLS COMPUTING PHOTOGRAPHY	EXERCISE I PADS AND TABLETS MUSIC AND MOVEMENT COOKING	PHOTOGRAPHY WOODWORK YOGA Book Group DANCE AT KIBBLE ART	GARDENING TAI CHI WEB SITE DESIGN SELF RUNNING CRAFT MY LIFE IN SONG	CREATIVE WRITING QUIZ RELAXATION

Fig. 32: Weekly schedule at the DRC (Author, 2017).

In academia, fieldwork has been an important stepping-stone for many graduate students involved in arts and humanities investigation. However, the analogy in the academic imaginary of the lone white male exploring the “other” in a unidirectional manner demystifying the other’s exotic culture by overcoming obstacles and “objectively” recording observations has become obsolete. There are similar problematic optics in an able-bodied individual accessing a physically disabled community to conduct an enquiry on their way of living, especially in modern times where the cultural representation of minorities is constantly scrutinized (Dowling, 2000). For this reason, the researcher should constantly aim to have a full understanding of the self as a

researcher, the researched, and the research context. Hence for the first period of 6 months, I visited many groups or sessions as a guest (Rose, 1997).

My aim was to be perceived as a friendly guest by the service users and staff members alike and to gain a comprehension that goes past “understanding” and more like the German word “Verstehen” conceptually defined in academic research culture as “indicative of a comprehension that is conceptually distinct and furthest away from explanation. Verstehen refers to participative understanding from the first person, from the case locals' point of view, in a never-ending process and considering history, culture, and previous understandings” (Moriceau, 2012).

Having this approach in mind, it was only natural for me to take a step further and be involved in the community and their activities, to then write ethnographic accounts of these encounters. I was doing this at intervals of morning and afternoon groups. In this initial phase of the study, I was easing my way into the community, trying to get to know them as much as possible, with the idea of building rapport by getting acquainted with the people in this institution while noticing the challenges present in terms of disabilities and diverse meanings in the context of living in this community (See Fig.33). “Rapport” can be interpreted in academic jargon as the ability to connect with participants in a manner that materializes a climate of trust and understanding. It also implies the ability to get closer to somebody’s viewpoint. Spradley asserts that rapport is “a harmonious relationship between ethnographer and informant. It means that a basic sense of trust has developed that allows for the free flow of information. Both the ethnographer and the informant have positive feelings about the

Fig. 33 First day at the DRC (Author, 2018)

interviews, perhaps even enjoy them.” (Spradley 1979, p. 44) As Spradley intimates, rapport is made from trust and respect for one another, and this is the ideal starting point of relationship building, to understand each other feelings and actions and create a responsive bond. Without this crucial bond, the researcher cannot gain insight into unfamiliar settings as it’s the participant's perspective and good channels of communication are the source of vital data (Guillemin and Heggen, 2009) .

From October 2017 to March 2018, I conducted mainly ethnographic investigation by visiting the centre approximately twice a week with the simple mission of practising “participant observation” (Delamont, 2004), and record this as ethnographic accounts. During this process, I had the opportunity to get closer to staff members, service users, and the centre as a physical structure with a “sense of place” because the experience of Place or ‘placeness’ varies from one person to the next (Casey, 2001). To this research, I was most interested in the service users and participants as the ones who contextualize and activate the space. Among the most common physical challenges among the service users, I could observe conditions related to cerebral palsy, spina bifida, or post-stroke, such as Hypoesthesia (reduced sense of touch or sensation), Failing heart, Ataxia (lack of voluntary coordination of muscles and eyes), Multiple Sclerosis, limb weakness and stiffness, generalized pain. However, these conditions do not come alone. In combination with these physical conditions, I observed, and consulted with staff members finding other cognitive issues such as autism, anxiety avoiding eye contact, or noticeable stress, or sudden emotional changes.

4.2 Leaders, gatekeepers & negotiating access.

In this section, I discuss the negotiation for access with social actors at the DRC to be allowed to have access to participants for studies and information retrieval. As outlined by the initial proposal of this project, during the first stage of the research, I worked with established VR experiences (these include virtual reality experiences at the time available on the Oculus platform). Employing user observation and ethnographies as a form of explorative reflection, I started forming an idea of their disabilities and what could interest them in terms of what artefact

I could create in the second stage. However, to do so, I needed not only to build rapport (Trust, see 2.8) with the staff members and service users alike but also had to maintain it, to have a smooth transition into feedback gathering and to have their collaboration for further developments. Because of the staff member's ability to grant me access to participants and valuable information, they can be identified as “gatekeepers.”

While it is true that on paper, my access to the field workplace was granted from day one as part of the project permissions, immediate mutual trust was not guaranteed. Naturally, this trust needed to be built through a sequence of actions and experiences, and normally what I found was a healthy scepticism and sometimes unfounded suspicion among the service users and staff members towards a newcomer such as myself. I could recognize that because one of my supervisors was employed at the DRC during that period, his input as my cultural supervisor was valuable to allow me to connect, as he introduced me to others within the centre, and in a way, he vouched for me helping me build these relationships. In literature, we can find accounts in line with this process in hard-to-reach communities in Kuebler and Hausser (1997).

The realization of how essential it was for me to have somebody on the ‘inside’ attesting to my intentions made me reflect on what strategies can be adopted to build good interpersonal rapport for me as a researcher to enjoy trusting access. As Rose (1997) puts it, a researcher needs to constantly aim to evaluate himself and their environment. In literature, we can find a plethora of approaches and discussions about this subject. Many focus on the approach of “matching and mirroring” our interlocutors’ behaviour without “mimicking”. (Emmel et al., 2007), (Hull, 2007a),(Yang et al., 2016). Human communication is much more than simply the spoken word. There are three forms of communications in which others can pick up on, and these are voice, words & body (Churches and Roger 2007) (Tickle-Degnen and Rosenthal 1990). Firstly, a good strategy when it comes to verbal communication (voice and words) is for the researcher to focus his efforts on a verbal input that it’s not threatening or judgemental and harmonizes with the pace and tone of the interlocutor.

Nonverbal social cues also need to be considered. When a non-body-able individual communicates with the body-able there might at first a cultural barrier; for example, the voice cues and modulations of the body able might give the impression to the non-body-able, that their interlocutor is impatient or unwilling to communicate, while the body-able might signalling their insecurities as they might be unsure on how to communicate, these obstacles can be overcome with politeness, flexibility and by building communicational experience (Li, 2016). At the beginning of my experience, I had many time issues understanding service users and had the help of a staff member to act as a cultural interpreter.

It is important to be aware of our own “physicality,” namely, size, posture & gestures, which can help us coordinate ourselves in the presence of others to give our interlocutor a better perception.” this can be done by trying to be empathetic and showing interest in addition to active listening by using verbal cues (ok, oh... right, hmmm...), making eye contact and smiling, leaning forward to listen, matching the tone of their body language, showing that we are on their side and that we are interested in their ideas or stories (Kuebler and Hausser, 1997) (Arnold, Elizabeth C., 2015) (Hull, 2007b). However, sometimes in my experience for some neurodiverse people fix eye contact might feel threatening for them, so I would not stare but look at the infinite.

Cultivating these behaviours is intended to demonstrate that we are on their same mental wavelength. For example, there is an equilibrium between “getting close” and “maintaining distance” (Gordon, 1987). I found that standing beside some participants rather than interviewing by standing in front of them would be made them more receptive, or that sitting down or kneeling slightly under their eye level during interviews would make feel my wheelchair participants more comfortable and likely to talk or expending time and chatting about “the weather..” in the bus-waiting area was a good way to build rapport by “being there and being seen” (Sixsmith, Boneham and Goldring, 2003). Attending events outside of the DRC and even following their social media incarnations such as Facebook and Twitter were ways of showing interest and befriending, and this helped me establish commonalities and a relationship of trust

and mutual respect with critical members at the centre out of the rigidity of sessions and groups (see Fig. 34), permitting me to enter in contact with those moments in which people are less aware of an external observer, aiming to be perceived as somebody who has transparent intentions.

Fig. 34 Tweet exchange with a DRC service user at external DRC event (Author, 2018)

The term “gatekeeper” is an abstract idea. The literature on gatekeeping is fragmented in terms of epistemologies and fields of knowledge. However, it was primitively a form of addressing “individuals important in constructing and operating the constraints of choice in access to key resources such as housing” (Smith, Gregory, and Johnston, 1994). In geographical research, nowadays, this term is used across many

disciplines in the context of academic investigation, see for example (Jeffery & National Endowment for Science, 2005) . As explained by Corra and Willer (2002), gatekeeper’s control direct or indirect access to “benefits” that they do not own, these benefits are desired by their “Clients,” and clients incur in the obligation that might take the form of “fees” to access these benefits, these fees can be negotiated. However, the object of these negotiations, unlike a middleman in a financial transaction, is not the “ownership” but the “access,” which is a form of power interplay (Corra 2002). These social actors can determine whether a requestor can actively pursue the benefits of their network. For this switch to occur, however, there might be a negotiation because gatekeepers are not middlemen. Most of the time, this negotiation takes the form of a social or political process that involves the researcher in being reflexive and analytical by introspecting in their practice, even if it is a complicated task (Rose 1997). The researcher may, intentionally or otherwise, try to control gatekeepers' perceptions to increase the legitimacy in the field, as this is part of being a ‘good researcher ‘and increases the chances

of success. While gatekeepers at first may be thought of as obstacles to access, especially in a small community like the DRC where traditional authority structures and safeguarding systems are in place to protect the vulnerable. when the researcher is positively perceived, and there is mutual respect, the gatekeeper can be an ally as they can be helpful facilitators to understand political/cultural nuances, and increase acceptance among research subjects, sometimes even affecting the research agenda (Campbell et al., 2006).

(Emmel et al, 2007,) explain that gatekeepers typology to socially excluded communities could be divided into three categories in a basic level, among those we can find the informal gatekeeper firstly; is one of the limited links and unable to refer to others. The relationship of this type of individual community is one of befriending and supporting kind. - In my view, volunteers and service users who are community leaders at the centre fit this category because of their “helping hand” status.

Secondly, in this continuum, we can find the comprehensive gatekeeper; they endeavour with the task of addressing the social care and health of the service users, has a wide range of referral mechanisms across different areas of service allocation, i.e., assistive devices, rehabilitation services, and occupational therapy. The comprehensive gatekeeper also has established relationships with different individuals and groups inside or outside of the community. In my view, any session facilitator that runs groups or sessions at the DRC enters this category because they enable the main mission of the DRC as an independent living institution. The Formal Gatekeepers: Their main goal is to enact statutory measures to address social exclusion, and many times are part of multidisciplinary teams but also have limited community involvement. The manager or the social workers at the DRC could be within this category as they work within the community, but they are deployed by the council in other institutions across Renfrewshire.

After rapport is established, it needs to be maintained and nurtured. Apart from my visits, the main mode of communication I implemented with the centre was via email. Doing this was helpful to maintain rapport, I would normally email with the centres link person, and then she

would help me communicate with the staff members of participants. Researchers should maintain consistent contact by remaining visible, and this has been noted in other academic accounts (De Massis and Kammerlander 2020, p.424). Emailing by giving updates on my research and more informally communicating, for example, to send best wishes for the holidays, proved to be a good strategy to promote reciprocity, encouraging a cooperative attitude among my gatekeepers. As well, using the emails and calendar to store a record of our conversations served as a useful reminder of past events and milestones. However, understanding what worked and what didn't take some time. As explained in the methodology section, phronesis is an abstract concept that can be used to guide ethics. Doing so via reasoning that has been acquired by way of applied experience regarding the impact of our actions and how others perceive us; in other words, phronesis is the virtue of prudence or, put more technically, a critical situational judgment. However, phronesis can also be present when building rapport or even negotiating access, but it can be acquired after the practical experience because it requires the acumen to understand the complexities of human power relationships and the conduct of individuals.

Early on in my research, I understood the importance of getting acquainted with different staff members at the DRC. Making initial contact with different staff members who were running their groups would extend my possibilities of engaging with potential participants, as the pool of participants was limited in the iPad & tablets session ran by my cultural supervisor. Thus, visiting only one session would have provided only a limited viewpoint to be able to understand the community. Therefore, I started visiting other sessions, always first agreeing my visits with the DRC manager, with the individual staff members who oversaw running their sessions so I could practice participant observation during their groups and continue building rapport with these gatekeepers. I recognized as a result of these visits the eagerness from these gatekeepers to maintain their credibility and to make sure that I would fit in without affecting their status within their community, this has been noted in other accounts (Eide and Allen, 2005) (Sanghera and Thapar-Björkert, 2008), so I would not endanger their relationship with their group members and maintain their status as respected members of their communities (McAreevey and Das, 2013). Gatekeepers exercise a form of power by controlling access. Hence, I had always presented these

relationships as built via a sequence of events that would be pleasantly remembered by service users and staff members, gradually gaining credibility and trust, which was also part of the process of continually negotiating access from a semi-insider position.

4.3 Pilot study

When I first started thinking about the type of research artefact or VR experiences for this project, I had to consider firstly my primary stakeholders, which are the service users at the DRC, staff members, as well as the centre itself as a physical space and as an institution with schedules and boundaries. To get to know them better, I socially engaged with group leaders and service users to start collecting rich data from the ethnographic encounters. I repeatedly visited the community via groups and sessions, recognising these as the driving force behind the DRC's "Independent living" guiding beliefs, in the hope this engagement would generate trusting and manageable relationships between myself as the researcher and my contributors. The catalyst to establish these relationships, as noted in different academic accounts, is plain good communication (Guillemin and Heggen 2009), especially when the researcher engages in observation and interviews. Hence in the next step, after attending groups and sessions, I moved to create ethnographies to reflect on my experiences, to also interchange this method with pilot studies.

Pilot studies are often used as a preparation for future studies (Polit and Hungler 1994). After the period of ethnographic data collection, I turned my attention to the purpose of studying the response of participants to VR experiences based on the simulation research design model (See 3.5). I searched for some ready-to-use applications which at the time I deemed useful to understand the relationship between VR and the subjective emotional wellbeing the service users at the centre could experience. During this pilot study, my secondary goals revolved around these 4 points:

- 1) comprehend the conditions of recruiting participants at the DRC.

- 2) train me as a field researcher who aims to understand cultural phenomena to better develop immersive digital experiences.
- 3) reflect upon the meaning and challenges of living with a disability in as ableist society.
- 4) test the competency of the interview question and the process.

After researching what type of experiences were available on the Oculus platform, I decided to find out which were the most popular VR experiences and tested some myself or with users during my visits to see if they were suitable, then by doing a thematical analysis, the chosen experiences were divided into three categories.

The study was carried out at the DRC in Paisley. For the workshops, the participation was voluntary, and initially, it was individual due to the capacity of delivering VR to one person at the time and the fact that I had only one headset during that period. However, it became clear that it was necessary to at least do the study in pairs or groups. Some participants were contacted face-to-face in the days before the pilot study to make sure that they understood what the study involved and what was required of them, because as noted by some authors participants of co-production processes “will only co-produce when benefits outweigh costs “(Verschuere, Brandsen and Pestoff, 2012) This reward may be monetary, or altruistic in nature, going beyond self-interest, so they were at ease that the process was transparent, and interesting to them. Other participants were recruited during the day of the event with the help of the contact person at the DRC, who at that time was my cultural supervisor.

The workshops took place from around 9:30 AM to 3:00 PM in an area free from distraction (Library room). While I was the acting researcher, I had the help and company of one staff member per session. This was helpful not only for communication purposes but also because participants present an array of physical and sometimes cognitive challenges, and the help of an experienced staff member was required to meet their needs. Among the service users, I

established 12 of them as my main participants, and they are a representative sample of the DRC population in terms of gender, disabilities, and age (see Appendix B)

Before the interview session – there was allocated be enough time for the attendees to be put at ease and to explain the workshop to them. At this point was made clear to the participants they might be recorded and observed by signing the participant consent sheet. (5 min approx.)

The first phase was to meet and greet the participants. In this first phase, the scope is to introduce the participants to space, where he/she was greeted and brought to the room to start the workshop. The researcher will read or have read to them the participant information sheet, explaining who is involved and how the experiment will be conducted and reported. (5 min approx.)

The initial conversation and questioning moved from general questions to more specific questions depending on the conversation development. (5 min approx.)

The debriefing followed a similar format as phase one (semi-structured conversation), where the main intention is to find out how the participant felt after experiencing VR media in the context of their wellbeing. (10 min approx.)

4.3.1 “A place to visit” workshop - Tue 15th March 2018:

The first one was themed around the idea of place transfiguration of location, using VR to enable them to travel to exciting places transcending the boundaries of any mobility issues they might have, which was one of the first challenges I noticed, and something that could be done as it’s one of VR biggest strengths. Moreover, day trips are prominently promoted at the DRC as a form of leisure for its members. Therefore, I named the first workshop “A Place to Visit.” This workshop revolves around virtually visiting places of interest that would seem out of reach or would have a sense of thrill and adventure (See Fig.35).

I downloaded videos from the Samsung VR – Discovery App, the first one was a “Experience the Elusive Tiger” (Discovery, 2016) The places virtually visited were the jungle, where the users got

virtually close to tigers, under the sea where attendees virtually swim with sharks with “Sharks among us – Getting the shot” (Discovery,2016) and a virtual tour of Japan Discovery VR Atlas: Japan (Discovery, 2016). I am looking to find out from these experiences the positive impact of visiting a reality that is different and unexpected from one’s own.

Fig. 35 Man in awe virtually seeing tigers up-close (Author, 2018)

4.3.2 “VR Docs for empathy” workshop - Tue 20th March 2018:

The second category aimed to understand the empathy or emotions experienced by the user encountering other people’s realities via immersive movies. This is very important for my study, given that potential improvement in health and wellbeing could be elicited by emotional responses. This workshop aims to understand the connection with body ownership, immersion in the virtual world and wellbeing. The workshops ran over two weeks during the end of March, with four sessions. I employed qualitative interview methods, which were administered to the volunteers in a semi-structured manner.

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I wanted to find interesting and conversation-starting material, coincidentally at the time the refugee crisis was at its peak, and immersive documentaries were booming and were a growing field within VR; the experience chosen was “The Displaced” (New York Times, 2015), a documentary following the lives of three refugee children and their families. This workshop intended to understand the emotional response and perception of the attendees related to issues of others, when being immersed in a story, mainly to understand if there was more empathy than receiving the information through other media (See Fig.36).

Fig. 36 Man watching Documentary VR (Author, 2018)

4.3.3 “Hands-on.” Workshop - Tue 22nd March 2018:

The third VR event at the DRC had a choice of playful experiences. In this Workshop, users could see and play games with virtual embodiments of their hands. This workshop aims to understand the connection between immersion in the virtual world and wellbeing. These activities have to do with using your own body in the virtual world; this is achieved by using hand tracking recognition devices such as a Leapmotion or a GEAR VR controller. The activities are 4, and they all require fine motor movement and could be interesting from a storytelling point of view as well as challenging enough to be rewarding for them; the following three experiences for

leapmotion Playground were from the Leapmotion Appstore , a) “Robots” - In this activity, the participants must use their hands to grab the cubes and place them on the top of the robots, b) Kyoto– Where using your hands you can influence the growth of a tree and c) “Flower” – were the player can play “... Loves me not” (see Fig. 38, Leapmotion, 2015), and the one featured on the HMD was “Paint VR” (Coksami LLC, 2017) from the Samsung-Oculus store where the player can paint with a virtual brush (See Fig. 37).

This activity required the controller's use to draw a house using all the basic geometric figures, Circle, Square, triangle. The initial three visualisations played on a computer screen with leap motion, gathering interest in hand gesture controllers. The early idea for the leap motion-based ones was to play them with the VR headset. However, the android headset would have required a hack and much work to go into that to make it work; therefore, it was not sustainable.

The last activity was to draw a house with a motion controller in VR with the Samsung Oculus controller. I employed a conversational approach rather than questioning, using semi-structured interviews and interpersonal active listening skills, with the purpose to gather the testimony to gather their interests and opinions, to then use this information to develop software and immersive experiences for this community.

Fig. 38 Service User Playing with hand movement tracking game

4.3.4 Reflection and results of the pilot study

The primary purpose of this pilot study was to gather and study the response of participants to a selection of VR experiences, and even if some participants found the headset clunky and non-ergonomic. The workshops were successful on the premise of getting participants closer to VR and pave the way to more studies, After all, VR has that initial 'Wow factor', which is intrinsic to VR but fades over time, especially with mobile headsets. The workshops also helped me understand a bit better about their previous use of VR and their disabilities and gave me a glimpse into their way of living.

These graphs provide an overview of the population who was invited to these workshops (See Table 2); overall, out of the twelve participants, most of them have never used VR and those who had done it through google cardboard, which is a very basic apparatus for VR visualisation and some of them had trouble remembering what they saw. Most of the workshop participants were female and presented mobility issues using wheelchairs to navigate the world, and more than

three-quarters of my population are within the ages of 45 to 60+, making them reluctant to try new technologies, a proof of this is the digital literacy workshops that my cultural supervisor was running at the DRC with the hope of teaching basic digital skills to service users for an older population charity within the DRC. Overall, most of the participants agreed that it felt like “almost being there”, and most of them reported a sense of immersion that goes beyond other types of media such as television.

Table 2 - Demographics:

The first workshop was successful on the premise of detaching the viewing from their reality, taking them out of the room by virtually transporting them into realities that were new to them. On this day, they have virtually swum with sharks, visited tigers in their native jungle, and had a virtual tour of Japan. Immersive VR created a sense of adventure and the thrill of the unknown.

Or in other cases learning about other cultures and places of interest which could also be rewarding for the participants; beyond the awe of engaging with immersive VR for the first time, During the participant observation, I noticed that after all simulation participants were experience a sense of wonder, gesturing excitement and announcing their awe with onomatopoeic sounds like “wow”. Overall looking happier and more content after virtually exploring other places far away from their realities, there was immersion, curiosity to know more about these places.

At the very beginning of the second workshop, a lady who had participated in the last workshop told me excitedly “I told everybody at dinner that I have tried Virtual Reality, my grandson was so impressed, he wanted to know where you bought this?” (see Appendix A) She was referring to the HMD headset, to me, this served as a proof of the validation this participant received at home from her family for self-actualising and as a proof that immersive VR was slowly becoming commonplace in the imagination of the DRC culture. To me, the second workshop achieved the objective of putting the users in the shoes of refugee children; because watching it ignited a conversation about how much are we doing to help these children, and some felt the need to help. One of the participants said that seeing this over and over on the news everyday desensitises you, to what another user followed with saying, “Using this thing is like being there, in television you watch the news, and it doesn’t bring the message home like this, those children need help”. (see Appendix A) While it was obvious that there was a sense of immersion, I have to say that I noticed the mood of the participants overall declined as they were affected by it; for this reason, at the end of the interview, I would try to bring a positive note by closing with the question where you would go using VR. The care staff member participating in this workshop fed back that she believed VR could be used better for relaxation and mindfulness, whereas the participants mainly suggested going outdoors to nature or virtually touring Spain or Italy.

The third workshop was surprisingly enjoyable for the users; they were impressed to be able to use their hands in the virtual world and seemed to be more immersed and focused when they were able to interact. Probably because they saw an embodiment of themselves in the virtual world heightened the illusion of being there. Because of these activities, the impression I have is that they enjoyed playing and using their bodies within the digital world as this felt somehow natural for them; drawing the house was not as popular as the other two experiences where you use your hands.

Concerning my secondary goals **(1)** I was able to comprehend the conditions of recruiting participants at the DRC; the idea I had of inviting them personally failed in my view for some reasons, first the service users have fixed days of service, and second their purpose to come to the DRC is mainly to attend their sessions and they want to do that, hence the best way to get in contact with them was through the staff members running the sessions they would attend, this would help me recruit them with their rapport established with their staff members **(2)** being able to coordinate this workshops, also provided me with the first-hand experience of a field researcher aims to understand cultural phenomena to better develop immersive digital experiences, **(3)** I could also reflect on what is the meaning of living with a physic disability by asking them about their everyday lives, **(4)** conducting this semi structured conversations, gave an insight of their capabilities, and I understood that I needed to adapt my methodologic approach from an initial structured interviews delivered in a format of 1-on-1 sessions, to I have open conversations with a group of them, so they would feel more comfortable with other people they know and this would emulate the format they use for their own sessions.

As mentioned before, the purpose of the workshops was to collect the anecdotes and opinions after using different forms of VR with the service users at the Centre. At the very beginning, I wanted to co-create and co-design the immersive experiences, however after these workshops with all the disruption and work they imply after consulting with my supervisory team, I decided to approach the artefact creation method in such a way that I would move away from pure co-creation and co-design methods, but one that would have the participants as formal consultants.

For that effect I chose to engage the community into a consultation approach. Given the intricacy of having them to design on a computer, code or do recording audio and video, the methodology I had planned for these workshops was modified to benefit better conversations and to promote inquiry, always having in mind the comfort of the participants. One example is that attendees in most cases preferred to participate with somebody else for this activity: this allowed interaction with others during the viewings, or working within the spectrum of disabilities displayed by the users to enable communication dynamics that would make them feel at ease. In conclusion, I would say the general feeling is that experiences that go back to nature and connection with oneself bring general interest to the people I have interviewed. Others get comfort on the idea of revisiting places they have been before, and all the interviewed have a romanticised idea of a place they would love to visit.

To formulate my initial ideas, I opted for a user-centred approach, where I first took into consideration what I knew about the physical, emotional, and cognitive challenges the service users face, and a common denominator was the mobility issues, which prevent them from performing activities and experiencing. - Therefore, there is an emphasis on the DRC on day trips; many pictures of trips to natural spaces cover the walls of the DRC. Second, I thought about the needs of the staff members, who are there to deliver these sessions, they require simplicity, and there are varying levels of technical proficiency, and last I thought about the DRC as a place where the main form of service delivery are sessions of groups and has restrictions of internet connection, meaning the experiences need to work offline and have certain replayability (see table 3).

Table 3 - Observations on stakeholders (Authors, 2020)

| |
|---|--|---|
| Service Users | Staff Members | The Centre |
| Many service users live with physical disabilities. | Staff Members need to prepare for their activities; therefore, simplicity is needed. | Public wi-fi restrictions |
| They are interested outdoor surroundings, especially those in nature and in relaxation. | Technical proficiency differs from staff members. | The group schedule present alternative wellbeing sessions. |
| Some Service Users might present shallow breathing derived from anxiety and discomfort. | Some are not keen in new technology. | Activities need to be scheduled within sessions. |
| Because of their limitations, generally, they are in the lookout for stimulus. | Session facilitators are in the lookout for new ideas for their activities. | The DRC present various spaces, each of these has a purpose. |
| Prefer group activities, where there is opportunity for socialization. | Take pride on their work. | |

At this point, the type of experiences I had in mind was fell within the categories of mindfulness meditation, exposure to immersive natural healing environments, visits to places that can be explored and are of interest (museums, city squares, parks), or serious games where using kinetic controllers they could train their bodies, use their memory or undertake job training, in the next two chapters we examine the process of creation of the first experience and what methodologies were applied for community consultation, as part of user testing to produce a mindfulness meditation experience using the natural spaces of the West of Scotland.

Chapter 5: Produce – Tune into nature.

In the literature review, I surveyed the relationship between humans, images, and the power of immersive VR and how this media has typically been used for the illusory transformation of location and the self. Furthermore, I have also explained how immersive media has been explored for health and wellbeing purposes within research settings. Following this, I outlined how environments entirely composed or intervened with natural elements and processes, i.e., Natural light, the flow of water, patterns in the greenery, open air spaces etc., are discussed in academia as a healing influence, to then explain how guided meditation can build resilience, in both cases creating a sense of wellbeing through contemplation. I also described how rituals differentiate themselves from other quotidian actions and what benefits might they possess and how they are ubiquitous in human transactions. Understanding how rituals exist at the DRC might help to find a framework for immersive VR within the cultural grounds of the centre, as rituals, when performed collectively have the power to preserve old concepts or serve as a medium for traditionalization of new ones (Moore & Myerhoff, 1977).

5.1 Rituals at the DRC

As seen in Islam and Zyphur (2009) in any institution, daily activities serve to achieve a tangible end. For example, a student must study to obtain good marks, or an employed performing a good job could help you obtain a promotion at work. None the less, the daily actions of individuals or groups in any organization also hold symbolic meaning that provides a dual purpose. In which the identities, beliefs, and emotions of said communities can be established, and evolved. This way daily actions can reveal a duality of meaning. In other words, “Ritual action, it is proposed, is a form of social action in which a group’s values and identity are publicly demonstrated or enacted in a stylized manner, within the context of a specific occasion or event.” (Ibid p.116)

In communities these rituals actions are cultural phenomena that condense the culture of a place into micro-intervals, revealing to the researcher compressed information about the

culture in this setting that would be more difficult to read otherwise (Trice & Beyer, 1984). After my visits and consulting the literature, I realised that, during the period I visited the DRC, I witnessed activities and behaviours that hold ritualistic dimensions, ranging from small everyday interactions to ceremonies. From my perspective these ritual behaviour or actions gave a sense of formality and served different purposes that I would like to broadly explain to shed light on how rituals serve as liminal cognitive spaces to aid transition at the DRC.

As part of their nature, institutions move between the needs of stability and change (Leana and Barry, 2011). Using as interpretational tool the taxonomy of organizational ritual described in the book *The Cultures of Work Organizations* (McCollom, Trice and Beyer, 1994). While this taxonomy was originally created to fit work organizations, I believe it can be adapted to the centre. As to my understanding the DRC can be a hybrid surrogate solution for service users, where they can find the cognitive and societal stimulation, others might encounter in schools and workplaces.

Rites of passage are identified as rituals where an individual moves between spaces or groups (See Fig.39). According to Van Gennep et al (2013), often inserted within ceremonial context, this ritual has the purpose to reinstate the collective consensus. The lunch time is a locus for rituals to happen, the lunch happens in the main hall. In there, after lunch, they all might in unison sing and wish someone a happy birthday, this way celebrating the pass of time, or they might use this opportunity to welcome or wish goodbye to a member of the community (See Appendix A). However, I believe these rituals can be less ceremonial in nature. Salutation and tea pause rituals are routinary at the DRC, they mark the beginning, middle and end of activities, everyday buses and family members arrive to the DRC to transport the service users, where Staff members have the habit to friendly welcome the service users and help them to offboard the buses. They are sorted into their daily activities, then they participate in a tea pause, to then be transported back at the end of their service. These rituals of salutation and pause mark the symbolic rhythm of the day, in a manner that reminds the one of a school with classes and activities.

Rites of enhancement, highlight to the rest of the community the individuals whose behaviour represent the ideals and worldview of the organization. An example of this would be the status transition at the DRC where service users choose to become part of the Users Committee. This board seeks to promote the independent living values at the DRC and is involved in the execution of activities and consultation of the daily functioning at the centre. Their pictures and names are displayed in the entrance corridor as a point of reference to others.

Rites of renewal can be found in the periodical declaration of the guiding values at the DRC, an example of this would be ceremonies where the DRC displays their independent living ideals by showcasing art, dance, and musical performances of the community. In my view, this type of rituals serves as a perpetuation of the community's identity and takes the form of annual meetings or commemoration ceremonies.

Fig. 39 DRC members perform at an annual DRC Ceremony (Author, 2018)

Rites of integration are those rituals that provide a common ground where all members of the community can join and socially mix, at the DRC these rituals are of maximum importance, given that service users come from all paths of life are present. And these might choose different activities depending on their taste. For example, while the woodwork group is comprised of only men, and the Self-Running is comprised of only women, the same is true for some other groups. I believe the current affairs group is a “melting pot” of approaches, because while it is a competition game where the participants challenge their knowledge of songs and current culture, it also is a ritual where groups between different groups that would not normally interact enter in alliance with one another to be declared at the end the winners of the match: in this way establishing roles, perpetuating norms or establishing a change within the existent community paradigm.

Rites of conflict reduction as the name describe, are public symbolical demonstrations of action in responses to situations that lead to distress to the community. These rituals seek to open lines of dialogue and communication to deescalate violence. An example of these can be found in instances where the DRC connect to the local community via a program called “Spuds for buddies”. In this initiative the DRC engaged with local schools to promotes healthy eating and gardening skills, but it also improved the relationship between the DRC and local children. On itself this is a ritual where the DRC members allow these school children to enter within the DRC domain as co-creators of these project, working the plant beds jointly. Somehow this is a ritual where the ownership of the land is shared. The effectivity of this program is demonstrated by the reduction of vandalism in the DRC’s Garden area (See Fig. 40 and appendix A).

Fig. 40 Author helping prepare plant beds (Author, 2018)

In this section I have outlined some examples of symbolic actions that can hold a dual meaning and be interpreted as rituals within the DRC. In the adaptation of this taxonomy, I have omitted “Rites of degradation” as I never observed anything like it at the centre as it doesn’t align with its values of empowerment.

Furthermore, we can also find activities that are purposely ritualistic such the alternative medicine session, or others that find their origin in health practices that can defined as rituals of health, in some of these I found inspiration for the creation of the first artifact.

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5.1.1 The Creative & Production process:

In this section, I explain the creative process behind creating and producing “*Produce – Tune into nature*”. “Produce”, in short, was partly inspired first by the other activities at the DRC such as Relaxation or Tai chi; These activities are based on ritualistic contemplation. Second in the result of the workshops, as service users seemed to enjoy visiting natural spaces, associating them with recreation and connection to oneself ¹, these benefits had an impact to their well-being; following Gessler’s ideas, where the memory of specific environment is charged with emotions. However, visiting these spaces can be challenging for the DRC service users due to mobility challenges. Nonetheless, VR can produce the illusory transformation of place, recreating natural healing environments, “Produce” was created with the secondary purpose of creating familiarity with immersive media within the DRC community.

In his book *Network Nature* Richard Coyne asserts that “Tuning” was a famous metaphor of the electronic age - as if rotating the dial on an old radio to attune into the right channel. He also asserts that expanding into the meaning, it can also mean to “pick up signs and cues of a place” (Coyne, 2018, p. 9). In the same order of ideas, he says that “*tuning into nature*” is an expression used by those who commune with nature, to explain the human-nature relationship, where nature presents us with rhythms to tune into (Ibid). These rhythms can be made by specific frequencies that humans perceive as restorative sounds, for example birds singing or water flow (Ratcliffe, Gatersleben and Sowden, 2013). Alternatively, visually, they fall into the terminologies discussed in the “Healing Natural environments” section. “Soft fascination” and “coherence” (**AAT**), and surroundings with enough complexity, structure, and depth (**SRT**) providing humans with visual stimuli that are interesting and non-chaotic or overwhelming, that can sensibly engross our attention and leave enough mental bandwidth to reflect creating a restorative effect. Due to Processing fluency account, this interpretative approach explains that visual fractality and self-repetition naturally occurring in nature can be more easily interpreted by humans’

¹ See Appendix A, p.04

perception and efficiently processed by our minds, requiring less attention due to the repetition of the patterns, or self-similar items in a complex object (Joye et al., 2016).

Natural landscapes are also prominently featured on the walls of the centre, with pictures telling the stories of day trips with the moviemaking and photography groups, and at the first phase workshops many participants expressed they enjoy visiting the great outdoors with their families and DRC groups. Moreover, I realised big glass windows allow for the light, flowers, and greenery of the big outside front and back gardens to be seen inside. Indoor plants also claim certain space and are used as decoration – This suggest to me that as seen in chapter two, that metanarrative that we call ‘Nature’ is perceived at the DRC at some point in between environmental idealism and environmental instrumentalism.

Meditation can be used as a distractive tool for pain management. “Produce” supplies the viewer with easy and pleasant natural environments as a framing device for the service users to engage with MBSR techniques. Following these exercises, the viewers generate awareness on how to control their breathing and relaxing their bodies. Over guided mindfulness exercises the viewer could build discipline and resilience and use it as a well-being tool for service users and staff members alike. This immersive experience could have a plan build around it for further use as part of the services provided by the DRC, to reduce the effect of anxiety, depression and stress and aid their Perceived Restorativeness (PR). I would also like to point out that while at the very beginning I aimed to produce an MBBT guided audio experience, due to budget and time constraints, I had to choose one among the mindfulness techniques, and I chose to produce a mindful breathing exercise, as I discovered that shallow breathing was a common denominator among many service users.

In Chapter Two, I set out how media and its artefacts could be catalysts that affect people’s emotional states and that these media components can make people tune into different moods, but I also explained how the power of VR could help the mind to engross our finite attention resources into a different reality. In addition to that, the extended-mind thesis explains that the human mind is augmented by external tools of thought process (e.g. calculator, pen, telescope),

which extend its power of understanding, information processing, knowledge acquisition and world orientation (Clark and Chalmers 1998), With its capability to simulate the world, immersive technologies such as VR can extend the power of the human mind in thought processing at an unprecedented scale that has yet to be exploited for health and well-being. While VR experiences are currently used as part of exploratory therapy, few records exist in the use of VR experiences linked to Therapeutic landscapes or restorative theory elements, such as soft fascination and mindfulness techniques, combined with the likes of MBBT over extended periods, as supporting choices form the creation of wellbeing in disabled communities. In the future, I would like to extend this work by including PMR as part of the mindfulness techniques used in this series of projects.

In the last chapter, I explained the creation and execution of an explorative pilot study where using different categories of VR experiences, I conducted three different workshops to gather the reaction of the participants to VR, and how taking into consideration the results, reflecting on the constraints, the needs, and the wishes of the participants. As a result, I had the intention to create three different experiences, each one of them with a different focus. One of them being “*Produce*”, which is a mindfulness immersive experience aiming to use healthy natural environments and soothing sounds found in nature as a way of having within reach “Therapeutic landscapes” for the healing of the physically disabled individuals in a caring community in Paisley, to help them tune into pleasant mood states, there are other studies within the ecopsychology area proving similar positive affect as seen in immersive VR for health and wellbeing section.

Based on my experiences at the DRC and their testimonies, I knew DRC service users were interested in visiting natural environments and spaces that were difficult to access because of their mobility issues. For the said reasons, in the planning phase of this experience's production, my first step was to research online and by “word of mouth” places that interested my users to visits and were also within my reach (see Fig.41), During this time my cultural supervisor was also involved in creating an immersive tour experience of a natural reserve for ROAR another institution in Renfrewshire who care for the elderly. – This could have also inspired me.

5.1.2 Finding healing landscapes:

Fig. 41 Tuscan Hills equirectangular image, used in prototype as example of green space (Author, 2018)

Not all views are created equally. Within the terminology of “therapeutic landscapes”, there is a colour coding shorthand to identify healing spaces. The most common of these codes are “Blue” for aquatic, Green for those environments dominated by plants (Vaeztavakoli, Lak and Yigitcanlar 2018) and Yellow for deserts. The literature also tells us about the preference for green and blue spaces (ibid), but while overall blue spaces are preferred, (Völker and Kistemann 2011) it also says that green spaces, combined with interventions of “Blue Spaces” in them, for example, lakes, streams, fountains etc. are perceived as more pleasant and restorative than Green and Blue on their own (White, et al. 2010). Fortunately, Scotland is blessed with many green spaces, and these are graced with water bodies, making this spaces perfect for the finding of healing natural spaces. Therefore, the natural environments I was looking for, were spaces that provided Aesthetic properties such as coherence and fascination, in terms of naturally occurring patterns that are understandable and non-chaotic, but with enough to see in terms of complexity, structure and depth.

During the first recording phase, I visited “Green” and “Blue” spaces to explore the possibilities, including those mentioned by the DRC service users or staff members in our conversations, e.g.

Balloch, Lochwinnoch and Loch Lomond. These all were places with meaning and a sense of place for service users; however, I found three significant challenges when recording in these spaces. One was the unpredictable weather. When recording in 360 degrees, rain and winds are a risk for the equipment and the overall audio-visual fidelity of the scenes, especially in a region where strong winds and constant rains are not the exceptions but the rule.

When filming in 360 degrees, the first and biggest challenge I found when recording was the weather, the weather was the reason for which I had to plan and sometimes accept defeat at the hands of treacherous and unexpected winds combined with rains or unwelcoming. When recording in 360 degrees, rain and winds are a risk for the equipment, but for the overall audio-visual fidelity of the scenes, especially in a region, strong winds and constant rains are not the exceptions, but the rule.

The second challenge I encountered when looking for spaces to feature in the experience was the translation between the bidimensional images found online, illustrating natural spaces; or the imaginary depictions of these spaces referenced by others “word of mouth”; and the presential reality, deferred sometimes greatly, subverting my expectations. This happens because when a standard picture or video is taken, the viewer as a director can choose what to focus on and what to discriminate from the frame. Something like this happens when somebody tells you about a landscape they find healing or fascinating, as these recommendations are based upon memories constructed with the sociocultural elements, creating a phenomenon called place attachment, which, to put simply, is the emotional bond between person and place, where over time people can develop a sense of familiarity referred as a sense of place (Florek, 2011)(Rose, 2013)(Scannell and Gifford, 2017). However, I noticed this does not happen when the viewer is present; the place is unfiltered and unedited, leaving you the “viewer” with a raw version of the space, these spaces deferred from my expectations as their online embodiments were not always matching reality, finding buildings, abounding quantity of people, and sometimes litter as part of these realistic encounters. I felt troubled thinking about this “lost in translation”-experience. My expectations were crushed by the reality and affordances of the spaces, just as described by Kaplan’s “preference model” (Kaplan and Rachel 1987), where I felt,

I was not compatible with some of these environments because of their incoherence when translated into a 360° video, almost as if they didn't make me feel welcome, or made me feel disappointed by not fulfilling my expectations of the environment, and in some instances even made me feel at peril or in some cases triggering a sensation of discomfort. I was aware of debris, or strangers nearby, keeping me in increased arousal, therefore not allowing me to fully relax, in line with the idea that danger reduces restorative perceptions and the theory of "Prospect-refuge", This theory suggests that humans have an innate evolutionary desire for expansive views to oversee spaces [Prospect], whilst feeling safe [Refuge], be allowed to relax. (Birgitta and Andrews 2013; Dosen and Ostwald 2013; Herzog & Rector, 2009) considering this and thinking about how my participants would feel, I decided to look further and explore as abundantly as possible, up until I would find restorative environments where these elements made me feel out of place were not present.

The third challenge I encountered when filming on 360° was that because the camera only renders a monoscopic view, that it's then, in turn, reproduced in both eyes when the HMD is on. As a result, the viewer does not receive the presential fidelity as I perceived it while filming. Therefore, the end-viewer lost part of the sense of depth that we normally perceive with a human stereoscopic view.

5.1.3 Consultations and testing:

First service users' test and staff consultation:

After filming some views in different locations, were some were suggested by the DRC service users and my cultural supervisor. I prepared a proof-of-concept showreel on an immersive video format, with the scope of testing it with the HMD, to understand how viable this would be, and to run it by some peers to find out if after going through a ten-minute meditation in VR they experienced any mood improvement. For this proof of concept, I used the audio from a free to use an online resource, with the idea of doing something similar, then I created a proof of concept that was only to test the interactivity using a controller with the idea of presenting it to the DRC users & staff to gather their impressions (See Fig.42).

During December 2018 I conducted a user test with 4 service users and a support of a DRC staff member, the idea was to gather some feedback and to have a consultation on the idea of producing a VR experience using natural environments and relaxation, for this day I wanted to let them use first an early technical prototype to understand what would be their relationship with the navigation options available within the app, the first alternative was to use their hands or to use a timed-gaze input by directing their look at one of the options, in this version if they were able to first click a scene with the controller, they would be taken to the another similar scene where they had to trigger the video with their gaze, and only after they had successfully cleared this two scenes, they would be virtually transported to a single nature location where only natural video and sounds were in display and I would let them watch the video up until they would raise their hand to have the headset removed.

Fig. 42 "Produce" interactive controller prototype (Author 2018)

The second activity was to watch an immersive video showreel of selected locations listening to a guided meditation. In the end, I would ask them to let me know which ones were their favourites for future development and what was the opinion of the interlocutor's voice.

When I asked them to perform the tasks during this user test, two participants had issues using the controller, even if the Timed-Gazed input was less intuitive; however, they understood how to use it quickly. I believe this is because the gaze input was the form of navigation that required less effort. After some minutes of visualising the natural environment with only the naturally occurring sounds, the participants were slightly confused about what to do next. One of them abruptly asked, "Is this it?", other participants did not last on average more than 4-5 minutes on

the virtual space. I understood the DRC service users would be engaged for long enough if the only attraction this experience had was the display of natural landscapes. That event opened questions about the re-usability of this experience and how reliable an experience like this would bring upon a sense of wellbeing. Considering the before mentioned, I was now sure the experience needed an activity to perform to keep the service users engaged, and for the staff members to see this experience as a viable investment of their time as they could use within their activities or groups.

Since the beginning of the project, nature and meditation were elements that kept appearing in conversations, as suggestions from both service users and staff members. While mindful activities such as meditation, colouring books, and walks on parks are often prescribed to fight over-thinking, I did not want to assume they were a perfect match up until I proposed this prototype during the first user test, where participants expressed that it was not meant to engage with this environment with no other input, and during this session, they agreed among them that having a mindfulness activity would be interesting to them and appropriate for the DRC.

While the proof of concept was adequate because people using it reported feeling better after practising meditation using the experience, and they were responding to the natural elements in a soft fascinating manner one participant said “The waves hitting the rocks looks perilous at first, but then you focus on the sunset and the sound of the waves and it makes you feel calmer”, it was clear that it needed to be adjusted, for example, considering what I knew about the manual mobility of my participants. I decided that the menu would not be selected using a hand controller but a “Timed-Gaze” input, which at the time was a widespread and uncomplicated module of interaction in VR. Also, some who tested it agreed on what spaces they preferred discriminating those clips with images that were not clear enough (pixelated). Because the quality affected the immersion or those clips, they deemed less attractive, and finally, many thoughts that the guiding voice needed a Scottish accent to feel more familiar and perhaps more endearing to the DRC service users, rather than the English American accent from the test version of the experience as this would bring a sense of closeness to those spaces they knew.

In the Methodology chapter, I explained the limitations, methods and methodologies of this project using a Human-centred design, going through an iterative and incremental development process. In addition to that, in this section, I expand in more detail the production process, with examples and anecdotes to illustrate my experiences, which cannot be divorced from each one another in exploratory research such as this. For this reason, I will continue to discuss the timeline of the creation and production of this piece.

The second step in this process was the analysis of my stakeholders by assessing the project scope, which was the design & planning. To reflect and understand better the journey of my participants, I created a storyboard reflecting the scenario. The storyboarding method can be a form of organising thoughts, communicating an idea and visual analysis for real-life situations (Walker et al., 2015). In it, I portrayed an inspirational idea of what I wished for my users to experience, always grounding this scenario to real life. This was useful for me to reflect on the user journey; in addition, it was a great tool to communicate my ideas and intent to others in a visual manner.

During my visits to the DRC, many times I observed the relationship between service users and staff members as one of trust and friendship; in this “Scenario” storyboard (see Fig.43 (Schmidt, et al., 2020)). I aim to capture a representation of hypothetical scene, that could happen in real life where in the right side we see the actual scenario, where a staff members engages in friendly and helpful conversation with a service user, and the situation it portrays is one where somebody with a disability can sometimes have feelings of anxiety or depression due to personal circumstances, leading to unhealthy habits, such as stress eating or ruminating thoughts. However, a staff member can offer support in the form of advice or the implementation of new media such as VR, to help the main character in the story. On the left of the storyboard, we can see what could happen, in essence after this recommendation, our main character goes through a journey of contemplative practice using VR, feeling better at the end of this.

In mid-January 2019, I visited the DRC once more to conduct an interview to test another prototype version of the experience with the staff members. Because I wanted to have as many participants as possible and not to hurry them, I simply sat in an office the DRC provided me during the whole afternoon, and I welcomed them as they had time to spare during the afternoon. The procedure was simple. I would first explain the scope of the application using the storyboard, to then onboard them into this prototype, it featured one home scene with three scenes to go to, however tall the scenes would play the same showreel with different immersive natural scenes. After the simulation, I would ask them how they felt again and if they had any thoughts they wished to share and if they thought this could be something they could see working at the DRC.

During the first sessions, I tested the prototype and consulted with two staff members. It was the first time they used VR, both were able to focus their gaze on the button and access the scene with no problem. After the simulation, when I off-boarded them and asked them to tell me about their experience, they were impressed, one of them said that it should be used only for service users, this could also be open for staff members, during this conversation one of them told me she practised meditation for a long time and sometimes the hardest is to stay sited, because thoughts of things to do come to your mind, but because she had the headset on, it was a reminder that this was a time to meditate. At the end of the conversation, both reported that they experienced a sense of immersion and felt calmer and more focused afterwards. Following this, it was the turn of another staff member; however, she did not like putting the headset on, so she kindly declined the invitation. After her, the fourth staff member came to try it, he was able to enter the scene, but after trying for the 10 minutes the experience lasted, he told me that he thoroughly enjoys the scenery. Unfortunately, his tinnitus was not letting him listen to the voice, so he couldn't properly follow the exercises. He runs the relaxation session, and he thought introducing something like this in one of the sessions would be interesting. In general, my impression was that this prototype was received well, most of them thought this would be a great idea for the DRC if it was implemented properly, and those who could follow the breathing meditation felt compelled to express their immersion and that wholesome feeling of mental calm after practising breathing meditation. Each of them had a different opinion on which scene made them feel better or more welcomed, nonetheless in every case, green space with blue space interventions was the favourites. At this point, it was clear to me what clips I wanted to use, and I was sure that the navigation process was a success. Interviewing them and showing this prototype also served me to prove to them the dimensions of the work I have been doing to catch their interest, so they would be inclined to provide further help in the future.

“Produce” Final study:

By the end of April 2018, the final prototype of the experience was ready. I contacted a DRC staff member who was my main contact at the centre with enough time to help me organise the

sessions and let me conduct the final studies for this project. During May and June (2019), I conducted the final lap of research; I divided it into three sessions with a total of 4 DRC service users each; I shortlisted the immersive clips of natural landscapes that to my perception resonated the most among the participants of my previous tests and allowed the participants to test the experience and let me know what they thought of the environments, the navigation, and other elements of the experience. My main goal, however, was to understand if there is a significant change in the self-perceived wellbeing experienced by the workshop participants.

The experience (see table 4), was delivered as an application featuring a home screen and three different scenarios that could be selected by using the rotational head tracking head-tracking capabilities of the headset, and each simulation would feature a therapeutic landscape in a 10 minutes long movie if the service user had any physical issues that did not allow for gaze-input-selection I would ask which movie the user wished to see and then I would play on the HMD the movie the user selected The methodology of the workshop is divided into five parts (See methodology section), recruiting this is normally done with help from staff members on the

Table 4 Produce Sample (Author, 2018)

day, during the session I started by briefing the participants on the ethics and the scope of the study, afterwards we had a semi-structured conversation.

In another group sessions, I had the sensation some of them were not able to communicate as much as they probably wanted because of their challenges; as a result, other participants would monopolize the conversation, so this time around, as a conversation starter, I used Visual aids embedded in the forms. I also explained these events to them to avoid confusion. Then, I moved to collect their feedback and enquire about their overall mood. Subsequently, I let them use the simulation to then finish with the debriefing by having another semi-structured conversation to ask them how their mood has changed and ask them to tell me how they were feeling again using the same visual aids. Because the participants seem to have a relationship of trust with the staff members, I had the help of the staff member as my cultural ambassador, helping explain and clarify so everyone would have equal understanding, and then help me collect feedback from the service users, each session ran for about one hour and a half.

Session one: (1st May 2019)

This was a morning session; the recruiting for this session was done on the day with the help of one of the staff members at the DRC, who is the senior officer at the centre and my main point of contact. I contacted her before I visited the centre, asking her to provide me with a calm space where to have the session; I was assigned the library. The library is a quiet space with convenient conditions in terms of ventilation and light to have a session like this one (see Fig.44).

Present in this session were me, a group leader staff member, three service users and one volunteer. I had not worked with all the participants in this session before, however they had used VR with a console provided by the DRC, so I knew they were not new to VR. They all present mobility issues due to limb weakness; all of them suffered strokes. This session was the first time I used the new HMD's. Those who had used the mobile HMDs noticed and were excited to try them. We followed the procedure by briefing them and explaining the study, then placing them into the simulation and then debriefing the participants.

Fig. 44 HMDs & Documentation ready to start the sessions (Author, 2019)

In the after part of the study, P3 felt compelled to share that she now was calmer and that it is interesting that she noticed how she was feeling just after she started the guided meditation and mentally scanned her body, and that she felt more focused to go back to her activities and more relaxed. Other participants reported that he was feeling “happy” rather than ok, and he mentioned that he was happy just to sit there and watch the sea wash away over the rocks and that he enjoyed this better than the PlayStation VR games where animals appear from the sides as he felt scared, while we all laughed I felt there was a feeling many had, and that his favourite scene was the sea one, another participant said he liked the view, and he said the hillside near the lake reminds him of his holidays with his family, he also said to feel more focused agreeing with the first participant. The last participant shared his thoughts, he was the only one who did not feel different afterwards, but he mentioned feeling amused with the experience, and he enjoyed it, especially the one with green elements as he liked the sound of the birds. At some point, we can see him in one of the images from the session trying to reach for something in the virtual world. From this, an idea came from this that would be interesting to have a VR cinema

session at the centre for those who enjoy VR. After the session was finished, they all left for lunch, or the buses provided from the DRC to their homes.

Session Two: (16 June 2019)

Before this session, I contacted the DRC staff member who helped me last time. She is another senior staff member at the centre, and she allowed me to come and do my study with the music group in the afternoon; at my arrival, there were five participants. However, an elderly lady was not able to participate due to her blindness. The remaining four all had experienced VR before and were happy to try the experience and provide feedback, and we waited after they all were settled to brief them and share the forms with them, as per this time, individuals were experiencing cognitive and physical conditions the staff member help me brief those who needed attention (see Fig.45 and 46). And just like before we went around the table talking about how we were feeling on the day using the visual aids to help communicate how their state of comfort (level of pain) and self-perceived mood state, the general feeling around the table was a state of just being “Ok” and maybe a bit sleepy after the lunch time, only **P3** was feeling stressed and tense.

Fig.45 Staff member assisting as a cultural ambassador **Fig. 46** User fitting his headset (Author, 2018)
(Author, 2018)

This time I empowered the staff member to lead the session, and I took a step back to prepare and get the participants ready for the visualization. They all watched the visualization, following

the instructions with no issues apart from headphones falling off a couple of times. Afterwards, in the second round of conversation, they expressed to feel more relaxed and focused, a continued with a comparison with the current experiences available at the DRC, **P2** said, “It’s like being on your own bubble”, the other users agreed that this would work very well as an addition of the relaxing group available at the centre because it allows you to be “in your own bubble” and relax, some comments on the table were around the lines of feeling lifted in spirit and happier. However, for **P3** this was not the case as she was still feeling stressed, she seemed to feel quite tense. Almost everyone’s favourite scene was the beach scene, because of the warm colours. After this session, the staff member helped me rotate the group with other participants she had contacted before my visit.

Session Three: (16 June 2019)

This session was the tightest in time, as some needed to go home at some point soon, so again after they all had been helped into the standard room, I explained to them the conditions and scope of the study, and the staff member helped me brief the service users as she is well acquainted with them.

In the briefing phase, the mood around the table looked tired but good, there were no problems during the VR experience, and after trying the experience, some participants (**P3** and **P4**) had a smile on their faces when taking off the headsets, to me this was a good sign. **P3** expressed satisfaction with feeling that within the VR headset, she was within her own space, cut off the world, and could relax and focus on how her body was feeling. **P4** had a similar experience where her mood was lifted, and she said partly it was because she could forget about her surroundings and follow the guidelines of the lady asking her to breathe. It was Robs second time, and he added that, interestingly, thanks to feeling the weight of the headset, he didn’t fall asleep, but instead stayed awake completing the breathing exercise; communicating with **P1** wasn’t easy, yet the staff member helped me gather written feedback from her. After that, it was the end of the day at the centre.

Fig. 47 Participants filling the forms (Author, 2018)

Fig. 48 Participants engaged in mindfulness (author, 2018)

After compiling the information of the workshops. I have understood that there was an instant increase in the sense of wellbeing and that there is an interest on behalf of staff members and the service user at the centre to use VR, not only for wellbeing but also for entertaining. While I think there is nothing wrong with experiences that can create emotions of fear and surprise for entertainment purposes, I would say that perhaps these are not for everybody, because as we had seen, these can impact the emotional state of the most more vulnerable service users. If the DRC decides to build a library of experiences, I believe that experiences like Produce could be valuable for their portfolio of simulations. Primarily because while there were some meditation experiences available on the Oculus store when I started the project. None of them featured Scottish scenery, and while white sandy beaches or exuberant tropical views can be beautiful to look at, I could see by the way they reminisced and shared the memories triggered by these spaces, that there was a sense of familiarity and ownership over these spaces, which made these special for them. There is clear evidence on the tabulation of the participants that there was an increase in the perceived wellbeing demonstrating the positive influence experiences as this one could have in the overall comfort of the community.

On a final note, I would say that during a competition to extend their portfolio of immersive experiences, *“Produce – Tuning into nature”* was selected to be included within the library of experiences offered to the service users at LOROS Hospice, reaffirming the importance of mindfulness immersive experiences for the service of those facing challenges (See Fig.49).

Fig. 49 This experience was selected as part of a selection of VR movies used for the service users at LOROS

5.1.4 Results and findings:

After my initial encounter, I understood that for VR to be accepted by the different stakeholders it should present content in affinity with the activities at the DRC. The first artifact produced was a mobile VR application, with set of immersive films, featuring natural landscapes of the west of Scotland, coupled with breathing guided meditation. This experience is based on attention restoration theory (ART) and "Aesthetic affective theory" (AAT) aiming to restore the viewers' directed attention and build resilience. To test this and to complement the participant observation, I implemented a conversational questionnaire and a form that aimed to measure the comfort or discomfort (See Fig. 50) and the "valence & arousal" (See Fig. 51) of the participants to help them gain the granularity of communication to convey how they were feeling by associating their cognition to images and structured words, as talking about how we feel can be a difficult task, these served as visual aid.

Fig. 50 Before & After comfort chart results after immersion (Author, 2021)

As we can see in the “Produce” – Comfort chart, where the discomfort represented in the Y axis, it goes from zero which is the most comfortable to 10 which is the most discomfort (Overall Mental or physical). Almost all participants (12) which are on the X axis, self-reported an immediate sense of increased comfort, meaning that while most of them at first (before) oscillated between 4-5 in the “I can manage” Bracket, it the (after) oscillated between 3 and 1 on the “Good” bracket, this was not the case for participant seven (7) who reported since the beginning to the end of the session to feel stressed and tense, in the case of participant 4, reported not to feeling particularly uncomfortable before the simulation and her answer did not change afterwards.

In the Valence and arousal chart (see Fig. 51) participants were explained the cardinal associations of the Valence (Pleasant axis) and arousal (Activation axis). As explained in the methodology section (See 3.5) this chart clearly delineates four sections of emotional expression, where depending on how close the words are to the axis or cardinals ends, the participants are more likely to agree with it. For example, if “Alert” and tense are both the highest activated mood

states (Arousal), yet “Alert” is towards the Positively valence (Pleasant) direction, where “Tense” goes towards the negative valence (Unpleasant).

Fig. 51 Emotional circumplex” Before and After” immersion chart result “Produce” simplifying Russell 1983 (Author, 2021)

Out of 14 participants, at the left side of the “Before” chart we can see that 3 participants expressed that they felt their current mood was better explained within the Unpleasant & high activation area, while other 4 expressed to be within the unpleasant & low activation area. 5 participants expressed they were within the Pleasant and low activation activated area, and no participants expressed to be within the pleasant and highly activated areas. In the right side of the same chart “After” section, we can see how most participants (10) response felt within the pleasantly moderate activation section. Some of them making a significant positive leap on their emotional state: this section is usually related to a mental state of being in “control”. Another 4 felt within the area of pleasant low activation which relates to relaxation, and only participant 7 was still felling stressed, making little improvement.

In chapter 6, I shall discuss the journey of creating the second VR experience, its results and then I shall compare the results and their meaning in chapter 7, the discussion and conclusion and final chapter.

Chapter 6: **Discovery**- Memory game

In the literature review (Chapter 2), I established the importance and place of play in the human condition. I also explained the narratives that allow play. Playworker Bob Hughes was an activist for play as a fundamental and essential part of human growth, created a categorization of play behaviours in his book *Playworker's Taxonomy of Play Types* (2002). In this book, he aimed to create a flexible identification of behaviours of children plays for development. In modernity, the lines between play and work have blurred, allowing adults to play more freely. These behaviours can also be identified in grownups, as (Heljakka, 2013) Sutton-Smith says, referring to how some psychologists embrace the idea of play mainly as a means for children to mature (Groos, 1901) (Vygotsky 1978). "If play is a preparation for maturity, then what are the mature doing when they play? - Are they preparing for death? Perhaps they are not preparing for anything." (Sutton Smith 1997, p. 47). Play an essential place in adults' healing processes. According to the book *Play Therapy with Adults* (Schaefer, 2002, pp. 1-10) therapy harnesses the power of play to allow adults to cultivate flexible and reflective conducts such as "creativity, Role Rehearsal, and mind/body integration" among others (ibid, p. 2) she says "Play can increase our self-esteem. It invites access to states of well-being and calm as well as silliness and joy. When relaxed in play, we often have an increased capacity for empathy and intimacy. Play is affirming" (ibid, p. 4). For examples related to the DRC, see the table below (pp. 140 – 144), adapting Hughes' definitions. These behaviour taxonomies have become widely accepted, partly because of their granularity, to identify playful behaviours, and they have become a reference on the planification of spaces, experiences, and time for play. After considering other similar classifications and inspired by Huizinga's idea that "Play" is a catalyst for community, I adapted this taxonomy to fit the DRC community like (Marsh et al., 2016), and I list below examples on how I have encountered play or playful activities at the DRC, identifying these sessions within Callois' principles of play. These play types are not isolated, and it might be that one might find elements of these mixed or overlapping in the sessions or groups organised by the DRC (as seen in Fig.32, See table 5).

Table 5 Hughes Adapted definition (Author, 2020)

Hughes adapted definition:	Examples of Play at the DRC:
<p>Communication play, uses words for name-calling, singing, and joke & storytelling, but it also uses gestures and body language to add meaning, using facial expressions, hand gestures such as clapping, groans and grunts, aiming to create a reaction and explore the impact, this is a form of communicating that the individual is on play mode.</p>	<p>Many groups fit this play behaviour at the DRC. For example, in the “Singing” group, the service users can choose together songs to sing and use percussion instruments or clapping as a way of making music. Other examples are the Quiz, creative writing</p>
<p>Imaginative Play refers to play based on reality but not for a realm. For example, pretending to be a tree or roar like a tiger is within the mimicry realm.</p>	<p>In the “Tai chi” group, there are movements designed to simulate the roots & branches of a tree, or the Bear & Looking Owl, and the 5 Elements of the Qi Gong practice, this could be an example of play “Role Therapy” at the DRC.</p>
<p>Locomotor Play refers to the use of our bodies to move; it can have llinx characteristics.</p>	<p>The “Dirty Feet” is a dance group meeting every week at the DRC. The service users and facilitators dance and explore what they can do with their body and push the boundaries of their mobility in a fun manner in here we can see mimicry and llinx combined.</p>
<p>The creative play focuses on expressing the self, with spontaneous creation, invention, and</p>	<p>The “Art” & “Craft” groups allow the service users to explore what can be done with an</p>

<p>experimentation. It can involve various materials and tools and go beyond arts and crafts, using exploration and curiosity.</p>	<p>array of materials. It goes yond what we understand as arts a craft because they are empowered to create their projects within a theme, giving free rein to creativity. Here we can see Agon's traits as the seeking to master the materials can lead to creation to demonstrate superiority.</p>
<p>The deep play has to do with the exploration of physical, mental, or emotional risks. This form of playful fear teaches the individual, especially figures of power, to understand, manage and overcome perceived risk. Examples of this could be wall-rock-climbing, truth or dare and confronting a bully.</p>	<p>I cannot say I have found this Play behaviour at the DRC, but the closest to this would be field trips to natural parks or boat rides as they can take some participants out of their comfort zone and give them gratification and a sense of adventure.</p>
<p>The dramatic play has mimicry elements; this is when the individual pretends to be part of an event where he or she was not present, for example, a historic event, a singer, or a television show, it enables the individual to express the self by experimenting with their identity, this behaviour is normally staged.</p>	<p>At the “Dirty Feet”, “Music” or “Singing” groups are the kind of groups where this is likely to happen. The main room has a massive stage where sometimes acting takes place. Other events such as important historic memorial events, Halloween or Christmas parties allow them to dress up to ratify and/or play with their identity.</p>

<p>Object Play; refers to the action of surveying objects with our eyes and hands, enjoying and understanding their shapes, colours, textures, and affordances. Creating a connection with new or unusual objects, or many known objects that we take for granted, can become more meaningful if approached within a flexible frame of mind, for example, arts, crafts, and baking, namely cardboard or wood scraps.</p>	<p>“Alternative health” is a group the users can interact with alternative healing items such as warm rocks, massage items etc. In the “Arts and crafts”, users can work with or wood pieces, paint, paper, and even recycled items to create pieces that then are exhibited at the DRC or the local museum, in the “Music” users can interact with musical instruments and movement groups are groups where this is likely to happen.</p>
<p>Exploratory play; has to do with figuring out information about an environment, artefact, or object; by entering in contact with it, the individual can evaluate the possibilities and particularities of the object, an artefact of environment, an example of this could be putting apart a bicycle, playing with building blocks, clay or woodwork.</p>	<p>The “Photography”, “Moviemakers” are groups where they typically organise visits to sites of interests such as museums, essential squares, or natural spaces to take pictures and make videos. The Gardening group allows service users to interact for leisure with seeds, plants and soil to plant and create gardens. I believe these activities enter this category.</p>
<p>Rough and tumble play involves body contact but not hurting somebody. But more like playful touching, tickling, and even dancing. It helps discover owns strengths and physical flexibility and interpersonal social codes of physical conduct (Hughes 2002). I have left out</p>	<p>In the “Woodwork” group, there are mostly or only men. This group has a very rough and tumble energy, where the service users pad each other in the back, or depending on how much they know each other, they can even hit or play-wrestle one another, there is name-</p>

<p>the behaviour of Recapitulative play, which has to do with the idea that children would spontaneously recap features of human evolutionary history through play, i.e., light fires, grow food, mock battles, this has been contested because of its implications about how these memories have been passed down through millennia, and to be honest it isn't relevant to the current discourse.</p>	<p>calling and a constant negotiation about who is the best woodworker.</p>
<p>Socio-Dramatic play: it's like dramatic play, but it doesn't emulate an interpersonal and highly domestic situation from the individual's reality; instead, it emulates experiences close to their everyday reality. For example, organising a meal, playing the house, faking a wedding, etc., these behaviours can sometimes be used for therapeutic motives to enact moments that elicited difficult emotions.</p>	<p>While I never visited the "Cooking" group to write ethnographies, I have been told what the group offers. I believe the cooking session emulates many of the home-cooking characteristics, as if preparing a home meal, therefore there are mimicry play elements in it.</p>
<p>Role Play has to do with the emulation of somebody else familiar with the individual's reality or an action, experimenting with one's identity with an emphasis on the role this person plays in the individual's life, which might be beneficial to understand somebody else's reality.</p>	<p>In the "Woodwork" session, there is some playful imitation of other identities (Mimicry). (Not of disabilities but more geared towards their accents or physical movements as a form of humour), In the woodwork, we can also see Agon as a form of demonstrating superiority in mastering the wood and tools.</p>

<p>Social play, this behaviour has to do with the play that abides by social rules, this behaviour allows for social engagement, and it's compelling on the creation and upkeeping of the sense of community, for example, building something together, creating a group, or singing together. It can feature elements of Ilya (competition) or not.</p>	<p>The “Debate”, “Quiz”, “Memory Skills”, & “Current affairs” groups are very similar. The facilitator divides the group into two or more parts and makes them listen to a piece of audio (i.e., Music, News) to then make a question, and then groups talk among themselves and take turns to answer, at the end of the session, the winning group it's the one with more answers, all these groups display Agon characteristics i.e. Group A Vs. Group B.</p>
<p>Fantasy play rearranges the worldview to one of imagination or unreality. This can be in real life with the example of people playing quidditch in a field, wearing scarfs and using brooms as they run around a field, or making as if the individual is casting a spell with a pen as if it was a wand, also in the age of videogames and ludic digital experiences this can be facilitated by playing videogames.</p>	<p>Halloween and Christmas events allow for this type of play through mimicry. Also, the realm of the video games can enter within this, for example, playing a game in the “iPad and tablets” session.</p>
<p>Mastery Play; has to do with controlling and modifying the natural environment, for example using your hands in building a sandcastle, digging holes, and planting. It</p>	<p>The “Gardening” & “Woodwork” session is within this category, as it allows them to work, gain skills and change the DRC with the pieces they have built or change the scenery by</p>

<p>expresses the individual's need to control and provides an understanding of the environment's allowances, making the individual obtain validation of their competence and abilities and build an emotional connection with the environment, deriving ownership and respect.</p>	<p>planting trees, flowers etc, in the central garden.</p>
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The sessions or activities are the backbones of the services of the DRC, and every user attends a session for a purpose, to learn something, meet friends, or enjoy the specific activity (See Fig. 52). Adapting Hughes' play taxonomy and using it to cross-compare how the activities at the DRC, we could see examples of what activities intentionally offer play, as there are sessions with it built on them, i.e., "Debate", "Quiz", "Memory Skills" & "Current affairs" or we can find those that feature it unintentionally. However, play finds a way to flourish, for example in the Woodwork session which is about constructing element from a template using wood. The session acts as a medium for these buddies to meet and emulate the rough and tumble play behaviour, leading to a playful interaction among the service users. As we can see, the concept of play is in different manners intentionally or not used to create community and wellbeing among their users, and it shows how important it is playing for the "independent living" concept that drives the mission statement at the DRC and at this point, were game has an intention, it becomes a serious affair.

Fig. 52 Service user playing a puzzle game (DRC, 2018) used with permission.

6.1 “Discovery”: the Creative & Production process:

The DRC workshops provided me with helpful insight into the DRC’s participants' response to VR media. This helped establish the foundations on the type of experiences I would be creating. I needed to find an option to encompass the DRC service users’ needs, which would empower them to access VR media in a fun and engaging manner while also generating Health and wellbeing. After finishing the user studies with “Produce”, I was ready to move into the creation of the following experience, always taking inspiration from the sessions offered at the DRC and the workshops during March 2018 after some drafting and consultation with the participants at the DRC I decided to draft two-game experiences, where the user could explore the world in 3D.

A) Second planned Experience / “Xanadu”: originated from the pilot study within one of the workshops (See 4.3). In this workshop, participants could play games were using their hands; they could see a virtual embodiment of their own hands on the screen while they played. Using a hand tracking device called “LEAP MOTION” LEAP MOTION which is a hand tracking device used to track hands and replicate such motions in the virtual world., this workshop aimed to understand the connection with Body ownership, immersion in the virtual world and the wellbeing elicited by a meaningful experience such as being able to interact intuitively using your hands instead of controllers.

I realised as well that many of my study participants were stroke survivors suffering from some form of cognitive challenge. Concentration games are a mental workout that keeps minds sharp and train memory (see the game concept “Discovery” in the next section). This game would also benefit those who need fine motor movement training as they will have to use their hands to interact with the board. I gathered inspiration for this idea from DRC groups like Memory Skills, where the service users play in teams and use their memory, they win points and the iPad & tablets session where they use their fingers to play training fine motor movement.

The player will use his/her hand to untap the tiles to match two of the figures, using hand tracking leap Motion attached to the headset. I believed this would make the experience more meaningful and engaging.

B) Third planned Experience / “Explore”: Explore is about mobility in the virtual world and creativity. Like the second experience originated from the Pilot Study, I realised during the workshops and the participants' feedback that they did not want only to be entertained but also wanted to create and explore.

Concerning my participants' population, they present many mobility challenges, and this is an opportunity to allow them to create and explore the virtual world without the constraints of their reality. To explore the VR space, they would use controllers and the headset to move around in 6DOF; they could also grow plants in certain virtual plant-beds and trees to modify their environment.

In a final thought about this, the importance of an artefact made to fit the needs and wishes of my participants with a creative process. Aiming to understand realities and create new knowledge on how immersive experiences can improve people's lives. This cannot be compared with other less personal and more general experiences ideated with the mass market in mind and which have not gone through a journey like this.

I had to be realistic in terms of timing for the completion of the PhD, and the time it would have taken me to test and have a polished version to have a final testing prototype, then there was a question of how to implement my ideas into the experience, because of hardware compatibility is given that unfortunately phones or mobile VR devices still run Android OS. For this reason, I decided to consult the DRC service users and staff members again to produce this artefact. To view the design document for these (see appendix D).

6.1.1 Discovery Game Concept:

Memory loss and cognitive challenges are common denominators among stroke survivors, and it is estimated that about one-third of the survivors will develop it. Older people are likely to suffer from it, too, with this condition can interfere with the normal functioning of the individual. The use of memory games has been linked with the flourishing of the mind allowing for better mental well-being.

The “Concentration” game genre branches out into a myriad of sub-genres, among the most popular sub-genres, are *Solitaire*, *Crosswords* and *Match-up*, also called *Memory Challenge*. These games provide a framework for individuals and groups to enhance their cognitive abilities. Among the benefits, we can find concentration improvement, visual memory training, the increment in short memory, attention to detail and vocabulary; this is very important given memory loss is a common denominator among many service users. Furthermore, the DRC features among their session’s memory challenges with a social element (See Hughes adapted chart p.142)

While observing the service users playing games on their tablets, I realised there was a mood improvement when they were interacting with visualisations that provided an instant visual input, and they also featured meaningful games elements such as stories and characters. Nonetheless, I also noticed that this game featured sounds that might be stressful or would feature unethically addictive game mechanics to incite the user to pay to keep playing, using reward techniques like those seen in a “Skinner box”. In addition, it also drains the directed attention of users, the purposeful creation of these addictive technological behaviours has been noted in (Light, Powell and Shklovski, 2017) and linked to loss of memory in (Hyrnsalmi, et al., 2020).

A common denominator in serious games is storytelling, as generally, people are prone to better understand and communicate concepts through it. Stories make knowledge more meaningful.

Because storytelling allows us to inhabit a character's point of view, and this can challenge our perspectives or help us learn by entering the flow state. Immersive media have changed storytelling to “Story experiencing”. Through the sense of “Presence”, we experience that sensation of being somewhere else when using a head-mounted display and somehow inhabiting somebody's reality. Going beyond the illusion of presence, VR is the only type of media where the user can experience embodiment illusion through hand movement with a handheld controller. The embodiment can evoke real feelings to the point of changing the way we think about others or our environment, and this is because VR, unlike any other media, closes the gap between knowledge and experience by the qualia of presence.

“**Discovery**” is inspired by two interactive SG’s prototypes produced within academic research settings one is “*Mystic Isle*” that focuses in cognitive and physical rehabilitation. In this game you can use your upper limbs to navigate the environment and find items. The scenery and items to find change depending where you are in the island (Ma, Proffitt and Skubic, 2018) and the second inspiration source is none the less the most academically cited serious game for pain management - “*Snow world*” (Hoffman, 2004) is a pain management game for burned patients where the player explores the artic, featuring whites and blue colours that aim to visually induce a cooling effect on the player and with easy to navigate environment with snow, penguins, mammoths and snow men, in this game you can throw snowballs to the animals present. Both *Mystic Isle* and *Snow World* are serious games that use distraction as a form of therapy, “*Snow world*” also shows that the sense of presence can have a strong effect bringing your attention in the virtual world, with a clear correlation between what is perceived in the virtual world and the pain experienced by the patients under wound care.

Exploring new environments rewards us with feelings of wellbeing (Heller et al. 2020), This also happens in VR when our attention is engrossed by the combination of cognitive, emotional, and spatial immersion. *Discovery* is a 3D game with a first-person view game invented by me, with a memory challenge component where the gamer virtually travels to different habitats and needs to find three items across these natural environments, In no order. This is a game with a theme

of “being away” and a mechanic of “memory and finding” to create cognitive immersion. Capitalising on the feeling of “extension” when humans see an environment that is open for exploration but bring a sense of structure, depth, and complexity. The game aims to engage players in a concentration activity with an added scope than entertainment, exploring these simulated habitats adding a layer of difficulty by asking the gamer to find items in these digital 3D worlds.

I wanted to understand how the depiction of different habitats would make them feel, to see if the results were like those in *Snow World (2004)*, to understand if this could cause enough positive distraction with the game-flow mechanic and the illusory transformation of location. Giving the viewer enough to do and see but not to cause too much stimulation. For this reason, while there are elements being animated, all animations are subtle, and to avoid any simulation sickness the navigation is linear or by teleporting, however in the final phase I also build a version where the user can move with a joystick simulating the motion of a wheelchair given them enough (See Table 6).

The player starts in an aquarium, an underwater scene inspired in the lost city of Atlantis, with the choice of 3 scenes (A, B, C, See Table 6). As per figure 53, the user can choose where to go. The cognitive difficulty of each scene has to do with the individual's perception. At the beginning of the creation process, I thought of making the game more complex, so the user would have to find the items in the specific order they appear on the main screen. However, I also wanted the user to feel more relaxed and enjoy the scenery because games are also about having fun and enjoyment; every scene has a theme habitat and set of items to find to increase re-playability. This scene features special effects such as the refraction of the light underwater, bubble sound and floating plankton to simulate undersea conditions. It also features a pop song

Table 6 Discovery Sample (Author, 2020)

that is not too stimulating in every scene and a little platform or path, making clear the boundaries of the navigation.

Fig. 53 User journey of the virtual theme park (Author, 2020)

Scene A: Inspired by the original “*snow world*” by Hoffman, this scene features a Polar habitat with igloos, sleighs, glaciers, northern lights, and the respective fauna. This icy background has items that need finding, recognisable for being orange numbered crates. While working at the DRC, I recognised that some users who could not speak would have tables with letters and numbers to point out on their wheelchairs and compose words to communicate, so I felt that using numbers was the best choice can be easily recognisable patterns. I thought the orange colour would be easier to spot in this gelid habitat, so I chose the colour for the crates. By matching the numbers in the screen that appeared initially, the player accumulates points to complete the scene. At the very end of the scene, it features an Eskimo settlement with artic wolves, a sledge, and igloos as a way of saying “You are home”, Differently from Snow World, I did not want the player to throw things at the animals, as I wanted for the players to cultivate a feeling of harmony towards all living things.

Scene B: Features a night-time forest. In the main menu, the player needs to read and memorise the names found. The challenge here is to match the name to the actual figurative element of the present fauna characters. I thought this would be a good challenge for those living with aphasia (Aphasia is the disability to assimilate and phrase language), which unfortunately can be present in stroke survivors. It also features a Stonehenge to add a mystical charm to this forest at the end of the scenes. It features animation such as moving clouds, blinking stars as the other scenes, but the music is mysterious, this environment has enough entertaining elements, we can find the wolf howling, and other sounds that make us believe we are surrounded by a mystic forest.

Scene C: The original name of “Mystic isle” was “Jewel Mine”. The player had to use his hands to find gems; this game is a call back to it. This scene is also inspired by the Serengeti, with a Kilimanjaro towering high in the background. It features the African Savanna habitat, where the player needs to find gems of different colours; the challenge here is to find the exact gem colours that match the same shapes seen at the beginning, the gems used to be Red, Green, and Blue; however, one of the participants suffered from colour blindness. As a result, I changed the green colour to white to facilitate this task to the colour-blind. In the end, the player arrives at a settlement with an African style palace. The background music has tribal drums, and there are ambient sounds to immerse the player into the scene, such as an elephant call, this scene was inspired in one of the travels of a service users (Dan, see appendix B)

There are, of course, machine power and resource constraints when developing mobile-based games in VR. While a mobile headset it's more versatile in terms of mobility, the 3D processing power leaves room for improvement. Especially when prototyping in an academic environment where the production skills are not the same as a Game studio, i.e., engineering skills and compression of files. This makes it challenging to reproduce special effects such as waterflow or reproduce very elaborated environments. The embodiment is limited to only a handheld controller this is common in VR games given the limitation of this type of mobile media, or I

hacked the headset to use a controlling stick to simulate the movement of an electric wheelchair by using a joystick; the view will be FPV (First Person-View) that can be used to view around but also to select the items. Every time a scene has been completed; the player rewards a fish for his/her aquarium.

Design: Virtual reality is an immersive interactive experience where the real world is left behind to be transported to a new environment of objects using computer-generated images, sounds or haptic feedback. The term Serious games can be defined as games designed for a goal other than for entertainment purposes. (D, J and JP. 2011), The intention behind “Discovery” is to create an item finding game using VR / 3D animated low-poly art style assets. This choice is due to the popularity of low poly elements as a well-established Art-Style in digital games. This style focuses on simplicity and flat colours, making it perfect for “Mobile” graphics real-time rendering without compromising. This is very important because this application needs to run smoothly and also have an appealing and engaging graphics style; other games found at DRC, including the same or similar style, are *Crossy Road* and *Monument Valley* two games I saw service users playing. This art style also brought the challenge of not being able to reproduce the look of the water waves correctly.

Audio in video games is essential. There is “non-stressful” Dynamic Audio, reacting to the user’s choices and the environment. Also, diegetic sounds referring to dialogue or authentic calls. For example, I have also included non-diegetic sound in the form of music. The sound will aim to trigger a sense of adventure and exploration. This experience was developed using UNITY. Developing first a paper prototype to ask the users at the centre for their opinion, and then I pushed the boundaries of what could be done with the headset. The low-poly models were purchased from a third party or the UNITY asset store and then be modified to the needs of the project if needed using the UNITY animation tools or 3D models rigging. I used other third-party assets such as audio clips or music for this prototype.

6.1.2 Discovery task-based usability test, DRC

In November 2019, I had a meeting with one of the staff members to test the initial version of the game and make sure this was appealing to the centre. She was optimistic about it but said that the game format should be linear rather than circular as some service users would have issues looking around. After working on the fixes, she proposed during January as part of the evolution of the project. I conducted two usability tests to understand what the participants thought about it and check if they could complete all the tasks.

The usability test was carried out at the DRC's Library. It is a space free of distractions and a calm atmosphere, and the study is divided into three parts. First, welcome users and help them settle down, read the documentation, or have a staff member read it for them. The second part is the actual usability test, where I firstly explain what the experience is about. We do a play-round explaining what needs to be done, to then ask them to perform a particular task, and then I start asking questions. Finally, in the third part, I ask the participants, how was the experience, and which one of the tasks was the most challenging; the following is a shortened version of the event. Before this session, as part of my preparation, I did test the experience with members of the VR laboratory I subscribe, none of them categorized themselves as having a significant physical impairment.

Session one morning 08 January 2020:

Both service users navigate the world with power chairs; after they settled into the library, I explained to them briefly the purpose of the study and allowed them to read the study information sheet, to then ask them to sign the consent form and only after they had signed, I explain the first part of the study.

The tasks were simple as I asked them to 1) access the first level, both did. 2) I asked them to look at the items that appeared and close the window, one of them was unable to do so or to

complete task 3) which was to look for the three items using the controller to navigate, they could navigate, however, one of them could not find the items because of his sight, the other participant was able to find the three items and go back to the main scene by looking at the yellow sphere at the end. In his final feedback, one of the users said he could hear the sound FX and the audio well; he also highlighted that the scenes were exciting and good looking. However, he also added that it would have been easier if I had used a visual aid to explain the game before using it *“it is difficult in the beginning, but once you get into it can be quite fun” (Player One)*. I took this feedback on board for the session after, where I would show participants what to do before they do it (see Fig. 54 & 55).

Fig. 54 The researcher briefing the participants (Author, 2020)

Fig. 55 Users using the simulation (Author, 2020)

Session Two afternoon 08 January 2020:

They all were able to complete task 1) to gaze and choose a scene. However, I noticed at this point that all of them entered the same scene (Forest). When going through the first play round, user two was confused with the buttons on the controller and quitted the application a few times by pressing the menu button. They had problems closing the window after memorising the items (in writing). She explained to me this is because she couldn't spot the "X" to close the window, so I closed it for her and then she was able to continue spotting all the animals as she couldn't hold the gaze for long enough due to her sight challenges (3 secs).

In this group, users 1& 3 had issues understanding what should they use to navigate or select (Controller & Gaze input, respectively). In the end, only participant 2 could complete all the task with no need for much help, and the other two participants performed 2 out of the three tasks well. Looking back at the results, two participants out of five could complete all the levels demonstrating the app is usable. One participant performed well considering her sight issues, and two participants could not complete the navigation tasks, maybe because, as seen in all participants, they all instinctively started pressing the buttons of the controller, which in some cases took them out to the main menu. So probably, work could be done in terms of making a version of the game that uses the controller ray to interact with the objects rather than using the “gaze” input module. Furthermore, the navigation of the spaces could be done as a straight-line rollercoaster.

Three of the users had issues with the window “X” to close the user interface, which is for two reasons. First, some could not conciliate the fact that by staring at it, you would be able to close it; Second, instinctively, all users started pressing buttons to see what happened, leading to different issues; this also can be resolved by locking the controller for 20 seconds so they can have time to read and memorise before they can press.

The two users who found this more challenging also had coordination problems and dexterity pressing the wrong button to navigate, so I would think about creating a rollercoaster-like motion to help them navigate the scene without using the controller (See Fig. 56).

Fig. 56 Participant using the small controller (Author, 2020)

Early prototype final test, session one morning 30 January 2020:

The first thing I noticed was that they had pictures of my experiments hanging on the wall; I felt at this moment that immersive VR became a part of the DRC culture (see Fig.57). I have many times seen how the DRC adds images that are meaningful to them to the walls, as a way of reminding interesting or happy moments. To me this suggest that possibly at this point, to then as a community immersive VR became an option to widen the participation of the service users.

Fig. 57 Pictures in the wall reminding my other sessions (Author, 2020)

This day we had 3 participants in the morning. I was accompanied by one DRC staff member and two service users; this user test was different. It had the purpose of gathering feedback from the service users and staff members at the DRC on a more developed prototype. In this prototype, audio-visual issues had been fixed, and everything should be running as expected. The user's tasks are the same as in the last session except that they need to complete as many scenes as possible in this session.

After reading with them the paperwork and facilitated the "mood" forms, as per the last sessions feedback, I managed to get the game running on a tv screen to explain the game

concept and what I wanted them to do. During the visualization, “User2” and “Staff” managed quite well to complete the scenes. Sometimes they smiled or emitted sounds of surprise and excitement while playing (see Fig. 58 and 59).

Fig. 58 Explaining the game to the user (Author,2020)

Fig. 59 User filling mood and comfort forms (Author,2020)

User1 was stuck in one scene, and he could not go forward; the controller was working correctly, but he could not feel it; unfortunately, I could not understand what the problem as it was working for me, then staff member trying to help him said that he might not be able to control it, because of his loss of finger sensitivity in his finger and the button being so discrete was hard for him to feel. He was right. He many times held the controller in the wrong way, as he couldn't feel the shape.

After the visualization I asked them what scene was their favourite and why as a way to open the conversation, User2 enjoyed the Africa scene because he could see all the animals giving him a sense of fun and he thought the one at the forest was the harder because he could not always find the right animal to match the word so he had to go back a couple of times, where Staff was feeling calm after seeing all the icy whites of the north pole scene, he thought the forest scene with the animals was the hardest because there is a white horse that looks like the grey horse but then the grey horse appeared and he realised the first white horse in the scene was actually the wrong one, User1 was feeling still frustrated and did let me know that this was

not working for him, and that he needed controllers that would fit his needs as this controller was not made for him, I remembered how some others struggled to navigate in the first user test. I think this was the reason why they struggled. These controllers were not made with accessibility in mind, the controllers were small, and the buttons were challenging to individuate with the touch. This was a barrier for the participant, he was feeling excluded, and this frustrated him. To me this was a glaring example, on how the design of an object creates a barrier that disables people in our societies, and why it is important to design bearing in mind the various needs and a range of disabilities (See Fig. 60 & 61).

Fig. 60 Participants playing (Author, 2020)

Fig. 61 User having issues with a controller (Author,2020)

This day, two of the participants managed to complete all the tasks and had an increase in their well-being. Unfortunately, due to the constraints of the controllers, User1 felt frustrated, and his mood worsened according to him because of the frustration elicited by not being able to use the controller.

Early prototype final test, session two-afternoon end January 2020:

During the afternoon, I had two female participants; one was a DRC staff member, which I will name Staff2, and the second a DRC service user, which I will name User3. None of them had used VR before. When both users arrived, User3 looked as if she was trying to be nice, but she looked sad. After asking her why, and filling the initial mood form, she told me she had a fight with her daughter and tearing up; she said she was upset because of that. I was concerned if she could

continue with the study given her mood state, so I asked her and the staff member if it was ok for them to try the meditation and mindfulness experience to breathe through her stress, both did. When debriefed, User3 said that she felt much better, and she seemed able to feel good again. She told me she enjoyed the beach simulation as the waves made her feel calm. Staff2 seemed relaxed and had a smile for a moment when I helped take the headset off. She said that she enjoyed the experience and enjoyed the river scene best as she could enjoy the sound of the flowing water and the slow movement of the trees.

After this, I briefed and helped “User3”, and “Staff2” put the headset on. During the simulation and after getting acquainted to the headset and the controller. Surprisingly, they had fewer issues understanding what they needed to do and took less time to complete the scenes. This might have been because they were only two participants, and I had more time for each. It did feel at the time easier because they were present, and with me explaining less, they did more, which leads me to believe that performing mediation before this experiment made them both feel more focused and ready to take information and open to enjoy the game (See Fig. 62).

Fig. 62 Service user enjoying a game (Author,2020)

During the debriefing of the study, their facial demeanour denoted enjoyment, and they both agreed that they had fun. When asking them which were their respective favourite scenes, User1 said that she enjoyed the African Savanah scene because it has more animated characters than others and had more to see from her perspective. She also found it more interesting, as it was more challenging for her to find the items the first time around. Staff 2 said she preferred the Mystic forest scene; it somehow reminded her of home (Eastern Europe) and that she found the African scene the hardest because the gems and colour shapes could be challenging to remember

to mix and match but that “overall, she liked all of them”, both thought that it would be interesting to include more videogames in the DRC activities because they have a form of interactivity that would bring a broader range of activities. As per the image below, the move improvement in terms of number didn’t change respect with to the initial mood chart; however, the second time around, they described their emotions differently.

After this session, I listened to my participants needs and adapted the prototype and hacked the headset to accept the input from the accessible controller (see fig. 63) to make this technology more accessible for people with disabilities, to control the game as if it was a power chair (Joystick). However, because of the challenges brought by the covid-19 pandemic, I could not use it and have a final user test of the finished prototype where I addressed all the feedback I was given on that day, In the next section I will present results and give an overview of the findings.

Fig. 63 HMD coupled with Accessible controllers (Author, 2020)

6.1.3 Results and findings:

The second artifact is a memory challenge interactive SGs that explores 3D environments aiming to bring the user to a flow state, using concentration via task immersion to distract from pain and ruminating thoughts (Discomfort). This creates a sense of wellbeing by exploring and discovering virtual world elements using the participants' directed attention: this experience has to do with gamification, play theories and the concept of "Flow".

The date represented here is from the penultimate user test, given that due to the worldwide pandemic in 2020, therefore this data is not from a prototype in its latest stage. On the comfort chart for "Discovery", shows how participants (2,3) experienced a betterment in terms of their comfort, however the first participant (1) suffered a decrease in his sense of comfort, while the rest of participants (4,5) remained stable.

As we can see in the before "Discovery" – Valence & Arousal charts, two participants (1,2) were in the unpleasant – deactivation area, where one participant (3) was in the highly activated – Pleasant area, and two participants were in the Low activation – Pleasant area (4,5) *, with the caveat that those participants experienced the immersive breathing meditation experience "Produce" before experiencing the memory challenge game "Discovery".

Fig. 64 "Before and After" comfort chart result "Discovery" (Author, 2021)

Following this in the after section of the chart, we can see first how one participant (1) switched from the unpleasant low activation area to a higher activation related to stress, this was due that after his stroke he suffered a loss of his sensory touch called hypoesthesia, while he was able to hold the controller, unfortunately he could not grip it properly as he was not able to sense the button having an impact in his navigation of the virtual world interrupting the sense of flow and not able to experience VR uninterrupted, this led to frustration. In the positive valence with low activation the chart shows that participant 3, who was a staff member moved from a state of alertness to feeling calm, he attributed this to the whites and blues of the arctic scene where he contemplated the aurora, in the area of higher arousal the chart displays that three participants (2, 4, 5) expressed to happy or excited, this is important because this tells me they entered in a state of Flow, and while the prototype was still in an experimental phase, the fact that they also seemed to enter in this state provides a certainty that games in VR could be used for emotional survival, as explained in Chapter Two.

Fig. 65 "Before and After" Valence / Arousal results "Discovery" (Author, 2021)

Because of the focus on the present moment and resilience over discomfort, I believe this experience has increased the self-perceived sense of health and wellbeing. To me these results suggest that there was an increase sense of wellbeing by producing a sense of comfort and providing mood improvement. In the next chapter I shall discuss the meaning behind these results.

Chapter 7: Discussion and Conclusions

Exploring virtual worlds with disabled communities is an exploratory and practice-based research project, whereby means of creating a space to interact with VR, my aim was to explore the relationship between health, wellbeing, and immersive VR within the Disability Resource Centre in Paisley. As far as I am aware, this is the first study that has explored the creation and implementation of immersive media with and within a disabled community for an extended period, creating artifacts that were the basis for knowledge creation. For the discussion section, I have chosen a narrative approach, given the predominance of exploratory, practice-based, and qualitative research methods employed, threading together results, findings, and other elements within the discussion.

As a designer my first task was to identify the stakeholders and the relationship among them. I did this in an exploratory manner identifying the social actors, their needs and wishes, recording my encounters within the Centre and their initial experiences with VR. Listening to the stories of the participants this heightened my empathy towards them. Given the community context at the DRC, I understood that to belong and being part of groups is meaningful to them, therefore as a designer and I needed to use participative forms of enquiry and methods that involved not only the service users, but also the group or session facilitators in line with community participatory approaches (PAR). The participants are part of a social cluster; I realized that being in workshops with other people close to them, made all feel more comfortable as they had people they liked and trusted beside them. This also helped me have cultural ambassadors in the form of group facilitators, who by example taught me about disabilities and how to work with groups comprised of people with disabilities. Little gestures and actions such as the way of facilitating somebody in and out of a wheelchair, served as example for me to develop an understanding the manners required when engaging in demos like placing and removing HMDs or creating the experiences. This in-person experience is important to me and integral part of my researcher identity. Today among my colleagues at the labs and other alumni, I am the only person I know from my circle of creative coders and designer colleagues who had this transformative experience with a disabled community as a catalyst. While there was a steep learning curve, today I can say that this episode

deeply informed me about the disability rights struggle and observing this generated an empathy that will always drive me to consider different needs and a wide range of disabilities when designing or producing any future product.

To me, the first stakeholder encounter was to explore the DRC as a place of community. As a physical space the DRC has multimodal physical spaces for activities to occur, (see chapter 4). These activities present themselves as daily or weekly activities creating health and wellbeing by satisfying the needs of the community. They are internally motivated with the purpose of building community, but they also provide meaning to the lives of the DRC's service users by existing in the broad interconnected spectrum of work, ritual, and play. In this context the second group was the one composed of staff members who oversee asserting the rules and schedules of the DRC and facilitate the services to users. Third were the main group of service users or service users, facing different physical challenges, likely accompanied by emotional and cognitive ones.

Given the current state-of-the-art, with rapidly reducing costs alongside increasing dissemination of the underlying technologies, immersive VR is becoming an increasingly affordable form of media. During my work at the DRC, the exploratory data collected through diaries of visits and user test sessions suggests that VR is a safe and effective media for the creation and implementation of experiences to promote health and wellbeing amongst disabled communities such as the DRC. However, to do so the needs, and preferences of the individual and collective needs to be taken into consideration.

7.2 Disabling barriers caused by VR Hardware

As part of my reflection regarding the barriers people with disabilities face when experiencing VR, I believe are as similarly seen in section 2.5.4, underscoring the need of the inclusion of people with disabilities in the process of creation of experiences made for everyone. About hardware and movement, VR rely in physical movement, which can be discouraging for players with motor movement disabilities. Current VR devices are made in a way that force people with

disabilities to comply with abled body expectations by turning their head and bodies in different angles to look around or reach for items. Furthermore, both controllers are normally needed to perform physically demanding range of arm motions, including the use of their fingers to reach buttons and triggers within the controllers, and then there is the weight of the headset that can be exhausting over time. This is problematic both for players with motor disabilities and those with chronic pain. Furthermore, the Current physical design of HMD's requires fine motor movement to set up the interpupillary distance and head strap, also there is no modular replacement headset lenses to adapt for glasses prescription, and fitting glasses within the headset can be uncomfortable, as many glasses might not properly fit. These are barriers that might require players to seek aid rather than empowering them on self-reliance and might deter them from using and enjoying VR.

7.3 Discussion of the meaning of the findings:

I have presented the results and overview of every intervention on their respective chapter (see chapter 5 and 6) the following is my interpretation of these findings. The offboarding notes of the "Produce" sessions suggest that it was meaningful for the participants to visit natural landscapes familiar to their locality (West of Scotland). Many of them also noted that these spaces reminded them of places they already knew or had visited with their families, meaning that these spaces acquired heightened significance by association with other spaces that were familiar to them, and positively remembered. In relation to the scenes, it was remarkable to see how most of the participants reported that the sea view was their favourite scene.

My interpretation of this finding was that some considered that the warmth of the sunset and the calm roll of the waves provided them with enough interesting input to focus, allowing them to concentrate on their breathing. The likeability of blue spaces water has been also noted by other authors in the "Healing Natural environments" section, however I noted that the green landscape was preferred by participants who in my impression were prone to be more anxious, probably because the movement of the leaves and greens (See Fig. 66). Unlike the sunset scene

where the water is very close, but the view gives a sense of security and predictability probably associated to the idea of prospect and refuge, discussed in the “Healing Natural environments” section. Looking at the “Produce” comfort chart, as explained above, the participants experienced an instant positive change in their comfort or pain resilience, which leads me to believe that the participants health and wellbeing was benefited from this instant change.

While both experiences cannot be fairly compared, as the second experience “Discovery” development was interrupted by the pandemic in early 2020, the comfort data suggest that this benefit, was not as substantial I believe this is because the sense of “Flow” that videogames produce and that makes the time pass by (Sometimes called Escapism or Hard Fascination), and immerse ourselves in the virtual world was truncated by the difficulties the participants faced when trying to manoeuvre the controllers, interrupting the flow sensation and creating a sense of frustration in some participants.

Fig. 66 Trossachs (Author, 2018)

If the circumplex model (Russell, 1992) is transposed in top of the mental state model (Csikszentmihalyi, 1997), this way transposed and compared; we can see that they are very similar in terms of how certain mental states correlate to certain emotions, because mental states and emotional states are intrinsically connected (See Fig 67).

In terms of what emotions fit the domain of certain mental states in relation to the experiences, we can see that in proportion the “Produce” activity trended towards the pleasant middle and low activation areas, while the “Discovery” responses trended to be more towards the highly

activated section, showing that these two contrasting types of media content elicit different mental states.

Fig. 67 Mental and emotional circumplexes model based on Csikszentmihalyi & Russell (Author, 2021)

The 'Produce' side shows how many of the participants moved into a zone where their mental state was one of relaxation, control, or flow. This is important because to me this indicates that the participants acknowledge that they have become more resilient and in control, but the zones of flow also correlate to focus and attention. With the already explained limitation of the experience called "Discovery", fig.67 shows how the emotion of most participants in this session fell in the highly activated and pleasant section, where two of the participants seemed to be in the flow area or close by, however I believe the one participant in the relaxation area might have found the game too easy for him. This suggests that if data could have been recorded from a final prototype. most participants' responses would have fallen within the Control, Flow, and Arousal areas, where they would have had enough to see and do to heighten the sense of escapism from their current reality. Since with the right controller or game form they would have been able to have an uninterrupted immersion experience and navigate the spaces and accomplish the tasks to the best of their abilities, giving them a sense of validation, in turn influencing their mood and sense of self reported wellbeing.

The meditation experience results are in line with the “healing natural environment” section of the theoretical framework, during the participant observation and the form responses we could appreciate that participants felt restored and close to the area of “control”, meaning that their perceived restorativeness (PR) was high. While there were other elements like the voice over guide, results show some elements of “soft fascination” elicited by the audio-visual experience, for example participants said that they felt as if being there as if “being away”. Another element was “extension”, participants felt there was enough happening without being totally engrossed, likewise the “compatibility” element was present meaning that participants felt comfortable in the chosen environment. This results also correlates to “place attachment” as some participants said to have visited some of these areas with their loved ones.

The game experience results were incomplete; however, the results demonstrate how different experiences can elicit different moods, Participants were vestiges of “Flow” while not many participants were in the areas of arousal and flow. This environment created curiosity eliciting first spatial immersion where participants were happy to explore them and even got frustrated because they couldn’t see more due to their challenges. A second element of game immersion was the Senso motoric was also observed, where participants were engrossed with the navigation and moving their heads around to find the missing elements, a third element the cognitive immersion where a participant went back to unlock the trophies this in turn leading to emotional investment.

7.4 Conclusion:

In the final section of this chapter, I will outline the main conclusion and implications of the study, however because of the limitations resulting from the 2019 - 2022 pandemic, some of the conclusions might be speculative in nature. These contributions inform the DRC. stakeholders or anyone who is a researcher or game designer interested in the deployment of immersive media in the form of experiences designed for and with disabled communities. During the first stage of this project, I explored the lives of the DRC community in an ethnographic manner. I conducted a pilot study of 12 participants across three workshops, testing different immersive experiences

to understand how VR. could be implemented within this centre. During the second stage, using a recursive method of testing and consultation with some DRC service users and staff, I co-created and developed a breathing meditation experience using natural Southern Scottish landscapes; this experience was tested with 14 participants using a before and after simulation method: this has to do with healing environments and soft fascination theories. In stage 3, using only digital elements, I experimented with testing the memory game experience until the worldwide pandemic interruption (2020). This application is related to gamification and play theories and was pre-tested with 5 participants using a before and after simulation method.

This project's first aim was to expand our understanding of immersion and the relationship of living with a physical disability in the 'real world' compared to the sense of agency in the 'virtual world'. Based on the results of the analysis of the first stage of ethnographies, it can be concluded that depending on the level of immersion, VR. experiences can constitute a source of surrogate experiences of real work experiences, helping bridge the gap knowledge and experiencing. The results indicate that meaningful responses to virtual scenarios can be elicited using VR.

The second aim was to further the objective comprehension of working with immersive media and interactive technologies: this aim was pursued under the framework of accessibility. The second and third stage results suggest that adaptive software and the modular inclusion of assistive hardware to suit disabilities are of prime importance when designing VR experiences and targeting people living with disabilities. The results of stages two and three indicate that the agency and immersion in the virtual world of potential users can be interfered by interactive limitations undercutting the immersion experience. Therefore, to create experiences for all, modularity and adaptability are needed to allow for meaningful and rich interactions. Furthermore, these should be prioritized within the highest importance when designing and developing immersive software and hardware for any audience.

The third aim of this project was to promote the advancement of co-creation, co-development with disabled communities. As explained in the methodologies section, using an iterative design

process of consultation under the participatory action research framework (PAR), involving both the DRC and the researcher. The feedback of the participants was gathered throughout the development process. This provided participants to sessions and workshops at the DRC and the researcher to engage in immersive media before and after experiencing the simulations. They were engaging in these scenarios, and then talking about it changed how they would simply experience any media by its ends. Because adding language to articulate what the individual just experienced and listening to the experiences of their interlocutors helps calibrate through social thinking their own assimilation of such immersion, in turn, this creates a conversation with the researcher who is an expert on this topic and enriches the DRC participants with vocabulary, knowledge, and their perception of these VR encounters but also the researcher experience of this episodes augments his first-hand experience regarding the life of and complexities of working with this community or other similar institutions.

Finally, the fourth aim was to create new VR prototype experiences as part of the care regime and sessions at the DRC. The contribution in terms of artefacts and their creative process can be seen in the fieldwork chapters.

Immersive VR is becoming an increasingly affordable form of media, and during my work at the DRC, the exploratory data collected through diaries of visits and user test sessions suggests VR. My findings suggest that it can be a safe and effective media for creating and implementing experiences to promote health and well-being in disabled communities such as the DRC. However, to do so, the needs and preferences of the individual and collective need to be taken into consideration. Therefore, the experiences of users themselves should inhabit this negotiated space of work, play, and ritual to hold meaning for this community.

R.Q. 1: What is the relationship between the virtual agency afforded by immersive technologies and the experience and restricted agency of living with a disability?

During the first stage of the research, participants of the pilot studies interacted with different VR activities, after observing the participants, I can conclude that the relationship of the participants to VR. come from three viewpoints which are the following “Fascination”, “Wellbeing” and “Choice”.

- The findings of the first stage suggested participants had a relationship of hard fascination entering in a state of flow, when their attention was engrossed by the virtual transportation to ‘real’ spaces or engaged in rich interactions with different 3D worlds, serving as meaningful and stimulating surrogates to real live experiences beyond simple entertainment.
- Participants consider VR a tool capable of creating health and wellbeing, this was illustrated through the virtual translocation of the self to natural landscapes where to practice mindful restorative experiences, where most participants self-reported an increased sense of wellbeing and comfort.
- The participant observation suggests that stakeholders favoured immersive media implementations as part of the DRC during all stages. activities, providing choice and generating a narrative of progress.

This research clearly illustrates that there are benefits within the agency afforded by immersive technologies. However, to understand this better, participants need to experience avatar embodiment, which is the final illusion of VR. This raises the question of what the results in the perception of the self would be if they would engage in *Second Life*, or other more modern games such as *Fortnite* or other Massively Multiplayer Online Games (MMOG). Creating an avatar and richly interacting in everyday tasks and socialising through technology could allow them to interact with immersive media on their own terms, this way creating a world where the gap between the able bodied and disabled is closed by providing assistive technology; this in itself opens an interesting line for future enquiry.

R.Q. 2: What are the cultural benefits derived from the insertion of VR in this community?

The culture of the community was explored during the fieldwork chapters, through ethnographic methods, in stage one we established that VR helped provide a new perspective to the participants not only knowledge related to VR but also the content could provide knowledge and surrogate experiences, however as culture is ever fluctuating to draw clear references to it can be challenging in an exploratory study such as this, yet a summary of the cultural benefits observed are the following:

- Stage two findings suggest that knowing about V.R. and experiencing it, provided service users and staff members cultural capital to decide prospective non-medical treatment and services provided within the DRC. in the future.
- Humans have a relationship of virtuality with images, through the conversation and artifacts created within this research, Immersive media entered the imagination of the participants where they demonstrated ownership and interest by decorating the computing room with images of our VR workshops, this infers that any future VR interventions would be met with ease of adoption.

R.Q. 3: How could immersive media be integrated as part of the services disabled communities provide?

During the exploration of the activities in stage one, users engaged with a selection of experiences, during this exploration the results suggest that immersive experiences should be in principle restorative or edifying, and observe mechanics that oscillate between work, play and ritual. Other practical implications apply:

- Phase one exploration found that staff members oversee preparing activities and keeping them interesting they require simplicity and ease of use. It's important that these immersive media interventions provide affordances to accommodate these needs and the challenges service users face.
- In an ocular-centric era, other visually impaired service users might be failing to benefit from experiencing VR, service users facing these challenges cannot use a H.M.D. Instead, they might appreciate auditory experiences accompanied with haptic feedback.
- To create and cultivate a culture where VR can flourish it should be promoted by a staff member who has experience in care and has worked with VR media. This person should be empowered to be both a promoter and a gatekeeper that feels confident in the use of this media.

R.Q. 3.a: What creative and production processes are behind creating an immersive experience tailored for a service centre such as the DRC.?

At all stages, the project used an agile design and implementation process under a user-centric design method inspired in the motto "nothing with about us without us". This was combined with exploratory methodologies of co-creation and co-production with the users (staff and service users) and drawing relationship with their environment (DRC). I can conclude that these experiences are better designed alongside the target audiences to ensure that this process retain at its core theirs needs and wishes, this logic can be also better explained in the following points.

- Co-creation and co-production methods will ensure that the community will be more digitally aware, confident, and empowered.

- The community will exercise their agency under the service user care model of disability, advancing their agenda from consumers to agents of change and co-creators of media directed to them.
- These methods would also ensure a mutual benefit in this interaction by strengthening the bond between the community, academics and artists or technologists interested in social care.

7.4.1 Key contributions:

This thesis makes four contributions to knowledge in the form of advances to the conversation of the human living with a disability and his/her interactions with interactive media. Firstly, in line with the service user model of disability, which is the model driving operations at the DRC, this thesis provides empirical evidence, augmenting for the implementation of immersive media within disabled communities as in the form of activities to promote health and wellbeing, demonstrating that when correctly implemented VR is not only a safe but also effective media for such communities, this way creating a precedent for inclusive immersive media.

Secondly, this research illustrates that through the virtual translation of location, immersion can be achieved by physically disabled individuals. This can be done by adapting state of the art equipment to their needs. Demonstrating that using this new digital avenue, experiences in Virtual Reality can have a meaningful impact in people's moods and act as surrogate experiences to real ones.

Thirdly, in line with human rights model of disability, the metaverse offers potential as an increasingly prevalent form of media that will encompass 3D worlds and the internet, likely becoming a 'second life' for many. This thesis makes a case for the plurality in the human experience and adds weight to the importance of accessibility in the form of adaptable hardware and software for the disabled to access – and design, co-create and inhabit - virtual worlds.

Finally, this thesis contributes to the conversation of co-creation and co-development of interactive media for disabled people by empowering a disabled community to move from consumers to co-creator and co-developers proposing that the best way to create media for this market is to implement adaptive methods of enquiry and a reiterative form of participatory action research that focuses on studying all stakeholders and giving them a voice, valuing their life experience. The benefits of this are aligned with the social model of disability and the simulations add a layer of playfulness, where the service users are participants in the study rather than test subjects on the exploration of immersive media as an enhancer of health & wellbeing, being this last the major contribution of this thesis, as by including the perspective of historically marginalised groups we might be set to unveil benefits for everyone.

7.4.2 Limitations of the study:

I. Participant recruiting and sample profile:

The DRC is a place with very structured times for their activities and sessions. Recruiting was done by staff members on the day. This meant that the pool of service users to take participants from was reduced to the quantity of service users that had sessions on the chosen day and time (Morning / Afternoon), and this also meant that for mobility reasons, I could not invite anyone who would not be normally present on that predetermined day / time session, and in case a participant had expressed the intention to participate, I had to try to schedule my visit on that day and time. This limited the quantity of eligible participants for the studies meaning that I would need to contact the DRC more frequently or establish a rapport with more staff members, to allow me to come to their sessions and interrupt what they were working on to do my research.

The population sample had reached a sizeable percentage of service users overall, given than more than ten percent of the current population assisting the centre participated in the last study

of “Produce” (14) and the prototyping feedback session for “Discovery” (5). However, if we look at the types of different impairments present, it is noticeable that there are not participants facing visual challenges, and while the DRC is mainly a physical disabilities resource centre, they also cater for adult with other sensory impairments like vision and hearing. Most participants I consulted of the said impairment type did not wish to participate given that they did not want to wear the HMD, in the few cases these participants wished to participate given their curiosity and sometimes the limited explanation provided to them by the recruiter, I gently explained that because of the study being made with VR headset they were more likely to experience motion sickness, therefore I wouldn’t recommend it.

II. Equipment & resources:

Access to HMD headsets to conduct experiments with bigger groups were an issue during circa the first year and a half, given that I had at my disposal only two phone-based headsets. This made it difficult to have larger groups without the response of some participants being affected by social thinking, meaning that their response would be affected by their perception of other participants experiences, also phone-based HMD had less pixels and colour vividity. - This influenced the sense of immersion.

Because of the study depending on a head mounted display (HMD) I could not include participants with impaired vision in the study. this also was an issue that had to do with economical resources because this should have been a study where all disability existent at the DRC could have been covered in some shape or form, as explained in the introductory section VR comprise different types of immersive media, including 3D audio, this could have been solved with access to 3D audio headphones.

Humans can perceive depth with their stereoscopic vision, the 360 videos were recorded with a 360 monoscopic camera that in turn when participants would put their headset on would feed every eye with the same vision angle, instead of feeding every eye with the angle they would have been able to perceive if they were there. This had an impact on the sense of immersion as

the depth of field fell short. A stereoscopic camera would have created a more immersive experience.

Creating the artifact and finishing them to a point where the prototypes are usable requires different skills, and the skills one person can master are limited, therefore the shape of what can be created with this experience is limited to the skills of the artist, designer, or technologist.

III. Methods:

Methods such as participant observation, “before and after” forms and ethnographic recording of the events, were helpful because they allowed me to gather my thoughts about the community, their wishes, and needs. However, because I was conducting the workshops within the DRC, and the places as the DRC operate under the service user model where under my perception any equipment or language coming from an external guest alluding to the medical model is disfavoured, for this reason I refrained from using data gathering techniques such as heart rate sensors or anything similar; also because during workshops resources and equipment had to be transported, organised, and administered by me, creating a limitation in terms of the bandwidth of directed attention, I had as a researcher during the workshops, therefore experiments had to be as simple as possible. Laboratory studies might be easier to implement given the control of the setting, but participants would not feel in their element and in my experience, participants of co-production processes will collaborate only when the effort is not bigger than the perceived reward. This also means that being asked to perform a study somewhere else for example in a lab might be perceived as *experimented on* rather than *realising a study with them*, creating a disparity, and heightening the trust gap between researcher and the population, creating barriers to the authentic production of knowledge (See 3.1.3).

While during the workshops there was participant observation, self-reporting was the main method used to record for their overall comfort and mood of the participants. This means that participants’ answers could have been biased by social thinking, meaning that their responses were in line with the group.

IV. Timing

Because the iterative process of the artifact creation, I had to allow some time in between testing sessions for user fatigue, as that at times I experience diminishing returns as I kept resorting to the users that were most likely to participate. Moreover, because I was a guest within the DRC and the participants face different challenges, I had to take in consideration variables such as bus arrival times, toilet breaks etc diminishing the quantity and quality of actual contact time with the participants.

The COVID -19 pandemic had a significant impact on the completion of the thesis, cutting short the last round of studies, making my conclusions on regards of the memory videogame more speculative. To mitigate this, I reflected on possible scenarios and actions to these outcomes (See appendix F), ultimately to move forward, I opted to have a last session online with two of my participants and one staff member. In this session the scope was to ask them for final thoughts on the experiences, thank them, and say goodbye.

The pandemic also had an effect in the access to literary resources not available to me in the digital form.

V. The Researcher

The researcher was raised in a body-ableist society, therefore at the beginning of this research he was unaware that he understood disability under the medical and functional models, and he wasn't aware of the rich history and struggle disabled rights movement and the social model.

7.4.3 Recommendations:

At the beginning of the conclusion, I stated that this thesis had implications for stakeholders, academics or researchers who are also content creators, interested in the deployment of immersive experiences within disabled communities. Within the recommendation section I will address practical implications for the stakeholders and in the 'future work' section I will address

the other interested parts. Immersive technologies are becoming an ever more accessible form of media, in terms of user adoption and economic affordability. However, issues remain around the deployment of these specifically addressing the needs of disabled communities, where depending on their challenges disabled people still require software and hardware compatible to their needs. As a result, I would like to make the following suggestions:

- I. These software and hardware implementations need experienced staff members to teach the use and promote the benefits of this. The DRC or other similar institutions in Renfrewshire might take advantage of a shared resident artist and technologists for this purpose.
- II. The natural landscapes and mindfulness experiences workshops counted with the attendance of more than 10% of the population. Over 90% of this population expressed that they received a boost in their comfort therefore an increase in their overall perceived wellbeing. One of the participants went as far to say that he preferred this rather than the “relaxation” sessions on Fridays (see appendix A). This clearly illustrates that there is a place for the inclusion of VR as means of health and wellbeing.
- III. The inclusion could be systematically done by proposing different types of meditation experiences to users, mindfulness exercise such as breathing and muscle, but also having a wide library of different natural landscapes or natural soundscapes (for those with visual challenges) could be used for the illusory transformation of location.
- IV. People who had strokes make up a large part of the disabled population at the DRC. These individuals could make use of serious games as a fun therapeutic way to re-learn everyday activities i.e., cutting tomatoes, gardening, ironing, putting boxes away, etc.
- V. The pandemic has heightened the challenges disabled people face to socialise and participate in activities. As shown in the literary framework rich interaction is possible and

social activities such as singing, dancing and tai-chi could be incorporated into virtual meetings with other participants given that all can have access to a space in the metaverse. This could be explored even further with a metaverse space for disabled people where they could socialize and find strength in numbers without the constraints and implications of commuting or overcoming physical world barriers.

- VI. Abiding to the previous recommendation, surveying different digital outlets I realised there are many experiences that fall short in terms of providing sound accessibility for the disabled. This needs to change; a solution could be to partner with other care institutions within this common goal and in turn partner with universities for future prototyping and creation of knowledge, as there is a value in accessible design that interest us all in a society where we all will age and become less able.

- VII. In General, current VR devices always focus on tracking upper limbs and the use of two controllers and standing or seated positions. Favouring nonstationary experiences and games. This could be made better by creating surrogate adaptations to controllers to make them accessible for people with different disabilities. Allowing for the mapping of already existing accessible controllers and a lying-in bed option.

7.4.4 Further work

This investigation has called to attention different points of reflection to extend the conversation revolving around immersive media, wellbeing, and disabled communities. Firstly, as shown in the gaps and research opportunities section, there is only a modest amount of research on the beneficial effects of avatar embodiment in immersive media. Because embodiment is immersive VR's final illusion, it is challenging to speak of the real affordances of VR agency without inhabiting a digital body. To address this where disabled individuals can construct their avatar and interact in everyday activities adapting controllers and sensors to their bodies, as mentioned by Lanier (see page 80), avatar embodiment can elicit "homuncular flexibility" making it possible that somebody could control an avatar in inventive manners using accessible technologies. This raises interesting new lines of enquiry, for example: What is the relationship between the disabled body

and the virtual body? Or What are the aesthetic and meanings of customizable avatars created by disabled people?, Could social interactions in second life be as meaningful as those afforded by “real life”? What could be the therapeutic effects of everyday tasks in immersive VR?

Secondly, my results suggest that there is a health link between the meditative contemplation of natural environments and attention recovery. This opens a line of enquiry that could be explored further with immersive media. As in the theoretical framework, there is enough evidence that natural landscapes and meditation could be used as a form of therapy, but what would be more beneficial, to practice it at home alone or practice it as part of a DRC activity where participants could discuss their experiences? For better understanding of this phenomena, as a first step I would recruit at least 24 participants from the DRC. I would provide them with library of mixed – blue and Green Scottish natural landscapes or 3D soundscapes depending on their disability. I would then divide the groups into two, one group would be the meditation at home group and the second the meditation at the DRC group. For this I would provide each home participant first with a HMD or 3D headphones, either hardware would be set up with the experiences, and instruction to meditate. Second, they will be also provided with a note taking device. They will be instructed to use a methodology where they would record in a before and after manner their emotional state as detailed as possible, with the help of a carer if needed. They would need to complete the already mentioned “Before / After” methodology where the simulation experience lasts 10 minutes of immersive mindfulness every day for 8 weeks. Same tasks would be required from the DRC group, with the difference that they will get to talk to one another before and after the simulation. Then I would undertake participatory workshops with 6 people, each commenting on their own experiences and reporting on what they believe it would be the best practice for the DRC.

Another version of this exercise could be simply to implement it with one group of 10% of the DRC population. in a before and after manner such as this thesis methodology but would add finger or wrist sensor to gather data on their pulse and then gather data related to their heartbeat and triangulate results.

Thirdly, the results of the ethnographic encounters suggest that the experiences provided rich interaction with the virtual worlds. If creativity is the power to pinpoint ideas and ideate, this opens a venue for the exploration of the power of immersive media to stimulate creativity. In turn this could be also studied to add to knowledge and understand if the generation of creativity within VR can induce to a sense of wellbeing.

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List of Figures:

Fig. 1 The “Rave-Glove” prototype of a musical toy for therapy, (Author, 2016).	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig. 2 I.C.F. Disability Scheme (WHO, 2018).....	34
Fig. 3 Abstract representation of healing environments discussion domain 1, (Author, 2020)	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig. 4 Abstract representation of Healing environments discussion domain 2 (Author, 2020)	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig. 5 Clouds provide us with self-similarity patterns, this is a non-engrossing distraction that helps to restore attention through contemplation (Author, 2021)	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig. 6 Abstract representation of Healing environments discussion domain 3, (Author, 2020)	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig 7 Abstract representation of healing environments discussion domain 4, (Author, 2020)	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig. 8 Overview of the domain of healing environments within (Author, 2020) ..	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig 9. Children playing mancala (Furet, C., 2019)	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig. 10 Spacewar game MIT (cc 2012)	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig. 11 LIFE 1970 (cc 2012)	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig. 12 Caillois’s psychological attitudes and principles of games (ebrary.net, 2014)	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig 13 <i>Villa dei Misteri</i> - Pompei (Pagani, 2019)	76
Fig 14 <i>The Cave Automatic Virtual Environment</i> (Davepape, 2001).....	76
Fig. 15: <i>Trompe-l’oeil mural metro</i> , Morelos, Mex., Mexico (CC, John Pugh 2016)	77
Fig. 16. <i>Battle of Sedan immersive mural</i> (Werner, 1883)	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig. 17 Action Research Cycle, interpreted by author (2020).....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig. 18 Based on Skains, Practitioner model of cognition"2016 (Author,2019) ...	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig. 19 User-centred SLDC, interpreted by author (2019)	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig. 20 Valence & Arousal chart (Russell, 1980) interpreted by (Author, 2019) ...	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig. 21 Emoji Pain/comfort scale, (Mixing sources interpreted by Author, 2019)	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig. 22 Persona Archetype, Author (2018)	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig. 23 Disability resource centre in Paisley, Renfrewshire Council, 2017 Used with permission.	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig. 24: Weekly schedule at the DRC (Author, 2017).....	129
Fig. 25 First day at the DRC (Author, 2018)	130
Fig. 26 Tweet exchange with a DRC service user (Author, 2018)	134
Fig. 27 Man in awe virtually seeing tigers up-close (Author, 2018)	140
Fig. 28 Man watching Documentary VR (Author, 2018).....	141
Fig. 29 Woman Playing with a Hand tracking sensor, were she plucked the petals of a flower using fine motor movement (Author, 2018)	Error! Bookmark not defined.

Fig. 30 Man drawing a home virtually (Author, 2019).....	142
Fig. 31 DRC members perform at a commemorative Ceremony (Author, 2018).....	151
Fig. 32 Author helping prepare plant beds (Author, 2018)	152
Fig. 33 Tuscan Hills equirectangular image, used in prototype as example of green space (Author, 2018).....	156
Fig. 34 "Produce" interactive controller prototype (Author 2018)	159
Fig. 35 User journey by way of storyboard (Author,2018)	162
Fig. 36 HMDs & Documentation ready to start the sessions (Author, 2019)	166
Fig.37 Staff member assisting as a cultural ambassador (Author, 2018)	167
Fig. 38 User fitting his headset (Author, 2018).....	167
Fig. 39 Participants filling the forms (Author, 2018).....	169
Fig. 40 Participants engaged in mindfulness (author, 2018)	169
Fig. 41 Service user playing a puzzle game (DRC, 2018) used with permission.	180
Fig 42 User journey of the virtual theme park (Author, 2020)	186
Fig. 43 The researcher briefing the participants (Author, 2020)	190
Fig. 44 Users using the simulation (Author, 2020)	190
Fig 45 Participant observation (Author, 2020)	191
Fig. 46 Pictures in the wall reminding my other sessions (Authors, 2020)	192
Fig 47 Explaining the game to the user (Author,2020)	193
Fig 48 User filling mood and comfort forms (Author,2020)	193
Fig 49 Participants playing (Author, 2020)	194
Fig 50 User having issues with a controller (Author,2020).....	194
Fig 51 Service user enjoying a game (Author,2020)	195
Fig.52 HMD coupled with Accessible controller (Author, 2020)	Error! Bookmark not defined.
Fig. 53 Before & After comfort chart results after immersion (Author, 2021).....	171
Fig. 54 Emotional circumplex" Before and After" immersion chart result "Produce" simplifying Russell 1983 (Author, 2021).....	172
Figure 55 "Before and After" comfort chart result "Discovery" (Author, 2021)	198
Fig. 56 "Before and After" Valence / Arousal results "Discovery" (Author, 2021)	199
Figure 57 Trossachs (Author, 2018)	203
Figure 58 Mental and emotional circumplexes model based on Csikszentnialy & Russell (Author, 2021).....	Error! Bookmark not defined.

List of Tables:

Table 1 - Demographics:	144
Table 2 - Observations on stakeholders (Authors, 2020)	148
Table 3 – QR Code Produce.....	129
Table 4 – QR Code Discovery	147

Appendices:

- A. Ethnographies
- B. Participants and Personas
- C. Example material used in workshops
- D. Original Ideas of the experiences
- E. History of Games
- F. Lockdown test scenarios

A) Ethnographies:

Preface:

The following is a written report summarising my field observations and experiences deriving from my visits to the disability resource centre (DRC) in Paisley, within a realistic ethnographic writing approach to inform my research. The disability resource centre is a daytime service place providing services for physically disabled and sensory impaired people living in the Renfrewshire area.

The centre aims to promote independent living through various leisure, social, educational, employment activities and services. The principal way the centre achieves this is through the classes or session to provide through with this framework social interaction, among the classes provided by the centre we find Arts, Tai chi, Yoga, Knitting, Computing, and swimming among many others.

The centre has a range of specialist accessible facilities including a kitchen, library, and club room. Surrounded by a garden, this building is located just at the outside of Paisley town centre. The centre counts with many specialised care professionals and have among its ranks Volunteers that attend the centre as part of their learning or work experience. I came to the disability resource centre with the idea of becoming part of the community and understood what the needs, wishes and social interaction among the attendees and staff members were.

Methodology:

I visited as many groups as possible, aiming to be perceived as a helper or a participant, getting myself involved in the community. Visiting at intervals a morning group and an afternoon group, in this initial phase of the study, to get acquainted with one another and create trust. This way I would be able to hopefully be able to use this information to develop software and immersive experiences for this community. Names of Participants and Staff have been changed.

15th November 2017 - Art class & photography group:

The first day at the centre, I was introduced to the whole group by our facilitator Peter, he also explained a bit about my research. The scope of this class or group is to recreate an animal out of wood pieces, glue them and paint them, the participants of this group sit around one big, squared table minding their piece they wish to create, there are an instructor and one or two social care helpers to lend a hand.

Individually everyone chooses the pieces of wood or recyclable materials he or she wishes to use for his or her creations, pick up brushes from the shelves around the room. They also wear aprons and have paint mixers and brushes at hand.

The atmosphere in the art class was very relaxed, and the individuals displayed friendly behaviour towards each other, and the staff members aid them with any task.

Beside me sat Cara, she looked to be in her late 50's, and as she told me she was born has lived in Renfrew area all her life. Since the moment I sat down she wanted to talk to me, she asked me what I wanted to build, and I told her I wanted to build an elephant. – The facilitator told me as I was new that day, that I could take materials from the box-pile at the centre of the table.

When I started looking up for wood pieces in the materials box at the centre of the table, she seemed ready to start, she was wearing an apron and seemed friendly, and extremely interested in helping me find what pieces could help me to build the elephant. Also, she gave an apron and asked me not to steal hers because somebody already did once. – I could tell she was using humour to make me feel at my ease, but it was true.

While I was gluing the elephant parts, she told me her story, about how she had suffered a stroke, and as a result, she was left with aphasia, she also handed me a card where it explains that and how she struggles to write and speak when she is nervous, she seemed keen on sharing her story. Cara was trying to help me so much that one of the carers noticed and asked her to please continue with her work. She did, however, she looked at me and smiled while going back to her seat.

After this class the same morning, I was invited to join for the second hour the Photography class whereas a group the class was creating a website page for a past event and choosing what pictures to add to the albums of the DRC Facebook page. All of us seated in front of a

big computer screen, and the moderator of the group oversaw the mouse and keyboard control. I sat in one of the chairs that circled around the computer but were further back, as everyone aimed for the chairs closer to the screen. The atmosphere was happy and relaxed, they were delighted to look at past pictures of themselves in past events and reminisce about those moments, it was delightful to see how they were laughing about themselves, or acknowledging how well dressed, or funny they were in these pictures. Everyone was making comments on how it could be made better. To me it seemed that session made them feel as a team of photographers, it made them feel productive. The session finished on a positive note as they managed to finish the Facebook page before going for lunch.

16th November 2017 - Singing group:

This class happened in the morning in the main hall of the centre; it had two female helpers, the class teacher who was a young female, three female attendees aged 50+ and three male attendees aged 40+.

The class is structured as follows. The chairs are organised in a circle allowing some space among them, everyone seats in the chairs along the circle, and the singing teacher at the beginning welcome everyone, chooses a song and everybody with their own "songs book" look up the song and sings along following the instructions given. This repeats three times up until the first break, where everybody gets the chance to have a drink or go to the toilet and then after they go and practice again.

I arrived before many of the people attending; I was introduced by our connection partner to the singing teacher and the helper present in the class. Most of the people attending were able to find themselves a chair, and those who couldn't because of their mobility issues were helped. I thought it was interesting the way how those who faced the most challenges to walk, were offered an arm to help them walk by the present help staff, rather than grabbing them to lift them, this to my understanding sends the message that the person with moving challenges is being aided in his /her terms.

Two ladies sat beside me and welcomed me, one of them said "We are a friendly bunch", that day I had a toothache, the lady beside could tell I was in pain because of the way I was

holding my cheek, after explaining her I had a toothache, she offered me a painkiller which I gladly accepted.

The break arrived, and afterwards we continued singing, I was amazed by the singing skills of a couple of ladies in the group, and finally, the class finished for lunch.

I think it was interesting how glad I felt everyone was that I was there with them, they continued chatting to me and smiling in the song's intermissions, many times they complimented each other on their singing skills or made fun comments when the singing didn't go so well.

Monday 20th November 2017 – Tai chi group:

This class happened in the morning in the main hall of the centre; it had one male helper and me, the class teacher who was a mature man female, two female attendees aged 50+, a young woman aged 19+ and three male attendees aged 40+, all-male attendees were wheelchair users.

The chairs are organised in a circle allowing some space for arm movement. Everyone's seats in the chairs along the circle, and the instructor at the beginning welcomes everyone, explains what type of exercise we will be doing for the session, the lights are dimmed, and candles were dim lit, relaxing oriental music came from the radio, and at that point, the class started.

The exercises performed were from the upper side of the body only, attendees perform the exercises as instructed and there is a toilet and drinks break.

The instructor would perform the exercises, call them by name, and explain them as if they were figuring an action or a thing, i.e., pushing water, being a tree, fanning the wind etc. The music featured sometimes sounds like birds singing, wind, waves etc

This class is structured around the exercises in much-dimmed downlight, so there was no opportunity for chatting. I thought it was interesting how the only young person in the class was on her smartphone for the duration of the class and didn't join in the exercises.

At the end of the class the instructor turned on the lights and came to welcome me, he then asked me if I could come and cover him next week, he was surely confusing with somebody

else. I explained that I was there just as a student-helper and not in that capacity, he laughed, apologised, and did let me go.

Tuesday 21st November 2017 - iPad & Tablets:

This class happens in the computer room at the centre, the attendees sit around a small table, except two other people who were sitting in desktop computers and were doing their own thing, and a TV already set up, and each one is given a tablet to practice the teachings instructor have prepared for the day.

I arrived this afternoon just before the start of the session. Unfortunately, there was no internet. However, this allowed me to chat with some individuals, the first person I spoke with was with Dan (55+ y.o.). We spoke about a project he was working on about an emotional PC mouse, he was that day 3d printing the plastic outside of the mouse, and he was so passionate about it that I did allow him to explain me every minor detail. After the first break, I was invited to join the main table.

Everyone at table 2 mature ladies and all the three mature men joined us for a mobile VR session, some of them except one lady tested the headsets, the reception was positive, I suspect

Tuesday 28th November 2017 – iPad & Tablets:

This session set up was identical to the class before. However, to my perception, there were only three females all over 55 and one male under 30. Also, the instructor who normally attends this group wasn't there, but instead Anna one of the helpers was there.

I sat at the main table with the three ladies, and Anna was helping Dan who was this time creating a photo album from his holidays and required some help.

Amelia one of the ladies at this main table fell to sleep with a tablet in her hands and napped until the end of the session- Amelia was trying to do some online shopping, but she fell to sleep in the process.

The other two ladies were absorbed by the games on their tablets speaking only very little to recommend each other new games. Ross one of the attendees in this class has a speech and body mobility impediment and was a wheelchair user, I did notice that when he needed to use the toilet, he moves his feet and walks towards the staff member, while in the wheelchair. He also signals her, opening his eyes wide, pronouncing the word "Toilet".

Many of them used the tablets with stands, or any type of low-tech assistive artefact for example a finger holder, At the end of the session some staff member came to collect them one by one, Anna kindly taped Amelia in the shoulder as she fell sleep and told her that the class was finished and that the bus was here for them.

Wednesday 27th November 2017 - Dance at Kibble ("Dirty feet dance group"):

This afternoon class was not at the centre, but in a cultural space a couple of miles away, for this group attendees are required to be at the centre 10 minutes prior the class as they need to be transported to the centre in a minibus. The instructors for this class were 2, one male and one female dancers, and there were also four mixed genders and age group of helpers or carers.

The day I attended there was a workshop, the same was about dancing and instruments, the first part of the workshop was about playing with the instruments and making music together. So, we were separated into four parts and given each one percussion instrument

to share, the second part was about dancing and playing instruments because most of the attendees were wheelchair users the helpers were there to get the instruments close to them or hold them for them to play. After the break, the second part of this musical – Dance workshop was about choosing a preferred body movement and stick to it, then in the second part of this should copy somebody else's movement if they looked at you. This was a fun game, as people were mimicking one another as if stealing their own personal movements, and when someone realised, he / she was being copied normally a burst of laughter ensued.

I think in this group, it was interesting that there was a disabled couple who have been together for 25 years, the main facilitator a lady from the DRC took centre stage to announce this and ask for a round of applause for the couple to celebrate their union. People attending this workshop were keen on moving their bodies and playing with the instruments. Also, they made plenty of eye contact, and it felt like they were bonding with each other while having fun. At the end of the session, everyone got on the accessible bus were transported back to the DRC.

Monday 4th December - Current affairs:

This is a morning session which is structured like a guessing game, and it happens in the main hall, at the centre of the hall, everyone seats around the big table, and the conductor of the group divide us into two groups, a group leader is chosen.

The first part of the game consists of guessing 12 questions about current affairs, the range of topics varies, sports, famous people, serious news like politics, social issues, and sciences.

There is a break, and then, the middle part is about guessing the songs that are being played by the moderator.

The guessing structure is made in a way that after the question is made, / or song played, the first phase you to need to communicate among the group and each group gets a chance to answer trough the group leader if the question is answered the group who did get 2 points. If none of the groups answers the question, the questions are opened to everyone, and the moderator gives a clue if the question is answered in this phase the group of the person who did answer gets 1 point.

I think it is interesting that once or twice people tried to answer out of their phase and the moderator was strict about allowing whose answer she was accepting. This raised the stakes and brought order. During the breaks, I helped bringing water to the attendees when the session was finished. Everyone started putting the tablet for the lunchtime, which also happens in the main hall.

Tuesday 5th December 2017 – iPad & Tablets:

This is the third time I attend this session, and the structure is explained in the sections Tuesday 21st and 28th. In this session we continued with the regular tablet exercises, and in the second part after the break we invited everyone to try mobile VR again, me and the instructor set up the headsets again but this time we tried to mirror screencast what the people saw in the headset into the television, it quite didn't work as expected, but to some extent got everybody else involved.

From the six participants present, three of them namely Jim, Randy and Dan tested the headsets. Jim one of the attendees asked me during the session to help him to fit his feet which were badly positioned in the wheelchair and after he also asked me as a joke for a foot massage. At I felt happy he felt it was ok to share a joke with me, it did feel good to be seen as a friendly visitor, sometimes I feel like an intruder, my cultural supervisor explained me that some have trust issues given cognitive conditions and for many of them takes a while to build a bond with strangers.

Content redacted due to unpublished work without informed consent for publication. Further information can be obtained from the author

The session continued, and everybody share in a round table what their experience was, Jim's wasn't the best, he felt the headset was uncomfortable, so he stopped. Randy and Jim enjoyed the undersea experience, and they felt fascinated to see turtles, and excited to see sharks up close. Randy however admitted he felt slightly scared of the sharks as it appeared to come close fast and when I reminded him it was only a film he nodded and told me in good humour he just couldn't help it. After this we ended the session as the bus was here for pick up.

Wednesday 13th December 2017 – Debate group:

This is a popular morning session which is structured like a guessing game. It happens in the main hall, in the centre of the hall, everyone seats around the big table, and the conductor of the group divide us into two groups, a group leader is chosen.

The first part of the game consists of guessing 12 questions about current affairs, the range of topics varies, sports, famous people, serious news like politics, social issues, and sciences.

There is a break, and then, the middle part is about guessing the songs that are being played by the moderator.

The guessing structure is made in a way that after the question is made, / or song played, the first phase you need to communicate among the group and each group gets a chance to answer through the group leader if the question is answered the group who did get 2 points. If none of the groups answers the question, the questions are opened to everyone, and the moderator gives a clue if the question is answered in this phase the group of the person who did answer gets 1 point.

In the first part of the session attendees exchanged with each other Christmas cards, this was an organic exchange organised by them. There was a gender balance in the class.

However, most of the people in this class were older than 45.

The highlight of the break was that one of the female attendees brought mini-Lindt Chocolate Santa's to share with everyone.

Everyone seemed to be getting along with each other, the questions are being discussed as a group, but you can still see little clusters of people that seem to be closer to each other. There was a lot of laughter, and I think the group brings many benefits, like peer support, social interaction, and conversations that span in breaks and after the group session.

Wednesday 13th December 2017 – The Book Club group:

The book club is run by Ciara; she is a lady on her late 50's, attending the book class there was Stephen a man in his late 60's, and two other ladies who seemed to be very good friends both in their early 60's.

This group happens in a small sized room, with big, glassed doors facing the front of the DRC building. There is a two-seater sofa a Flat screen TV; it's used for the groups. There is also a soda drinks machine, and finally two tables one with around five chairs where we sat and the other on the corner that had some books and items for sale.

This group revolves around the idea of a social gathering where people can sit around the table read some part of the selected book and have a conversation at the end.

At the beginning of the session, I attended there was sort of a social sale was the attendees were decided whether to buy from the items on the table. I was told there is a bookman who brings books and other home items once a week and leaves them there in case somebody might want to buy a book or two.

After this we introduced to each other, the atmosphere was very relaxed, Ciara and the attendees seemed to know each other well, and there was some complicity going on with these two ladies.

I was intrigued on the social bookselling idea, and I asked if this was convenient somehow for them, and from this topic, we started discussing how difficult is sometimes with a disability going out on your own to pick up a book, or a gift for a friend. We spoke about how they do when they go grocery shopping, and the help they receive from people who take them there

and help them out during shopping time. I was surprised to discover that these two ladies were partially blind, and then I asked them how they read, and they showed me some apps they use to read and others to make their life easier.

At the break Ciara and I prepared coffee for everyone, Ciara gently woke up Stephen who fell asleep during the break and by the second part of the session we only read and commented in the book as the group intends it. By the end, we wished each other Merry Christmas and thanked everybody for their time.

Comments & conclusions of this first section:

As explained at the beginning of the report I am attending the DRC in an effort of understanding the realities of people living with disabilities within this centre, the everyday interaction with each other and the people who work for the centre.

My main objective is to have an idea of what disabilities compose the spectrum displayed at the centre. Moreover, use my experience at the centre to creatively construct an experience that might benefit disabled communities using Virtual reality and Immersive VR.

In my observations, I would like to highlight what interests me the most, which is the social interaction that is based on peer support and comradery. In every group, I have visited this a common denominator. There are always people who make small clusters of good friends, and the relationship between the attendees and staff is always a very friendly and kind relationship were both parts allowed to kid on each and share stories about their lives, this way enriching their relationship.

Also, I have noticed during the activities that it is important to let them enjoy the activities on their terms and pace; they are all different with different challenges. When it comes to the use of VR, some have been keen on using it, and working with them you can see the sense of wonder and enthusiasm when using VR. I would like to have the possibility to show it to more people at the centre to see what they think, and how they feel about it. Moreover, take it from there, I would like in the future, if possible, more 1 to 1 conversation or focus groups to dig deeper into what it means from their perspective to be a disabled person.

“Exploring Virtual Worlds at the DRC”

If you wish to virtually travel to farway lands, experience the life of other people or play some fun games, please register your interest at.. [REDACTED]

What is going to happen?

- 1) We will have a nice cup of tea or coffee, a piece of cake and a wee chat.
- 2) We will try some VR experiences.
- 3) We will discuss how the experiences felt.

Dates / Event / Description

Thursday 15th March

“A place to visit”

Virtually visit tigers in their habitat, swim with sharks and visit Japan.

Tuesday 20th March

“VR Docs”

Virtually visit, explore the life of others, through cutting edge documentaries.

Thursday 22th March

“Hands on!”

Play fun games, and interact with the virtual world using your hands or Controllers.

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In collaboration with...

DRC Paisley

&

Poster 1 Made to promote Workshops.

Section two of the diaries:**08th January 2018- iPad and Tablets:**

Today at the tablet's session, the session as always happens in the computer activities room, Peter the group instructor is going through emails, and how to use them within the tablets, attending the session there are 3 ladies Mani, Soleil, and Jen. There are other assistants (3) and another 2 DRC users, who are being helped by Jan, who is a regular member of staff, this is the first session of the year some regular attendees like Mohammed who wasn't there, probably because it is very cold outside.

We are sitting at the small table, this session's instruction revolves around the idea of using emails, the first task is to send an email to Peter (The instructor), who has replied to them all, and has also explained how to reply, attach pictures and what happens when an email bounces as the email address is wrong.

The user's tablets are being used with a stand, in the small breaks between tasks we socialise with each other, conversations revolved around everyday day topics, Dogs, Candy crush, biscuits. At the break everyone shared a cup of their favourite warm drink or freshwater, and we continued with the second part, in the second part we tried some VR in the form of Google cardboard YouTube videos, Jennifer was a bit reluctant in the beginning, but in the end, we found some content she was interested in (Robbie Williams LIVE concert, she used it for 3 minutes), "I love him, he is my boyfriend" she said while laughing. As a joke I asked if her husband knew, she told me she wasn't married but she has a daughter, Jennifer must have been in her late 50's.

Mani, who is an old lady, tried a headset but I believe it was too heavy for her, we also tried to show her the same videos on the tablets and let her have it on her hand, and this has little success, but it was a good idea it only needs to be tweaked and tested again, probably with other people.

My take on the iPad and tablets class was the structure; I believe the tasks a bit challenging for the users. However, the support they received was right, and there was somebody (The instructor) leading the group and time keeping the class attention focussed when necessary.

I think that was interesting about the second part was that it was a wakeup call, VR is not only about novelty, not everyone likes VR or is keen on accepting having a headset so close to their face. If I am to inspire people to get closer to VR, I need to find the right content to get them interested and try to keep things fun; I think I will print out a questionnaire asking them what kind of content they like and take it from there.

Thursday 25th January 2018– “Self-Running.”

Today I visited the self-running session. This is a morning session hosted by Ciara – a staff member who also runs the book club group; it happens in the Arts & Crafts room at the centre, it is run and sponsored by senior members of the “User's committee.

The structure is quite organic. all the ladies at the session get together at the main table in the room to practice crochet, there is a trunk where all the crochet instructions magazines are stored, every attendee brings their materials and sits with a cup of tea while working on their project. The session is quite quiet, the attendees today seemed to be quite immersed in their projects, Ciara introduced me to the group on my arrival, explaining that I was there in the quality of helper.

During the session, I started talking to Maria (62), Her accent was a bit hard to catch for me at the beginning, she is dependent on her wheelchair and has lived all her life in Paisley; she was telling me about how she learned to crochet from her nan, and that when she was younger it wasn't so easy for her and her family to access crochet magazines, so she learned by memory certain models.

Maria is married and has a daughter; her daughter bought her a embroidered figure on eBay that read “BABY”, this figure was meant as part of her baby granddaughter sweater, a gift for which she was working for, she was telling me that she bought an embroidered figure online for £5.30 and that she was surprised it was so expensive.

Carol (75) and Jaqueline (67), who are both members of the “Users committee.” We're working on baby boots, and scarf. They, however, struggled with finding a model they were working on. Speaking with them, I learned that to run the sessions they organize raffles and other activities to raise the money needed for the centre. After the break I was asked to

help them to find online resources for their knitting which required me to go to the computer room, I did not come back till almost the time the session was finished.

Wednesday 7th February 2018 – Woodwork:

Today I have visited the wood workgroup, this group happens in the woodwork room

Wednesday, it is run by Bob, and it is composed of only men.

The room is a workshop through and through; it has a sink with plates, cups and a small coffee area, the coffee has tea, coffee cookies and a big sugar pot. At the centre of the room, there is a big working table, on the sides there is a storage room, shelves, and cupboards with tools.

I was the first to arrive at the group just after Bob, then to arrive it was Brian who is a volunteer, Brian can walk with some difficulties, and he experiences certain weakness in the left side of his body, he seems not to have any speech or cognitive impediment. He greets Bob with a handshake and in a friendly manner, then he goes to one of the cupboards and retrieves tools for the session, placing them near the workstations, Bob explained to me he used to be a carpenter and suffered a stroke a few years back.

Then the customers start walking into the room, making themselves something to drink and greeting everyone present, as they go in. Bob explains to me that he is a craft & Arts worker, and everyone coming in have had in their experience with similar handy jobs; I thought this was interesting because in no other group nobody has explained me in such a detailed manner their previous crafts mastery of every attendee.

The interaction between the guys it's warm and a rugged, Al came in and said: "Hello gents..." Laughs and continues "I am using this term in a very loose manner..." blinks at Bob and speaks. "Starting with you..." they share a laugh as he goes in, starts chatting with Chris after greeting him with a handshake and a pat on the back. They start talking about the weekend, then about football. Finally, Bob interrupts the conversation to jokingly grab Brian's face with his right hand and say something along the lines of "he would know, this fucker is ugly as "David does" ... they all laughed and continued with their chatter while working. One by one they finish, tidy their stations and leave. Bob stayed for a final clean up.

Wednesday 14th February 2018 – Woodwork:

Last week I started working on a new wooden flower box, I thought it would be great to create something physical to blend into the session a bit more, Last week I did cut some wood pieces. And this week continued cutting up until I had enough pieces to create this box.

When I first arrived there was only Billy, he helped me set up my station, and then the others start arriving, as they arrived some on their own, some with the help of a career, everybody started putting together their own stations — pulling hammers and other tools from the shelves equipping themselves with what they would need for the session.

After helping everyone Billy sat beside me and started introducing me to those who were not there the last week, and once again he explained to me the jobs they used to have before coming to the DRC, for example, there is Bob who used to be a mason, now because of his age and aches he cannot work anymore, however now he has built over 10 furniture pieces since he started last year at the DRC.

Last, to arrive there was a young woman whose name I don't remember, she was taking pictures of her own university research, she was meant to be there only for that week. I noticed that there was not so much banter and swearing words as there normally were, it was almost like they were putting their best behaviour because there was a young lady visiting today.

Bob comes and helps me with the pieces of wood I was working with, and explains to me the procedure I should follow, Then beside me in their station there was Craig's who overheard our conversation and interrupts by asking Bob why is he explaining how to drill

the wooden pieces that way, given that there is an easier way, by the way, Bob stopped holding the wooden piece to then cross his arms and frown, I could tell he didn't appreciate the interruption and said... I must show him the right way, imagine he leaves this room, and he starts saying out there than me... "Bob" is showing him how to drill them without the right equipment. – Craig realised he wasn't very happy, he smiled and turned his head away to mind somebody who was asking him for he, Billy resumed.

It was evident to me that Bob is the facilitator and his background being a crafts worker he has certain skills and dexterity he wanted to pass on, Brian however by being a carpenter and this being his field of expertise wanted to help, however I could see how this "Trying to help", was creating tension between the two, and this wasn't an isolated episode, in other moments I have overheard other participants defending what they were doing by saying things along the lines of "I used to be a woodworker, I have done this before don't tell me how to do it" however they snap at each other it's mostly using a tone in their voice that denotes humour.

Today I have finally finished drilling the holes in all my pieces; I should be able to have the "Flowerbox" finished next week.

Wednesday 21st February 2018 Woodwork:

This Wednesday it's quite good for a winter day, not too cloudy. The first person to arrive is Bob; Everyone seems to be in a good mood. After everyone is in last to arrive is Brian, who brought with him a bottle of some sort of clear spirit in a gift bag. He greets Bob and give it to him, says something along the lines of "This is a little present for you", I thought it was probable that it was Billy's birthday, I asked one of the attendees that day, but nobody else seemed to be aware of his birthday, This leads me to believe there was tension built between them and Brian resorted to apologising for gifting Bob the bottle of spirits.

Another two participants were brought in by a staff member which we will call Ann, she says to Billy, here Sam and John are here. Ann greets everybody with a big smile and looks around as acknowledging everybody in the room. She grabs a tea bag from the rucksack of the customer in the wheelchair, and from the tea and Coffee box makes herself a cup of tea and asks the other customer that came with her if also he wants some tea. – He answers that he wants just black coffee. Sam in his wheelchair and he just sat there drinking his tea

helped by Ann who was joining us. I have seen her before helping this too gentlemen, so when I had the opportunity, I asked her if it was the duty to help them when they come to the centre, to which she replies that she normally helps them when they have service at the centre. (This expression used at the centre i.e. “They have service at the centre” or “Person x has service days on Mondays and Thursdays”, simply means the day the customers assist to the centre, some customers come once, twice, or thrice a week depending of their wishes and needs)

While working on my project, Bob buddied up with me to share the equipment, and he was telling me about his youngest son who is just finishing his A-levels and wants to build computer games like me. Bob suffered a stroke 3 years ago; he is around 45. The stroke had an effect his cognitive abilities and speaks with difficulty, taking gasps of breath while he speaks, he helped me with instructions on how to finish the flower box and what materials to use, Sometimes Billy will hover around to inspect, one of those times he looked slightly bothered I did not use the right tools, as he spotted how I wanted to use a nail to put together two planks, when I should have drilled and used a nut and a screw, Billy looked at Bob as if condemning this. – I had a sense that they had a sense of pride of their work and a clear idea of how things should be done.

Bob looked slightly ashamed as he oversaw helping me out. Next, I saw them both crossing glances in disapproval at me, I could not help but let a small nervous laugh scape and ask for forgiveness with an “I am sorry”, to me it was clear there was code between this two men and they took this flower box making seriously, at some point Bob had to go, and Billy helped me out finishing the flower box, and then I helped him by putting away the tools I used, he stayed a bit longer to finish up cleaning.

Tuesday 27th February - Monday 05th March – Tuesday 06th March - VR Workshops:**“A place to visit”- Tue 27th February:**

The first workshop has the theme of visiting a place which is a reality removed from our everyday life. This place of interest might give us the idea of going on holidays, in an adventure to make us feel the thrill to perform an activity out of the extraordinary.

This day we had swum with sharks, visited tigers on their native jungle, and had a Virtual tour of Japan.

Violet and Harriet: They wished to attend the activity together. So, I decided to run the workshop in a way that they both could participate. Violet is a wheelchair user, and Andrea has a failing heart, this condition makes them both face challenges when dealing with everyday life tasks, as going shopping or meeting friends, this also makes difficult for both to participate in activities they enjoy like going away holidays.

This day I only had one headset, so I did brief and explained them both the activity to then let Violet try.

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It was Violet's first-time using VR; she was incredibly excited looking around at 360 degrees. Mentioned many times the beauty of the scenery when visiting Japan, and she said, "This is the best next thing than to go there", I had the impression she enjoyed the aerial views.

When being debriefed, she highlighted many times how she did enjoy the tour of Japan, that the colours and ideal scenarios stole her breath, and that she felt happy to have seen this.

She didn't like to have the SUMO's fighting so close to her, and that the audio didn't matter to her as much, but she mentioned later it was thrilling to have the tigers walking around her, I have to say that her mood definitively seems to have improved after the visualisations.

Then it was Harriet turn, she was calm and seemed to be enjoying the movies at her own pace when debriefed she said she did enjoy the landscapes as this is something she is interested. When I asked her about the colours and how she felt about it, she instantly mentioned the undersea experience as she enjoys fishing and swimming. When asked she said she was ok with the music and atmospheric audio.

Both agreed that scenic contemplation and the right kind of atmospheric music and audio description does a lot for the narrative and adds an element of meditation which to me speaks about the power of immersion and mindfulness these experiences could create.

Dan: He explained to me, that his challenge is walking and standing up for periods of time, he also experiences a back and neck pain that gradually increases if he doesn't change his stance. He has done some mobile VR before, so he knows what to expect.

When he had the headset on, he was calm and looked around with interest, also up and down. I thought this would not have happened as he has used VR before and I had the theory that probably that with more experienced users looking around at 180 degrees would be the norm, but instead, he did 360 degrees in the swivel chair.

When debriefed he said he enjoyed them all, but his favourite was the Tiger experience, and the highlight of that experience was to be able to see a tiger so up close. He said that is more interested in getting out to the great outdoors.

When prompted he also said that the ambience sounds, audio description and music did a lot for him during the experience.

He thought it is interesting that technology like VR would help people reconnect with nature, as nowadays we are so embedded in our city routines, and more people live in cities than in the countryside.

“A place to visit”- Tue 15th March:

Kelly & Albert: They were briefed together, as they came at the break of one of their group activities at the Centre. Albert is a wheelchair user; motor movement and Kelly had a stroke however she enjoys good mobility and speech. In our initial conversation, both told me places they would like to go to, but it is troublesome for them due to mobility issues, and none of them is keen on long flights. However, Albert would love to go to Spain, and Kirsty has always wanted to go to New Zealand.

Albert was calm at the beginning of the experience, he seemed very happy when viewing the movies, and he was in-between vocal viewings about how much he was enjoying it. He said he enjoyed seeing the animals close to him, but he said during the experiencing that his favourite experience was the tour of Japan. Albert was debriefed first so he could go back to his activity, he was clear on stating that he had fun and that he felt very entertained. His favourite thing about the Japan scene was the fight scene, he said “I’d like to go to Japan” he felt immersed and that he would like to do again in the future as he enjoyed very much.

Kelly had her first viewing while Albert was debriefed, she was calm however she looked like she was enjoying herself very much as she smiled and looked around with interest and When debriefed she said she enjoyed the Japanese tour the most, she said it was interesting to feel like she was virtually there visiting the temples and having people so up close, and that the audio description and ambience added much to the experience. She also said that it was thrilling to feel immersed with the sharks and that she preferred actual videos of places to 3D graphics as she likes the realness aspect of it. She said, “it was very realistic”, and “Amazing the fact you can turn around, and get a feel in a wheelchair”

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seemed immersed.

Sarah: She had a stroke that partially paralysed the right side of her body before that she used to lead an active life. Today she faces mobility issues; however, she can still walk, but she needs company and help most of the times.

She has not done any VR before; she was fine using a regular chair, when placing the headset, she looked around calmly and with interest. When I debriefed her, she told me that accidentally she watched a Honolulu virtual tour, where she seemed to be happy. She said she enjoyed the nature visualisation the seaside, and to be able to perform an activity like surfing virtually.

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Sarah also stated that she was very entertained and immersed, she said she enjoyed looking at the landscapes and animals, also after being enquired on regards to the audio, Also Susan was vocal about how much she enjoyed the sound of the sea and the people laughing, she also said she would love going to Iceland and see some penguins.

“VR Docs for empathy” - Tue 20th March:

This experience visits the lives of children who have lost their way of living and sometimes family members due to war and now find themselves living the reality of refugees.

This workshop intends to understand the impact and perception of the attendees and the reflection on the reality of others and their own, with the mean to empathise.

Ellen: She is a wheelchair user and has cerebral palsy, this disability doesn't allow her to move about or communicate as much as she wishes. However, she is very involved in her community working with children and has received the highest award by working with this community (The Brownies).

When trying the experience, she looked around with interest; she was calm and attentive.

When debriefed she explained that she thought the experience was very interesting, and she said she felt lucky when being confronted with the reality of this children. When Ellen questioned, she said that she felt immersed by being able to look around using the headset. She agreed with the statement of feeling removed from this reality when using the VR HMD.

Resh & Kelly: both are wheelchair users and have a medium speech impediment. The initial conversation was concise due to this. They joined the conversation just after I debriefed Elle.

When viewing the experiences, they both looked around, interested and were calm. However, none of them felt like communicating their experience while doing so. When debriefed they thought the experiences were very immersive and exciting. However, we must note that when Kristy adjusted it, she viewed another experience (Tigers) instead.

Resh watched "The displaced" he agreed with the statement that he feels and understand the reality he did presence using the headset. He also said, he felt like he was on the boat, and it was good for him.

Kelly was quite vocal; she communicated that she was very happy to have the opportunity to go somewhere else when debriefed she said that at the start of the day, she was feeling anxious, but after viewing the experience she felt more relaxed and happier, and she wishes she would like to do it again. It was interesting to see this contrast between her and the quieter response I received from Resh.

To end the session in a positive note, I asked them if they wish they could visit a place, Elaine said she wishes to go to Australia, Resh wishes to go to China and Kelly would love going to The United States of America.

Pamela the Centre care staff who accompanied the three of them said that it would be interesting to create an experience to be used to help relax and dispel anxiety, the attendees present in that moment seemed to agree, also a social VR interaction where everyone could visit a place virtually to then share their experiences were discussed.

Aubrey, Harriet & Violet: Violet and Harriet have been interviewed before and used VR for one of our studies. This is the first time Aubrey or is interviewed by me. Aubrey has some mobility issues derived from a stroke; she is currently using a wheelchair due to this mobility challenges. The three attendees were briefed and explained the study at the same time; Aubrey preferred not to be video recorded or having pictures taken. At the very beginning of our session Violet seemed to be excited, she told me “I told everybody at dinner that I have tried Virtual Reality, my grandson was so impressed, he wanted to know where you bought this?”, I did explain... - To me this was a sign that she felt validated because she had been in contact with a something new and “Cool”, Harriet and Violet tried the experience first. All of them were calm viewing the experience, they showed interest and did look around in 360 degrees. At this point, we needed to break for lunch for Aubrey, and Harriet and Violet had to get ready for the bus to pick them up. Because of this, I had to debrief them on the go. I think it was interesting because even though they were debriefed separately, they gave me very similar responses.

They felt that there was a sense of immersion and that there were moments that deeply affected them because it was conveyed to them with Virtual Reality. They paragoned to the news, and they said that people become numb to the way society feed the news and this is a media format that could change the way we perceive other people’s realities.

Aubrey when being debriefed said “Using this thing is like being there, in television you watch the news, and it doesn’t bring the message home like this, those children need help”.

Aubrey, Violet, and Harriet also said that they were so immersed that they at moments forgot their reality (I guess they meant their actual surrounding and what was happening

around them). - To brighten things up and end with a more positive outlook, I asked them what country they would prefer to go. Violet and Harriet said that they would love to visit Rome (The Sistine chapel) virtually, Violet has been there before, and she recalled how beautiful it was, same happened with Ann, she said that she would love to go to Capri again and be able to enjoy the beautiful landscapes. I think it was interesting that these three ladies belonging to a similar age and background had a common romantic place in Italy, as a relaxing and lovely place to visit.

Martin: He has been interviewed before, and he has some experience using VR, he was calm during the experience and did look around in 360.

When debriefed he explained that he felt much immersed and that this form of media could convey people's lives better than the way we are fed the news every day. He said he felt the need to help; there were moments where he felt strongly affected about the story, he used as an example the story of one of the boy's fathers who was burned alive.

"Hands on." - Tue 22nd March:

Today's activities have to do with using your own body in the Virtual world; this is achieved by using a hand tracking recognition device such a LEAP MOTION or a GEAR VR controller.

The activities are 4, and they all require fine motor movement and could be interesting from a storytelling point of view as well as challenging enough to be rewarding for them.

In this activity, you must use your hands to grab the cubes and place them in the top of the robots.

This is a relaxing activity where petals need to be plucked from a flower

This activity requires the user to make the pad-to-pad precision grip to grab stars.

This activity requires the use of the controller to draw a house using all the basic geometric figures, Circle, Square, triangle, to build a house.

Tracy: She had a stroke as a product she is facing cognitive challenges, and currently in a wheelchair, however she can move her hands and arms, I demoed the day's activity for her to feel more inclined to participate.

She performed the activities quite well, she looked like she was having fun while playing, and she was focused. When debriefed she confirmed that she was feeling happy after the experience and her favourite activity was one of the Flower.

Maggie: She likes sewing and knitting, I have met Marjorie before in one of the self-run classes, she watched Marjorie perform the activities, and subsequently she felt she wanted to try.

It is not clear to me what the source of her disability, she can walk with moderation and seem to have quite good fine hand motor movement.

She seemed quite focused and excited when performing the activities, however difficult they were for her, she continued trying.

Her favourite activity was the flower activity, she said when enjoyed the music, and she felt relaxed, she also confirmed feeling good after the experience.

Tom: He has been at home and not coming to the DRC for a while, he had a chest infection, so today he was glad to be back, he uses a wheelchair, and enjoys photography and playing video games. - During the activities, he gave me the impression to be quite involved and seem to have fun; he mentioned the cubes were sticky, which is interesting as these objects only exist in the digital world.

When I debriefed him, he told me that he enjoyed the experiences even though they were a bit challenging for him or had fun, he said he felt immersed in the activities, and the music was relaxing, and that the embodiment heightened the immersion by having the opportunity to see them, and he experienced this that he could forget about the reality around him making the digital embodiment second nature. – After the workshops I understood that there was an

interest in interactive media within and outside iVR, it was clear to me that while there is still a lot of that wow factor surrounding a new media like VR, because of the immersion I have observed, and the way participants refer to it as “almost being there” this could be an interesting media to them. – This was the end of the preliminary workshops. In conclusion, I would say the general feeling is that experiences that go back to nature and connection with oneself bring general interest to the people I have interviewed. Others get comfort on the idea of revisiting places they have been before, and all the interviewed have a romanticised idea of a place they would love to visit.

Ideas that came to my mind are related to relaxation and mindfulness, with immersive imaginary either video or pictures, could also be an exploration of scenarios 3D and intractable with adequate audio, or in the other hand immersive documentary about places of interest providing a sense of escapism of reality.

Back to regular visits, Thursday 19th April – Gardening Club:

This is a Thursday session broken into morning and afternoon; I did choose to come to this group to hear about a project they are running with nearby schools called “Spuds for Buddies”. According to Bob, who is a staff member and main facilitator of this club, in recent years the DRC garden installations have been a victim of vandalism from children living in the neighbouring area, the aim is to invite children over and with the assistance of the gardening club plant potatoes, this way creating a bonding experience between the children assisting this session and the DRC installation. Bob says this has had an impact not only on how children view and interact with their local DRC, but as well with the local community in general.

This session happened both in the woodwork room and in the garden, the customer was Sam, who to me seems to be just about thirty, he uses a wheelchair as well as mild upper limbs mobility, he seems to be from Pakistan or India, Peter who has displayed hand dystrophy and Grant who seemed to me to have a cognitive disability, both are Scottish and around 25. Then there was Gustav who is a pensioner who uses a walking stick, and finally Thessa, an Irish woman in her 50s, who comes to this group as a volunteer.

When I first arrived, as always, I introduced myself, everyone was sitting in the main table having hot beverages and sharing a selection of treatments, I explained the reason of my visit, and where I come from (Venezuela). This triggered curiosity among the younger users

Peter and Grant, they asked where my country was, and I showed them in my mobile using a “google” map, we carried on speaking up until Bob divided the people sitting in the table into two groups, the first group would be Bob, Sam, and Gustav, and in my group, there were Peter, Grant and Thessa as we all were sitting together.

Bob’s relationship with the group is from my perspective one of respect and authority as well as a friendly and helpful almost paternal.

After this we moved to the main garden, Bob explained the first group’s task, which was to fill the plant containers with fresh soil, and organize potatoes in an aligned manner, after this he explained my group how to plant the potatoes in this container that are about 2mts x 1mts. While working, Theresa and the guys in my group were having a conversation about trucks, at some point Peter calls the trucks “UVs”, Thessa was puzzled and said “I had never heard that word” then she turns to me and says in an apologetic but somehow careless manner “I am Irish, these boys are from Paisley, they speak weird you see”, then she turns at them and blink with a smile which generates Laughter among us., just after Peter asks me if I understand what they are saying, I reply “most of the times” which triggered some giggles on Grant and a faint smile in Theresa.

The plantation of potatoes goes by fast, Bob comes by to check on the work and notices Grant trousers are a bit down on the backside, he says to him in a fun manner “Grant pull your trousers, I can see your butt, you guys are going too fast, remember there is no rush you have the whole day”. Grant took notice and pulling his trousers up giggled with everyone. As we went on Sam was using the hose to water the plants just after us.

By the end of the session we sat down to share a coffee and share the treats, Peter and Tessa who were sitting beside me were talking about their future holidays for what I understood Peter is going to Salem for Halloween and Theresa to Ireland to visit her family, Grant was playing “Pokémon Go” just listening, the bus driver who also came by and was sitting on the table with Bob tells us that his sister went to Cuba with her husband, and they were shocked to discover that the locals are not allowed to interact with the tourists and the economy it’s closed and controlled by the government. At this point, the conversation was over, and it was time to go, Tessa asks if it is ok for her to leave. Bob joking with her

asks the table to raise their hands if they think Tessa can go. Everybody chuckles and raise their hands. At this point, everyone starts leaving one by one.

Friday 20th April – Relaxation and hanging around the DRC:

On my way to the “Relaxation” session I first arrived at the DRC gates where I saw Violet and Harriet, they were having a bit of a chat and cigarettes at the small kiosk just outside the centre, Violet looked excited, and she called me over saying she had a secret for me. A famous singer called Paolo Nutini was supposed to drop by to deliver a cheque for the DRC, they seemed to be excited however they have been at the centre since 10:30 and Paolo has not arrived. - Fridays the centre finishes the groups at two pm, I arrive just after lunch for the relaxation session, and this group’s premise is to create an environment where people can relax un unwind, for this the library is transformed into a darker space by turning the lights off, closing the curtains, using colour changing candles, kaleidoscopic lights, and some instrumental music.

Everyone sits in facing each other and in the centre, there is a small table where the candles are the lid. Today’s customers are only two, one helper and the staff facilitator is Moe, he invites us to relax and close our eyes to start the session.

The session lasts only an hour, as the centre closes at 2:00 pm, not much happened at the session as it is a self-guided session. One of the customers, an elderly lady, fell asleep and started snoring hard, so hard in fact that another customer sitting next to her in a

wheelchair just beside me opened her eyes and couldn't close them again but kept them open for the rest of the session.

Just before the end of the session, the centre's bus driver came knocking as he came to pick up the users, the sleeping customer woke up immediately as the lights coming from the open threshold hit her straight on her eyes. Jan ended the session with the phrase "That's us, folks". I think it is interesting that they drastically changed the reality of the room by closing the curtains, turning the lights on, and using lights to change the atmosphere of this room that is normally very sober.

Walking out of the room towards the building main entrance, I see that staff members as well as customers waiting around, I sit in the meeting room at the front with all the other customers while we wait, they seem to be in a good mood still a bit excited but not very happy as some sigh waiting for Paolo who has not shown up yet.

I went nearby to buy something to drink and came back, Violet and Harriet are sitting outside smoking at the Kiosk, Violet calls me again, she asks me what did I buy and reply "A pair of cokes", she said she wanted one, I reach for one and when I try to give it to her she tells me it's the Glaswegian sense of humour she didn't want one. I shrugged, and we giggled.

Harriet pulls her phone out and shows me pictures of a man who had a bird of prey in his arms, "He was walking down the street when we were on the bus, I thought it was a cat", and then she kept on scrolling and showed me a picture of Violet with her head inside of the Oven, she described it as Violet saying "I want to be gassed"... They looked at each other in complicity and laughed, thereafter we started walking into the centre, they were not very happy on waiting anymore on this guy as it was already 2:15 in the afternoon, "We are too tired, we have been here since 10:30".

In the waiting room beside the reception we carried on waiting, the customers were a bit tired, at this point, Violet reaches for Moira who is one of the top staff members and asks her if they can all leave already as they are tired. Moira shook her head in a gesture of understanding and thanked everyone for waiting, called the buses, and the customers start getting on the bus.

Friday 15th May 2018 – iPad and Tablets session:

This session is an afternoon session, and it happens Computer activities room, Peter who is this sessions facilitator and my cultural supervisor, recently acquired a PSVR and he will use it today in addition to his “iPad and tablets” regular session, attending the session there were the regular 3 ladies that normally attend, Mani, Soleil, and Jen. and another 2 male DRC users, Rab, and Tom, who have both participated in my VR workshops, there is another student who likes me is assisting Peter, staff, one of them comes in a wheelchair the other uses a walking stick, but have good mobility on the upper body, there are excited to try this new game console, others have used it in other opportunities.

Peter set it up for us. The DRC does not have a reliable internet connection, so beforehand Peter Downloaded three different experiences, the game we are playing today is PlayStation VR worlds. It is not one game but a collection of VRs minigames, almost like a compendium showing what can be done in VR. Peter goes around the table were we are all sitting and asks one by one if they wish to try it, The ladies were not very keen on trying, Mani barely raised her head immersed in what she was playing in the tablet, and Jen jokingly said she had been at the hairdressers and she did not want to ruin her “Hairdo”, Soleil simply said, “no”, later she told me it wasn’t for her, she already tried and got scared with a shark in the “Ocean Descend” experience, and while she like the “Danger ball” (Ping-pong) she didn’t feel like doing it today.

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The first one to go is Rab, he is keen on playing with gadgets and enjoys videogames, being helped by Peter he decides he wants to try the “Danger ball” experience which you can play with your head, he starts playing and he seems entertained and challenged by the speed of the ball, after scoring some and losing some he asks to play another one of the options, so he chooses “Ocean Descend” experience, this is an experience where the player goes into a submarine pod and encounters different marine flora and fauna.

This is the first time I witness it too, at first, he is calm and seems to enjoy descending into the ocean, he tries to reach the virtual elements with his hand, there are turtles, fish, and a manta-ray. He seems relaxed and keeps chatting with us about what he sees at some point in the game a Shark appears on the side, and his moods changed he says “uhh a shark?!” he starts laughing and suddenly the sharks start attacking the virtual pod he is in. His mood totally changed, letting escape a small cry as he was scared but in the way somebody who enjoys suspense is.

In the experience the shark bites one of the oxygen pods and he seems excited and alert shaking his hands as if something is going to happen, he seems impressed and entertained, after that the worst passes and he utters a “phew” as a sign of relief, he had fun, he says. Peter helps him out of, and it's Tom's turn. Tom has tried the “Danger ball” experience before, and through the TV he was able to see what Rab saw, in continuation Peter helps him with the headset and same as before he starts descending and he seems to enjoy the view of the different sea layers, however while he comments that he is impressed by what he sees, and he seemed amused by the appearance of the shark, he doesn't seem wildly excited and surprised by it, he barely shakes his hands, but mostly he looks around at every re-appearance, after the shark, the experience is over.

I asked him how it was, he is telling me it was fun, he liked seeing the animals so up-close and the comments on the immersion, saying that having the “Pod” as a frame of reference made him feel safe and less dizzy, also the headset was more comfortable to the mobile headsets we normally use, Rab agreed and he added that he thought the ocean experience was the most interesting,

however, he thinks the “danger ball” was the one he could see himself going back to as it has more rep-playability.

After them it was my turn, I noticed only 2 games were downloaded, I first play the ocean descent, and then the “Danger Ball” I could see how the ocean descent was the most interesting in terms of story and is a game where you are only allowed to look around in a swivel chair it’s a good one for DRC participants with reduced mobility and wishes to go on a journey with low interactivity, the Ball game was exciting and fun, however, while fun I can see how many participants at the DRC would struggle with the movements.

The buses are here to pick up the customers and I stay back to help my supervisor packing up, and then I asked him why he downloads only two experiences out of the 5 total he could have used, and he told me these were the ones he thought would be best as the other three included different type of scenarios that might have been perceived as distressing by the DRC customer, so he thought he would start with this two and maybe show the rest at a later date.

Friday June 29th, 2018 – Lunchbreak Goodbye

Amelia, a DRC responsible contacted me as she was preparing a lunchtime get together to wish Rahul my cultural supervisor goodbye. This event was celebrated in the main hall where everyone gathers for lunch. - I knew for quite some time that unfortunately Raul’s contract was ending, so it felt right to go and wish him the best in his new adventure, also I was happy that

A l i t h t t i

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from the author

When I arrived, I sat in one of the tables close to the door, during lunch time there is some space for the food catering and then the tables are normally arranged around the room with enough space for wheelchairs to pass, before sitting down I saw Amelia and Amanda chatting away with some staff members, but also some people who also worked with Raul from ROAR (an elderly people wellbeing institution in Renfrewshire). I reach to Amelia for having thought of me and inviting me. – Then I took a sit. Raul arrived and went around the room that was decorated for the occasion saying hello to customers, staff, and me. Somebody gave me some food that I did not ask for, but I welcomed as I left my wallet in the office, and I could not stop by Greggs for my usual BLT. When everyone settled down with their food Amanda started the good luck speech for Raul, in resume she thanks him for his work at the DRC and wished him best, similarly Amanda also had a few words and gave Raul a beanie on behalf of everyone, then Raul got to have thank everyone for their time together, a round of applauses ensued after every speech. Many were moved and smiled, it felt like a moment of celebration for the time we all got to share with him. After that, we all had a chance to have a picture taken with him in front of a decorated wall. – Soon after I wish him best and left back to the office happy that I got to thank him for his help.

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Tuesday 4th December 2018 – Produce first user test (Prototype):

During the summer I was busy filming and creating the application, so I couldn't visit the DRC for an extended period, however, I was mindful of how important it is to keep in touch with the DRC community during times where I am not able to be present at the group sessions. I emailed and stopped by a couple of times while I was taking a hiatus on the DRC visits. During this period, I got in touch with Kimberly, and she invited me to assist to one of her sessions, and I took this opportunity to test with the participants the scenes I have recorded.

Kimberly runs the music session on Tuesday afternoon, and I did ask her on anticipation if she would be ok for me to show her participants what I have been working on, she was happy about it. For this session I prepared 6 short videos of 1-2 minutes each to show the participants the 360 video environments I have been recording, so we could choose the videos they would prefer. I arrived in this session before anybody else did and started to set up, first to arrive were Monica and Hellen as they came on the same bus, then on another bus Drew and Kelly arrived, Kimberly asked me how many headsets I had ready and how many customers were able to do it at the same time, I told her I had two headsets, she looked curious and somehow excited so I asked if she wanted to help me out by fitting the headsets on the participants.

When everyone was settled, Kimberly introduced me to everyone, then I explained the purpose of my visit. I made all the participants aware of the study and their rights as participants, and then I made some onboarding open questions, some of them had never used VR and this was their first time. I and Kimberly fitted the headsets first on two participants at the time, and as always, I would ask them to raise their hand whenever they were finished, many of them were excited to see what they were seeing, they all seemed to be paying attention the environment and after looking around for a bit every time a new scene would start, they would normally focus on one point. Afterwards, when everyone was done with their viewing, at the end Kimberly tried the scenes too. Subsequently, together we spoke about every single scene and how they felt about it, at the end I asked them to rate every scene from one to six being one their favourite and six the less favourite.

The beach was their most favourite of all and the one everyone was the most keen on, Drew said that “The waves hitting the rocks looks perilous at first, but then you focus on the sunset and the sound of the waves and it makes you feel calmer”, only one participant did not like the beach scene, she said she preferred the garden where not much happens and its calm, Kelly justified this by saying that she gets scared with things moving around her too fast and she feels less anxious when things move slowly, and she liked the sound of the birds. Then we all had a break where we shared cookies and made coffee, during the break we play to guess where this places that I just showed them were, this sparked a conversation and they were quite into this guessing game, which most of them got right.

This place seemed to hold certain meaning even if they have never visited them.

The session ended not long after when other DRC staff members came to pick up the customers as the buses started coming to collect them.

Tuesday 7th February 2019 – Produce first user test for Staff (Prototype):

Last week I arranged with my contact person at the DRC a visit during the afternoon, with the purpose that staff members could pop-up when available to try the late prototype of the experience and find out what could be improved and their overall impressions, the application had 4 scenes uploaded a test audio to give an idea of how the final prototype will look like. The test took the following form, I first ask them some conversational questions about themselves to break the ice, I explain them what the concept of the experience is and how to use it, to then help them take the headset to debrief them on their experience.

My first two participants were Amelia and Amanda. Amelia is my main contact person now that my supervisor Rahul is no longer working at the DRC, she manages the day to day at the DRC but also runs the photography class. Amanda is an admin person at the DRC and for what I understand the person who liaises the cultural affairs with the council within the centre. When they first arrived, I followed the ethics protocol and explained them the study and their right and asked them to sign the ethics form. They were happy to be helping, but we had some technical problems as Amanda's headset kept coming off, she was very patient and kind, while I fitted it a third time, I was a bit nervous because I kept messing with her hair.

After they watched the experience, before I would say a thing, they both looked at each other as a sign of agreement and told me Well done. Then I asked them if they thought it was possible for the DRC to be interested to use experiences like this for their service users and Amelia replied, "not only for the service users, but this could be good for staff members also, sometimes we feel stressed too", she smiles with her eyes in a candid way. I asked them what scene they preferred the best and Amelia preferred the beach and Amanda the lake but overall, they liked the whole idea, Amanda told me she is an artist herself and that she likes to paint, and that this gave her some inspiration, she wished she could go somewhere nice and relax but this was a good placebo. I asked them if they could find their way around the buttons of the app and if the audio was ok. And they both agreed that it was ok, however Amanda told me one of the experiences froze a bit, after that I thanked

then and asked then to help me spread the word with other staff members in case anybody wanted to try it.

Next staff member was Aileen, she is also doing some admin at the DRC, she seemed very keen, she told me she had never used VR before but she was very excited to try, however it was short lived when she put the headset on, she just couldn't process the images, she raise her hand one minute of two later when after I fitted the experience and explained her how to choose the experience she wanted. She wasn't feeling well, she was suffering from motion sickness. – We stopped the study right there.

My next participant that afternoon was Joe, Joe runs many groups at the DRC and helps around when needed. He has a very calm demeanour, He has helped me before, so he understood straight away what he needed to do, when I debriefed him, he told me he wasn't very keen on the audio because of the audio wasn't very clear and he didn't know if it was because of his tinnitus or the recording. He also told me I should probably do an easier transition as the transition between one scene and the next was a bit "choppy", he also told me he has visited some of these spaces. He told me his favourite scenes were the ones that featured the sound of the water, and when I asked him If he thought customers and service users could use this he

told me that depended very much of the setting but that he sees some potential. he also told me I should make clear to participants when the meditation is over because while the audio does not repeat on loop the video does and it's not clear and from a staff point of view.

Just afterwards Anel came in, she supports some sessions and she never did any VR before, I had to wait a little because the mobile phones were either very warm or without batteries, and after some minutes I helped her put the headset on, while she had a bit of issue while selecting the experience she desired, she looked calm and interested following the exercises, when she was done she raised her hand to let me know the video was finished. She was the only one, when I asked her, what did she think about it, she pointed that personally she was interested in this type of alternative medicine, so she thought this would be beneficial for the DRC. However, she had worries about the setup, she confessed she was slightly dizzy afterwards, and thought the headset was uncomfortable, and she didn't know if this type of VR would be suitable for everybody at the DRC because it involves a lot of work. Then we started speaking about the scenes and she told me she enjoyed the lake the most, it did remind her of family trips.

After this last participant it was time to collect my things, I had notes on things I had to either add or change, some of them like Amanda or Amelia were very kind and did not want to point out many flaws, I guess they did this seeing that I am a student completing some sort of homework and did not want to be too critical, however I found more helpful the feedback from Joe and Anel, they saw it from the perspective of somebody who has to prepare a group event and spotted what would be more helpful from them if they were to use VR as part of their sessions

Participants:

The following are field notes that have been created to reflect upon the population at the DRC, with the purpose of profiling the users, creating personas, however I would consider these notes part of the ethnographies.

Violet is a 62-year-old grandmother. She has been assisting the disability resource centre in quality of customer for over three years, part-time during the mornings. She is currently assisting regularly to the groups of debating, history of music and current affairs.

She is a Renfrewshire resident and uses the Renfrewshire accessible bus to commute to the centre picking her up at 9:30 from home and goes back at lunchtime with the 12:30 bus, to have lunch with her family. When she goes grocery shopping, she goes with members of her family or receives help from third-party assistance (Shop workers, carer...etc.)

Violet's best friend at the centre is Harriet. When in the centre, they assist together with sessions. During the breaks, they enjoy standing in the outside kiosk at the gate of the centre sharing a cigarette and chatting with each other, or anyone who approaches the kiosk. An example of their normal interaction would be Harriet and Violet are in the DRC's kitchen, Violet jokes Harriet about how horrible her life is. Harriet laughs, following that Violet opens the Microwaves ovens door and introduces her head inside. Harriet keeps on laughing takes a picture and shares it with friends at the kiosk while having a cigarette to have a good laugh. It is to note that mainly the groups she engages with are groups of high social interaction; these sessions fit well her personality.

She is a wheelchair user. However, she is normally very active and social, but because of her condition SLE (Systemic lupus erythematosus), she can feel very tired or unwell due to chemotherapy. Although she usually deals with problems optimistically and positively, she finds her mobility issues do not allow her to enjoy life to the fullest due to the difficulties she faces; this frustrates her. I have observed it causes her some anxiety.

Violet was particularly excited when she discovered Virtual Reality; she told me she went home that day and was telling her grandson and daughter about it and they gladly shared her joy. She normally engages in watching television for soap operas and news; she also owns a smartphone that she uses for pictures and social media, i.e. sharing pictures in WhatsApp or using Facebook.

Harriet is a Renfrewshire resident and a married mum of two; she is 44 years old; she is calm and shy none the less she is open to conversation.

She says that one day she had been feeling exhausted and short of breath and this has been going on for months, but it was not until one day when she suffered heart palpitations that she decided to refer herself to a doctor. She was diagnosed with “Failing heart”, since then she has been assisting to the centre, her condition can make her feel tired. Now she has been assisting to the centre for over three years.

She uses the Renfrewshire accessible bus to commute to the centre picking her up at 9:30 from home and goes back at lunchtime with the 12:30 bus, to have lunch with her family.

She is currently assisting regularly to the groups of debating, history of music and current affairs. Harriet can always be seen at the centre in the company of her good friend Violet, when in the centre, they assist together to sessions. During the breaks, they enjoy standing in the outside kiosk at the gate of the centre sharing a cigarette and chatting with each other, or anyone who approaches the kiosk.

In the family setting, she enjoys going fishing and other outdoor activities. She likes watching the news in the morning and some soaps in the evening, she owns a normal smartphone, which she uses for social media and picture sharing. Even though she can walk and doesn't need a wheelchair, she gets tired, and it can be frustrating for her when it comes to her everyday life as this mobility issues can be quite restrictive in her everyday life.

Dan is a 61-year-old man. He was born in Renfrewshire area however he lived almost 20 years of his life in Cape Town – South Africa. He retired three years ago when diagnosed with cancer at the lower back of his spine, because of this he is experiencing some problems walking and uses crutches, he uses the accessible busses at the centre to go to the centre and back home.

Dan does not see himself as old; he spends most days at the centre in its rooms developing his idea of an emotional mouse. He truly enjoys sharing his idea which consists of a mouse that could track if the user is suffering from stress. At weekends, he enjoys reading, cooking, and skypeing with his family. He is currently searching for a holiday or somewhere to go as he likes nature activities; he proudly told me the story of his visit to the Serengeti National Park located in Tanzania.

Dan is a highly educated individual; he completed a PhD related to business computing, and he is always on the lookout for material to read related to technology, medical wellbeing, and emotions, He also enjoys listening to classical music and plays the violin himself.

He is fascinated with technology, he is always happy to try new things, he was my very first VR participant, and he likes to engage as he finds the experiences immersive.

In regards of his media consumption and habits, he rarely watches anything out of the “BBC iPlayer”, or specific videos he finds on YouTube, he uses Facebook rarely, but he also keeps up with his family through Skype. His response to normalised media is completely standard.

Although generally fit and healthy, Martin struggles with mobility. He sometimes struggles to hear and uses reading glasses.

Tim is a 50-year-old man; he has lived in Renfrewshire his whole life. Currently, he lives with his sister and her family. He suffers from Dwarfism many factors among that muscular dystrophy; he uses a wheelchair and has been attending the centre for two years already, normally two or three full days a week. The bus picks him up in the morning from home, participates in the morning activity, enjoys lunch and after the afternoon session, he returns home after the groups. At the centre, he is open for conversation with anyone who approaches him. However, he has a youthful outlook in life when you get to know him, I have the impression he is not a conversation starter as most of the times is concentrated on his iPad, his favourite groups or sessions are iPad and tablets, Gym., Photography and Tai-chi.

He enjoys photography and digital painting on his iPad pro, spending most of his time in these activities on the weekends he enjoys family activities with his sister and his nephew, going to the park, visiting the museum, or watching a movie in the cinema.

When he is not painting or taking pictures, he likes playing video games or watching Netflix as well he spends time retouching his pictures or uploading his paintings and photography's online on Instagram or Facebook. His response to normalised media is completely standard. However, he always seems very interested in testing VR applications, and he is vocal on sharing his ideas, likes or dislikes regarding the media he experiences.

Ellen is a 25 year college old student; she lives with her family in the Renfrewshire area, she volunteers as a senior “Brownie” guide, she finds working there has given her personal growth and welcoming new girls into this guiding girls makes her feel happy. In this job has received the highest recognition in the sector for her work, she also comes to the centre 2-3 times per week and gets involved in many activities, her social carer is Pauline, who she is a good friend. Alternative health group, history of the music group, quiz Friday afternoon, exercise.

She was born with cerebral palsy, this makes her muscles feel stiff and results in poor coordination as well as motion difficulty in her movements, she also experiences medium speech impediment. As a result, she uses an electric wheelchair.

Kelly is a 27-year-old woman living in the Renfrewshire area; she used to train to become a schoolteacher. While she was training at 20 years old, she suffered cerebral bleeding on the left side of her brain; this left her with a weakness on the right side of her body, this also meant she needed to learn how to talk and walk again.

Now she assists to the DRC in quality of volunteer, for 2-3 days a week, she helps in the centre with paperwork and organising events, she says this has helped her to recover confidence in the workplace. She also involves herself in the group activities helping whenever she can. In her spare time, she likes visiting friends and family as she is very social, she also has a passion for music and knows how to play the guitar. When she tried VR, she preferred the documentaries rather than the 3D CGI environments.

She uses social media, watches television, and owns a smart mobile phone as well as a tablet to read or watch videos. During my observations I have deducted her contact with this type of media can as regular as any other individual of her age, for example, normal interest on stories with moving images, and slightly addicted to her mobile phone.

She feels frustrated whenever she witnesses discrimination against disabled people and wishes there were more empathy and awareness on the issues of this communities.

Jenna is a female customer at the DRC on her early forties; she was born with curvature of the spine, cerebral palsy, and asthma. She is left-handed four fingers on her right hand. She needs to use a nebuliser at night-time to sleep. She uses an electric wheelchair and the DRC bus to mobilise herself. She assists in the centre 4-5 days a week.

She is a reserved individual. However, she can be quite chatty when she feels comfortable with the people around her. She enjoys assisting to the iPad, Dance and singing classes at the CRD, now she is learning how to play the guitar, she is very affectionate to Pauline who is a staff member at the DRC and the closest carer to her, and she sees her as a good friend.

She can get frustrated and anxious at times and suffer from low mood due to her mental and physical conditions; she has expressed the wish find alternatives to fight her anxiety and frustrations. She watches television, read books and owns a mobile phone, her response to media is within regular parameters.

Resh is a male customer at the DRC on his sixties. He was born with bifid spine, impeded speech for which he is in therapy, he also hydrocephalus and his walk is gated, and it's slow, he uses an electric wheelchair, and relies on the DRC bus to mobilise himself 3-4 times a week, his favourite groups are Singing, movie makers, and tablets.

His speech is a fast slurry and struggles to project his voice. He doesn't control his breathing properly which causes him to lose his breath when communicating with his peers. That is why he has been assigned to the singing class which he enjoys; he wishes he would feel less anxious and frustrated due to his mobility and communication issues.

is a Renfrewshire resident and a married mum of two; she is 64 years old, she is calm and introverted, none the less she is open to conversation. She used to work as a public servant managing a department in the Paisley areas when a Stroke hit her, this affected her Speech, motor movement and stiffness especially in the left side of her body, and quite often she feels muscular pain. She uses a walking stick to get around. However, she and the DRC bus to commute 3-4 times a week to the centre.

Her favourite sessions are the singing group and the self-running. However, she participates in diverse ones depending on what she would like to do on the day. Her frustrations are her mobility issues, anxiety and low mood.

She is interested in finding ways to fight her anxiety and low mood. It is interesting for me to see that even if she struggles on constructing long sentences or articulating dialogue when speaking, she enjoys Visiting the singing group, achieving great performance in this activity.

She owns a smartphone and uses emails and social media, she also watches television and listens to the radio, in my observation her response to media it's quite normal for what we could expect in somebody her age.

Albert lives with his family in Renfrewshire, he is in his early forties, was born with cerebral palsy, and he experiences very limited movement and motor issues, to communicate he uses a speaking machine, a board with letters. He lives with his family, and in his spare time, he likes watching action movies. He assists to the centre using the bus 4-5 times a week and likes assisting to different sessions or groups mixing them up.

Maggie, she is in her early sixties, she is married and has a daughter and two grandsons. She is calm and reserved; she suffers from Heart and kidney conditions, faces memory lost, hearing, speech and

wishes to use her hands to interact with things, and she is very determined when it comes to complete tasks, her daughter normally helps her find patterns online and order materials for her to knit.

Aubrey, she is a woman in her early fifties. She suffered an intense stroke four years ago and had been assisting the centre for that amount of time, she can only say yes or no, she uses a motorized wheelchair speech, because of her dysphagia she relies on a soft diet, and even she can stand to move with small steps she can't really walk. She likes visiting the arts and craft sessions, alternative health. She feels more relaxed when filling books with colours; I guess having something to do helps her keep away unhelpful thoughts. Her response to media within the regular spectrum.

visual impairment. She walks with a stick and refuses to use a wheelchair even if walking causes her fatigue and faces stiff muscles that limit her mobility.

She visits the centre 3-4 times a week and enjoys knitting pieces for her baby grandsons in the self- running groups; she also likes sewing, the art group and the art group. She likes building things with her hands, therefore apart from the singing class all the other classes she assists to are mainly related to crafting. She

Personas:

These archetypes were created originally for my personal use, to reflect and understand better my users and use them as a reminder for who I was building this project for.

"I am gonna knit him a wee pair of mittens"

Monika is a widow, she lives 2 minutes away from her oldest daughter in Johnstone, She also has a son who moved to "America" for a job who comes back to visit in her words "Every blue moon", she used to run a cornershop in her area, however since her husband died she sold the place to somebody else.

She has attended the DRC for more than 2 years, She comes almost everyday and participates in groups like the self-running, sewing, book club and Tai -chi, lately she has been attending the tablets class as she got a new Ipad her son bought her so he could videochat with her.

She is always sharing knitting patterns with her friends at the centre, and commenting on how cute this baby clothes are..

She suffered a stroke 7 years ago, this resulted in Aphasia and motor problems in the left side of her body and acute pain sometimes, During the week when she is not in at the centre, she goes to physical therapy. at home she uses crutches to move around, however she needs a wheelchair if she is to leave her house.

Because of her condition she tends to feel anxious and melancholic at times, She likes using her hands to interact with things this helps her focus and not think too much.

Name: Monika Webster
 Age: 60
 Occupation: Retired
 Area : Renfrewshire
 Personality: Reserved

Handicapped Wheelchair Woman Images, Stock Photos & Vectors | Shutterstock". 2018. <https://www.Shutterstock.Com/Image-Photo/Happy-Disabled-Handicapped-Senior-Woman-Wheelchair-104110319>. https://www.shutterstock.com/search/handicapped_wheelchair_woman

"I like watching movies and making friends"

Peter lives with his Parents, just few minutes away from the disability resource centre in Paisley, he assist to the centre three or four days a week. His younger sister drives him to the centre when she goes to work, normally he comes back in the afternoon with the bus.

He has attended the DRC for more than 5 years, He is open to visit any group at the centre as long as he can be around other people and join the banter. His favourite group is the singing group.

He likes getting involved in activities and events organised by the centre, the other day he was in charge of picking the BINGO numbers, he brought luck to Emilia, who shouted "BINGO", and gained 10£.

He watches some action and comedy movies, his favourite actor is Jackie Chan. He also likes going to the park and watch people and dogs play.

He was born with cerebral palsey, he is extroverted but suffers of some speech impedements but enjoys listening to others, he uses a electric - wheelchair.

Name: Peter Brown

Age: 35

Occupation: DRC

Area : Renfrewshire

Extroverted.

² Alamy Foto Stock. 2018. *Man with Cerebral Palsy In His Motorized Wheelchair Laughing While In His Kitchen*. Image. <https://www.alamy.com/stock-photo-man-with-cerebral-palsy-in-his-motorized-wheelchair-laughing-while-66124106.html>.

"Can I help you?.."

Camilla suffered a mild stroke 6 years ago, she used to manage a store in a local mall, the stroke left her struggling with fine motor movement, and a weakness on the left side of her body. She also had to relearn how to speak and walk, she can now walk and speak properly however the weakness in one side of her body persists.

At the moment she has a part time job in a bookstore in Paisley, and also assist to the DRC in quality of volunteer, for 2-3 days a week, she helps in the centre with paperwork and organising events, she says this has helped her to recover confidence in the work place. She also involves herself in crowdfunding activities at the centre for example organising raffles to pay for daytrips for the users and facilitates sessions when the regular staff members are not in.

She lives with her younger sister and her twenty years old niece, Camilla cannot drive due to her motor abilities but she and her sister enjoy visiting family members and local trips on their free time, she really enjoys boat trips on the lake.

She comes across as a friendly person but also she can be very reserved. Sometimes she can feel a bit sad and depressed. Her mobility issues and freedom limitations can surely make her feel uncomfortable with herself.

She wishes to travel and visit places she has never been in.

Name: Camilla Pearce

Age: 49

Occupation: Volunteer

Area : Renfrewshire

Reserved.

Pixabay. 2018. *Woman Serious Bored*. Image. <https://pixabay.com/en/woman-serious-bored-satisfied-2385789/>.

"I enjoy engaging in activities related to world events, and technology"

Ronald used to teach math at Paisley's Grammar school, now he enjoys his golden years as retiree. He lives with his wife. His two daughters are married and live around Glasgow area, they come to visit often. He and his wife are very happy one of thir daughters just gave birth, and one of them just gave birth.

He suffered a fall last year and had to start using crotches, his bones have become weaker and thinner, doctors have diagnosed him with osteoporosis. His hearing is not what it used to be, but in the other hand he is energetic and he is able to run small errands, however he gets tired and requires assistance to go shopping or visiting friends.

He has attended the DRC for less than a year, he attends the centre three days a week, and he has made a few good friends already in the iPad class which is his favourite, he also attends the computing class and the movie makers group, he found a new hobby on taking pictures of his grandson.

Even tho he doesnt always understand how things work he has a curious mind and welcomes technology, he has recently discovered VR and he was quite impressed watching immersive videos or interactive experiences on the headset.

Name: Ronald Dolan

Age: 65

Occupation: Retired

Area : Renfrewshire

Calm and friendly demenour.

For the image source please look at *Smiling Woman Wheelchair*. 2018. Image. <http://www.handyinclusiva.com/producto/campera-mujer/>.

	<i>"Believe in your dreams"</i>
<p>Name: Rose Buchanan</p> <p>Age: 25</p> <p>Occupation: Student</p> <p>Area : Renfrewshire</p> <p>Reserved.</p>	<p>Rose lives with her Parents and older sister, they have a puppy called Travis She is currently completing her undergrad at UWS in scripting and filmmaking, and assits to the centre in quality of volunteer.</p> <p>She has attended the DRC for more than 2 years, She comes twice a week to help in the photography and the movie makers groups. Her favourite part of the day is when she sees that "Wow" face of everyone when they see the movies edited. As a hobby she also runs a youth blog where she talks about young peoples struggles.</p> <p>She suffers of dwarfism due to mild muscular distrophy, meaning that her legs are disproportionally smaller than the rest of her body, she uses a weelchair. She mobilises with the Paisley Council bus to go to the centre and her friends or relies on her mother or sister to drive her around.</p> <p>Her biggest frustrations is to see disabled people's rights not being respected, for example dirty disabled bathrooms, or parking spaces used by the non disabled.</p> <p>She wishes to find an outlet to show people how disabled people live and create empathy among the non disabled.</p>

For the image source please look at *Smiling Woman Wheelchair*. 2018. Image. [http://www.handyinclusiva.com/producto/camera- mujer/](http://www.handyinclusiva.com/producto/camera-mujer/).

"Let me tell you about that time..."

Emilia used to work for the local council authority, now however she is retired. She lives with her son, his wife and daughter. She has a cat called Arthur. her friends describe her as bubbly and warm.

She suffered a stroke 5 years ago, this resulted on light motor control issues (Ataxia), her limbs have become weaker due to a condition known as paresthesia she also feels pain. She is able to mobilize herself around the house. But requires assistance to go shopping or visiting friends.

She has attended the DRC for less than 4 years, she relies on the council bus to visit the DRC, four mornings a week, at lunch time she goes for lunch with her family, her favourite class is the Taichi session, other than that she normally attends classes where she can interact with friends and pass her time.

She can feel very anxious at times, she wishes to go to interesting places.

Name: Emilia Wilson
Age: 60
Occupation: Retired
Area : Renfrewshire
Friendly and Chatty.

6 LoveToKnow. 2018. "Senior Wheelchair User. Image. https://seniors.lovetoknow.com/Clothing_for_Wheelchair_Users.

“Produce”

A Conversational interview.

At this point, the attendee should have been halfway through the “Meet and greet” phase, where we meet, set the study attendee(s) in place, read the information sheet, and set at ease before the interview. From this point onwards, we will loosely follow the below structure.

Before placing the headset on:

How are you feeling today?

Would you mind tell me your age?

What sessions do you normally visit at the DRC?

Could you tell me if you face any mobility challenges in your everyday life?

What things do you find difficult to do?

Have you ever used VR before?

Do you know Virtual reality can be used to go virtually to different places?

Explain that the use of VR for disability is the development phase. However, the success of these types of studies are promising.

Explaining the exercise and what is the intention.

Ask them if they have ever done VR – if not explain how some people might feel dizzy during or afterwards, this is normal and goes away if you close your eyes for a few seconds, if this problem persists, please raise your hand, and I will provide aid.

Place headset and record user’s reaction, the recording methods are written observation and Image / Audio Recording.

Take the headset off and debrief: Tell me, explain to me, describe.

The “debrief” is about having a conversation that would draw a comparison with the initial conversation, to provide an insight into how or if the VR experience has influenced the participant’s sense of health and wellbeing.

How was the experience? - If so, why? If not, why not? Which one was your favourite? – why?

How do you feel after the experience?

Did you feel like being there?

Were there specific moments or instances that were particularly affecting?

Were you conscious of your challenges during the experience? – if not how did that make you feel? Is there any place you would like to go to, that you have not gone because of any mobility issues? **End of workshop**

Criteria for the study

Introduction:

With the purpose of gauging the impact of Virtual Reality experiences among volunteer members of the DRC community, to understand their relationship with immersive digital experiences. I will deliver a research workshop session today using mobile VR media, to gain an insight into how the use of digital representations of natural scenarios accompanied by breathing guided meditation might improve the health and wellbeing of DRC members.

General procedure for the workshops:

Research agenda: The purpose of the research interviews is to document the feelings and responses of the participants from the Disability Resource Centre in Paisley to selected VR experiences.

Employing qualitative interview methods, the attendees will in a semi-structured manner, have a conversation conducted by the researcher, in which he will use interpersonal skills such as questioning, conversing, and listening.

Before the interview - there will be enough time for the attendees to be put at ease and to explain the workshop to them.

Recording methods: The interview observations from the researcher will be recorded in writing; there might also be Audio / Video recording of the session throughout the workshop.

Procedure: Participation will be voluntary and individual; the workshops will take place from 10:30 – 4:00 in an area free from distraction.

I will pitch the study to the participants, explaining aims, the duration time (25 min approx), the three stages of the session, and that if they are interested, I will leave them with an information sheet and book a slot on the day for them. When it's their time, I will come, and with the assistance of a staff member, I will take them to the study space to start the research session.

The first phase is to meet and greet the participants. In this first phase, the scope is to set the participant at ease, where he/she will be greeted and brought to the room to start the workshop.

The researcher will read or have read to them, the participant information sheet, explaining who is involved and how the experiment will be conducted and reported. The initial conversation and questioning will move from general questions to more specific questions depending on the conversation development. (10 min approx.)

The second phase is the facilitation of the VR experiences. With the permission of the participant and once it has been ascertained that there are no obstacles to the workshop proceeding, the researcher will arrange the setup and fit the VR headset over the attendee taking care to attend to and record any specific challenges presented by the participant's disability. During the participant's experience, the researcher will be taking notes on the observations of the participant's during this time. (10 min approx.)

The third phase is the debriefing; it will follow a similar format as phase one (semi-structured conversation), where the main intention is to find out how the participant felt after experiencing VR media in the context of their wellbeing. (10 min approx.)

Participant Information Document

I would like to invite you to take part in a research study. Before you decide to become involved, you need to understand why the research is being done and what it would involve for you.

Please take time to read the following information carefully and ask questions if anything you read is not clear or would like more information. Take time to decide if to take part or not.

“Produce” - an immersive experience using natural environments and guided breathing meditation will be tested today as part of a doctoral project with the involvement of the University of West Scotland, in partnership with the University of Edinburgh and the Disability Resource Center (Paisley). For this academic research fields such as ethnography, social care, psychology and interactive visual arts (Creative Computing) are used with the aim of exploring possible associations between the use of Virtual Reality and the improved wellbeing of the individuals with disabilities.

The Director of Studies is Professor Nick Higgins, and the supervisors are Professor Richard Coyne of the Edinburgh University and Paul Cameron who is the DRC organisation partner contact.

The researcher conducting this study is Jesus E. Russian. If you have any questions about the experiment in the future, please contact me on.

The study will only require a very limited amount of information from participants and will focus on gathering responses to a select number of Virtual Reality experiences.

- **Why have I been invited?**

You have been invited to take part in this study because you are a DRC user.

- **What do I agree with?**

I have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet; I have been given the opportunity to ask questions and have had them answered to my satisfaction; I agree to take part in this project; I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason during the session; I give my consent to have pictures and film taken, and be used as data.

Before ○ / After ○

What Comfort/ Pain emoji represents best how you are feeling?

Choose a word according to your mood?

How was the experience?

How did the experience make you feel?

Did you feel like being there?

Did any scene bring you memories?

Did you feel as if you forgot reality for some time?

Do you **think** Concentration, Memory games like this could be used at the DRC?

Which One was your favourite and why?

Aquarium

A

B

C

“Xanadu” – Game design document Foreword:

The DRC workshops provided me with useful insight into the DRC’s clients response while encountering different types of iVR media; this was helpful in terms of establishing the foundations on regards of the type of experiences I would be creating.

I realized there was a mood improvement when they were interacting with visualizations that provided an instant visual narrative. But also, other meaningful elements to them were stories and the interest to learn about other places, and this came up in the workshops with the virtual tours. A common denominator in serious games is storytelling as. Generally, people are prone to better understand and communicate concepts through it⁴⁸; stories make knowledge more meaningful. Because “Storytelling” allows us to inhabit a character's point of view, and this can challenge our perspectives or help us learn.

Immersive media have changed storytelling to “Story experiencing”. Through the sense of “Presence”, we experience that sensation of being somewhere else when using a head-mounted display and somehow inhabiting somebody's reality. And not only presence but VR is the only type of media where the user can experience embodiment trough motion tracking with a handheld controller. The embodiment can evoke real feelings to the point of changing the way we think about others⁴⁹ or about our environment, and this is because VR, unlike any other media, closes the gap between knowledge and experience.

Game Concept:

The word “Xanadu” refers to an idealized place; it is a place that is beautiful or delightful, the purpose of this game is to inhabit the perspective of a God, with the purpose of creating the ideal place for your creatures to inhabit.

A biome is a community of plants and animals that have common characteristics for the environment they exist in. Your mission as the God of this island is to create a biome starting with the plants aiming to lure animals into your island, the way to do this is to create the right conditions in the biome using different plants. A helpful voice might give you hints on how you can go to the next level by unlocking another creature; this can be done by finding the right combination of tiles. the player starts with an empty desert island and depending on the combination of tiles you will unlock animals; the final goal of the game is to unlock all the creatures for that biome before the time is up.

My intention with this experience is to allow the DRC client to receive validation by creating different environments with their choices of plants, flowers, rocks, water, and soil, discovering different animals along the way. And just like a mandala, the island will refresh after you exit the game.

The embodiment of the players will in this game is a “Hand”, as in the hand of God. While the embodiment is limited to only a hand; this is common in VR games given the limitation of this type of media, the view will be FPS (First Person-Shooter). This game provides a visual narrative to learn about conservation and the importance of other living creatures and the fragility of a biome giving it an educational meaning beyond entertainment. But also, this correlates to question one regarding the exploration of virtual environments, embodiment, presence, and the perceived wellbeing they might experience by the agency afforded by this media, opening new lines of enquiry on regards of the cultural benefit of VR when implemented in a community such as the DRC.

10 -12 minutes experience, the dioramas are in the diagrammatic popular “Low-Poly” style, simulating real 3D spaces with 3D spatialized audio. These polygonal tridimensionality spaces

simulate nature's own "Soft Fascination" stimuli, like the song of birds, the breeze caressing the leaf of trees, or the sound of water allowing the user to feel as immersed as possible in the scene. Moreover, there are animals and when interacting with them trigger diegetic audio.

Production:

Going through the ideation process, I took in consideration different types of interactions devices, i.e., the Leap motion or game console controllers but finally due to the simplistic mobile nature of the project I chose to confine the project within the OCULUS and its controller.

I will start by doing a basic paper prototype and building UX scenarios using scripts to test with the users at the centre and will try finding other ways of co-design to integrate their voice into the project. This experience can be done using UNITY using and the Oculus plugin; the low-poly models can be purchased in a third party or at the UNITY asset store. I will be looking to use other third- party assets such as audio clips or music to finalise this prototype.

“Discovery” – Game design document Foreword:

This is the second iteration of this idea, for the first iteration see “appendices”, I needed to find an option to encompass their requirements, a solution that would empower them to access iVR media in a fun and engaging way while also generating wellbeing. This was when I realised that table-top games were not part of the DRC schedule and the few board games around the place were never used.

The “Concentration” game genre branches out into a myriad of sub-genres, among the most popular sub-genres, are “Solitaire”, “Crosswords” and “Match-up” also called “Memory Challenge”. These games provide a framework for individuals and groups to enhance their cognitive abilities, among the benefits we can find concentration improvement, visual memory training, the increment in short memory, attention to detail and vocabulary.

Game Concept:

Memory loss and cognitive challenges are common denominators among stroke survivors, and it is estimated that about one-third of the survivors will develop it. And not only them, but older people are also likely to suffer from it too, and this condition can interfere with the normal functioning of the individual, the use of memory games has been linked with the flourishing of the mind allowing for better mental well-being.

“Discovery” is a solo card “Match-up” memory challenge, this is a serious game; the target audience is mixed gender, but majority female aged forty-five or over, with mobility issues and in many cases cognitive and emotional challenges; this is a card game in which all of the cards are

laid face down on a surface, and two cards are flipped face up over each turn.

The goal of the game is to turn over all pairs of matching cards. But there is a twist, the most compelling feature of the game is the iVR enhancement, by using an HMD every time you match the pairs, to celebrate you winning there is a small digital animation to let you know you have made it.

The idea is to allow the users to team up to discover turn by turn a digital environment, united with a visual narrative. After the player had untapped and discovered all the pairs, the game allows the player(s) to visualize a natural wonder related to the tiles, the theme in the scenario could possibly change to drive re-playability.

With this artefact, I could explore the impact AR interaction can have in the mood of the participants when used to drive connection among them and determine if this type of activity is the best manner to implement this sort of media as a part of a group or a session at the DRC.

Design:

Virtual reality is an immersive interactive experience where the real-world is left behind to be transported to a new environment of objects using computer-generated images, sounds or haptic feedback. "Serious games" can be defined as games designed for a goal other than for entertainment purposes.

The intention behind "Discovery" is to create a Match-up card game, using VR / 3D animated lowpoly style assets, the reason behind this choice is due to the popularity of low poly elements as a well-established Art-Style in digital games, this style focuses on simplicity and flat colours, making it perfect for "Mobile" graphics real-time rendering, this is very important because this application needs to run smoothly and also have a nice and engaging graphic style other games found at DRC including same or similar style are "Crossy Road", "Monument Valley", "Minecraft".

One of the Challenges I am to undertake is to use participatory methods to allow the DRC stakeholders to co-author the piece with me; I will do this by visiting the art class and asking them to help me co-create and co-design the physical part of the tabletop game adding this way a sense of ownership.

The cards are cardboard cards, from one side all the cards look the same from the other side, every card has a pair, after shuffling the deck the x number of cards are laid facing down.

Audio in video games is very important; there will be Dynamic Audio reacting to the user's choices and the environment. Also, diegetic sounds referring to dialogue or real animal sounds, for example, I will also include non-diegetic sound in the form of music. The sound will aim to trigger a sense of adventure and exploration.

Production:

This experience can be developed using Unity, first I will develop a paper prototype to play with the users at the centre, and then I will start practising rendering the images and the animations in the cards. The low-poly models can be purchased from a third party or the UNITY asset store and then be modified to the needs of the project if needed using the UNITY animation tools or 3D models rigging. I will be looking to use other third-party assets such as audio clips or music for this prototype

History of games:

It is believed that during the Neolithic era, ancestral societies played a predecessor of the modern game called “Mancala”, as seen Rollefson, 1922. Neolithic societies used it as a form of mental challenge and pastime (Crist, 2016, p. 232). “Mankala” how it is also known, comes from the Arab word to move (“Naqala”) (Rollefson, 1992). It is a two-player boardgame, featuring a “Count and Capture” mechanic, and it is believed to represent a theme of agriculture (Sowing) and landscape. It portrays a land lot that as the game progress it is turned into a fruitful field through clearing, cultivating, irrigation and gathering. This game is still played today in Africa and the Americas. It is believed it arrived at the new continent through slave trade, and today there are more than hundred versions of it (Crist, 2016) . it worth noting that this game’s believed period of birth coincides with the age of early agriculture and the rise of civilization known as the Neolithic revolution (Culin, 2011).

It is known that before recorded history (40,000 B.C.), religious shamans used sticks and bones as a form of divination rituals, and these then was used for hunters and then the common people for gambling, and then this became dice. The oldest dice was found in Iran dating 985 B.C. These artifacts were widely used in ancient India, Greece, and Rome. There are accounts of Romans invoking the goddess “Fortuna” before throwing the dices, showing ritualistic dimensions when gambling (Schwartz, 2006).

In ancient Egypt, Senet, the game of passing, was a popular game which dates from 2620 B.C. This is a game that features strategy, position, and chance. The winner was the first person to move all the pieces off the board, simulating the passing to the afterlife. It is believed that the Royal Game of Ur, a predecessor of backgammon, comes from the same period. Both games acquired a religious or esoteric status among players at the time and are the first board games in recorded history (Crist, 2016).

A predecessor of football originated in China under the name of Tsu Chu around 5000-300 B.C. In this game, only using their feet, players had to kick a stuffed leather ball through a hole. Across history, there have been other embodiments of this game, in regions like Mesoamerica, South East Asia, Greece and Europe, in every region creating variations of the same game, even if there is not a clear conection among them (Goldblatt, 2008).

Playing cards appeared in Europe around the 1200s, probably imported from Korea, China or the Middle East. Taking the shape of a deck of cards and they were played among all social levels. They were also used for divinatory purposes as the Tarot, this was invented in the late 1430s by newly adding illustrated cards called triumph and the fool. The fool changed during the 1800s to become “the joker” making a transition from a tarot card to a mainstream salon game. In these european salone games it’s common the player can only see the cards they hold, similar to Majhon and Dominoes (Parlett 2017).

The game of “Chaturaṅga” was born in the courts of the Gupta Empire of India. The game was the first game in recorded history to adopt a militaristic allegory in a board game. It had the purpose to teach strategy using as a representation the military divisions of Raja, Mantri, Infantry, Cavalry, Elephantry, and Chariot. It thrived during the 6th century in India, and then spread and evolved via cultural trading to Africa and Europe and become during the 1700s-1800s the game of Chess that we know today, changing the previously mentioned pieces to King, Queen, Rook, Bishop, Horse & Pawn (Murray 1985)(Wilkinson, 2016).

The 1850s, in the industrial revolution era, allowed for the propagation of more affordable cardboard made games such as checkers, Ludo, and the game of the goose, propelling the games & toy industry in the west. During the first half of the 1900s, a proto monopoly was born. The Landlord's Game (1906), a forerunner of Monopoly, was created by Elizabeth J. Phillips, with the attempt to explain the economist Henry George's single tax theory and raise awareness of the dangers of Capitalist methods of renting lands and taxes, but also she created a set of rules where the players would compete against one another for the monopoly of the squares. "Her vision was an embrace of dualism and contained a contradiction within itself, a tension trying to be resolved between opposing philosophies. However, and of course, unbeknownst to Lizzie at the time, it was the monopolist rules that would later capture the public's imagination." (Guardian, 2015).

During the 1930s, the game was bought by a game maker and acquired international acclaim; then, this game was used within another game, the Game of War. During the Second World War, self-care kits were distributed under the Geneva Convention to British Prisoners of War by fake charities that were set up by the Allies. These care kits contained sundries such as "games and pastimes." What the enemy did not suspect was that many Monopoly boxes contained escape-aid items such as compasses, maps, and money, effectively helping some prisoners to escape. During this period, other games that could teach and educate were born, like the war and strategy game "Stratego" (1920) and the Lexia and spelling game "Scrabble" (1938), both featuring elements of competition (Alea) and space negotiation (Donovan, 2018).

Drawing on both on T.S Eliot and McLuhan (Murray, 2006) we can assert that the way we perceived previous media or artwork is directly influenced by a new one. In the 20th century computer media would shift gaming from boards to pixels. Wolfe indicates that the advanced period of recreation began by the end of the 1950s, by way of an array of "wargaming" simulations and new instructive hypotheses that focused on dynamic cooperation, for example, experimental learning, acknowledging the influence of games such as Chess and Chaturanga (Wolfe 1998). The year 1961 saw the birth of the first interactive game at MIT. It was called "Spacewar", and it was an early version of a spaceship shooting genre; it did not have any purpose other than entertaining. Therefore, another game holds the first interactive serious game title. During the mid-1970s, the rules for "LIFE" (1970) was the first serious game in the digital format; it featured a zero-player game, where after the hacker inputted few lines of code, it featured pixelated cells that would simulate the life spam of living cells, with the hope the algorithm would produce them in a way that they would not isolate or overcrowd on one another, causing them to 'die'. If the algorithms were correct, the cells could reproduce, evolving into beautiful emerging patterns. This game had to be implemented using code, effectively teaching players about coding, and while not realistic, players would also learn about cell reproduction (Gardner 1970).

Scenario one:

Situation: There is a second wave or the uncertainty over the safety of customers and staff members at the DRC, the centre is not allowed to open before the end of September, therefore I won't be able to continue the field studies. So, I will have to modify the focus of my research.

Result: This will have a high negative impact as I will not be able to gather the final feedback for my studies, as a result, I will have to substantially change the thesis structure.

Scenario Two:

Situation: The DRC is not allowed to open; however, I can interview the staff members using telepresence (Skype, Zoom) and by showing them videos and pictures I can gather some feedback.

Result: While I will have some material to make conclusions, I would still miss the DRC customer's feedback. This would significantly change my final thesis, as I will not be able to demonstrate that the use of VR can bring increased health and wellbeing as I will only use non-immersive media.

Scenario Three:

Situation: The DRC can open in September; therefore, I can interview one by one the staff members and customers alike using telepresence (Skype, Zoom) and by showing them videos and pictures I can gather some feedback.

Result: While I will have some material to make conclusions, I would still miss the use of VR headset this would significantly change my final thesis as I will not be able to demonstrate that the use of VR can bring increased health and wellbeing as I will only use non-immersive media. – Also, with the necessary set up needed for this customer, this will be very time-consuming.

Scenario Four:

Situation: The DRC opens in September; however, I am allowed only to interview staff members using VR, However, I can instruct a staff member on the use of VR headsets and this member can run a small workshop with me in telepresence (Using Skype or Zoom).

To me, this is the most interesting of the scenarios, because while I will not be there personally, I can set up the equipment and paperwork for the day to then have somebody else administer it. So, I would be using VR and gather the required feedback and collect enough data causing minimum.

Scenario Five:

Situation: All is well, and I am allowed by the end of September to run the workshops with the DRC customers and Staff members.

Result: **while** highly unlikely, this would be the best option.